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**D5.5 Global pathways & EU response: A 2nd
European Regional, National and Sectoral
assessment**

WP5 – Transforming Europe

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is released publicly, available on the project website. It serves as a key reference point for policymakers on Paris-compliant deep mitigation pathways for the EU, as well as the impact of the current policy context towards realising key climate targets, and national regional and sectoral implications. Finally, it also informs climate-economy modelling scientists on a realistic current policy baseline, under the recent COVID-19 situation.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

With the EU policy context fast evolving in the light of recent challenges, such as COVID-19, there is a need to guide and scientifically underpin key policymaking decisions to ensure that ambitious targets are realised. In this context, this deliverable presents a set of EU scenarios that achieve the 55% emission reduction target by 2030 and net zero by 2050, on top of a realistic current policies baseline, essentially ensuring that EU effectively manages its contribution towards achieving the Paris Agreement target. Produced by a diverse set of models in a multi-model setup, the scenarios are assessed in terms of their implications on key climate, economy, and energy indicators, as well as their impact on the member-state and sectoral level. Key results including the role of key mitigation options such as renewables, electrification, carbon capture and storage, negative emissions technologies, and hydrogen are validated from the lens of stakeholder input, as elicited in a series of national stakeholder workshops in Europe. Finally, the analysis further delves into niche modelling areas, including updates on the current policies baseline scenario in the light of COVID-19 and the "Fit for 55" package, long-term strategies for the Agriculture Forestry and Land-Use sector, and the evaluation of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

PARIS REINFORCE will develop a novel, demand-driven, IAM-oriented assessment framework for effectively supporting the design and assessment of climate policies in the European Union as well as in other major emitters and selected less emitting countries, in respect to the Paris Agreement. By engaging policymakers and scientists/modellers, PARIS REINFORCE will create the open-access and transparent data exchange platform I²AM PARIS, in order to support the effective implementation of Nationally Determined Contributions, the preparation of future action pledges, the development of 2050 decarbonisation strategies, and the reinforcement of the 2023 Global Stocktake. Finally, PARIS REINFORCE will introduce innovative integrative processes, in which IAMs are further coupled with well-established methodological frameworks, in order to improve the robustness of modelling outcomes against different types of uncertainties.

NTUA - National Technical University of Athens	GR	
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Cambridge - University of Cambridge	UK	
CICERO - Cicero Senter Klimaforskning Stiftelse	NO	
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E4SMA - Energy Engineering Economic Environment Systems Modeling and Analysis	IT	
EPFL - École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne	CH	
Fraunhofer ISI - Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research	DE	
Grantham - Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine - Grantham Institute	UK	
HOLISTIC - Holistic P.C.	GR	
IEECP - Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy Stichting	NL	
SEURECO - Société Européenne d'Economie SARL	FR	
CDS/UnB - Centre for Sustainable Development of the University of Brasilia	BR	
CUP - China University of Petroleum-Beijing	CN	
IEF-RAS - Institute of Economic Forecasting - Russian Academy of Sciences	RU	
IGES - Institute for Global Environmental Strategies	JP	
TERI - The Energy and Resources Institute	IN	

Executive Summary

This report contributes to the evaluation and guidance of EU climate action as it has been significantly revised in the last years to comply with Paris Agreement. It does so by analysing a set of multi-model produced Paris-compliant deep mitigation pathways for the EU and assesses them in terms of their climate, economy and energy impact, as well as shedding light on national, regional and sectoral implications.

First, the analysis delves into global scenarios to understand the role of the EU towards realizing the Paris Agreement goal. Global simulations have shown that current EU commitments are stronger than optimal EU mitigation pathways delivered by these global models, essentially ensuring that the net-zero targets of the EU currently pursued are in line with the Paris Agreement, and also manage to alleviate the NETs required in the second half of the century, which is a key component of the feasibility of the ambitious global temperature goals.

Second, the analysis delves into the EU climate action context by presenting two deep mitigation net zero scenarios on top of a current policies baseline. The NZE scenarios for the EU produced by the diverse set of models employed have highlighted different mitigation strategies between models. A key diverging point concerns the use of NETs, as a large mobilisation of NETs, and particularly BECCS, will reduce emissions mitigation in hard-to-decarbonise sectors, such as transport but is also associated with a high feasibility risk. Nevertheless, we highlight that several models reach the NZE target in 2050 with a moderate use of BECCS (or no use at all in some cases).

Delving into sectoral and macroeconomic aspects of the NZE scenarios, we show that, the decarbonisation of the European final energy use is achieved through increasing electrification, as well as by an important fuel shift towards bioenergy, accompanied by significant energy savings in some models. From a sectoral perspective, the electrification of the final energy uses under the emissions constrain is allowed by a European power generation that becomes carbon neutral between 2035 and 2045, supported by a large deployment of RES (80% in 2050) and particularly of solar and wind energy. The macroeconomic mitigation cost of the NZE objective is relatively moderate under the condition that advanced mitigation options are available.

Finally, additional analysis of the EU climate action, in niche areas of the modelling and policy context is performed. In particular, this report presents the third update of the “where is the EU headed” baseline scenario in the light of the “Fit for 55” package, showing that the EU updated policy for 2030 will allow reaching the 55% reduction compared to 1990, but it may be more challenging for achieving the RES share (even more with the REPowerEU ratcheting) as well as the energy efficiency objectives. Focusing on the MS LTSs for AFOLU, an area usually underrepresented in core modelling studies we conclude that, despite that MSs have evaluated the role of AFOLU to reduce GHG, more effective policies and measures should be planned and implemented to enhance the AFOLU contribution toward climate neutrality. Finally, a modelling exercise about the EU CBAM implementation shows that CBAM may reduce carbon leakage and alleviate potential competitiveness loss of EU energy-intensive industries (EII) but it also shifts the economic burden on non-European countries, especially on LDCs. Thus, the use of CBAM revenues to support the energy transition in LDCs may reduce carbon leakage and improve their welfare with relatively the same costs as the EU.

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1 Introduction

Following the Paris Agreement (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2015) and the subsequent scientific works (e.g. Rogelj, et al., 2018), the European Union has successively revised its climate ambition, firstly, with its Long-Term Strategies, aiming at becoming a carbon neutral economy in 2050 (European Union, 2020a) and secondly, its 2030 GHG emissions targets (European Commission, 2021a), confirming its international leadership in terms of climate action (Oberthür and Dupont, 2021) and followed rapidly by some other large emitters, such as the United States of America or China (Carbon Action, Tracker, 2022). Knowing that the 2020 net GHG emissions of the European Union amounted to 3.35 GtCO₂eq. (-32% compared to 1990), reaching -55% in 2030 and net zero emissions in 2050 appears as an unprecedented challenge for the EU (European Environmental Agency, 2022).

The transformation of the European economy to compliant with its climate goals, implies the deep transformation of the European energy system (Capros et al., 2019) and embraces a set of research questions to tackle regarding the impact of current policies (Nikas et al., 2021a), the massive deployment of existing low carbon technologies (Ortar and Ryghaug, 2019; de Glas et al., 2020), the mobilisation of close-to-market technologies (IEA, 2021) or game-changing innovation (Wilson, 2017), and overcome existing barriers to such large deployment (Zappa et al., 2019; Doukas et al., 2022) as well as the limitation of some potentially related side-effects on sustainability (Dhar et al., 2019; van de Ven et al., 2020) as adverse economic impacts (Markkanen and Anger-Kraavi, 2019). In this context, it is essential that the community of Integrated Assessment Models supports decision-making (Doukas et al., 2018). In broad modelling exercises including nine different kinds of models (from global to European models, from macro-economic to energy-system or from wide-system to sector-specific models), we assess a set of scenarios regarding EU climate action towards a carbon-neutral economy in 2050, with an intermediate target of 55% emissions reduction in 2030. We explore a large set of models' results to show how our models respond to some key issues that have been considered essential during several stakeholders' workshops to map the climate transition in the EU, such as electrification of the final energy uses, or the role played by negative emissions technologies (NETs).

We start this report with a synthesis of global mitigation scenarios, run by PARIS REINFORCE global models in Section 2. We focus on the CO₂ emissions pathways in the EU to compare with the new European Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC). We continue in Section 3 with the implementation of a set of mitigation scenarios for the EU: a post-COVID19 "Current Policy" scenario, called WWH21 (drawing on the WWH reference scenarios presented in D5.3), and two deep decarbonisation scenarios, both reaching a 55% reduction in 2030 and NZE in 2050. We firstly analyse in detail the results at an EU level, pointing out the emissions reduction dynamics between sectors, the role of carbon capture and storage technologies and the evolution of the energy mix. We pursue the analysis with an in-depth look into five key sectors: two supply-side sectors (power generation and hydrogen) and three demand-side ones (industry, buildings and transports), of which the later cluster benefits from a more detailed analysis allowed by the sector-specific models. We continue with a focus on the potential socio-economic impacts of these NZE scenarios in the EU and we carry on with a transversal view of their impacts at a Member States level. In section 3, our results are cross-checked with the insights and guidance delivered by stakeholders during national workshops. Finally, section 4 compiles three deepening analyses regarding the current EU climate policy, the first one is a multi-model analysis of the "Fit for 55" proposal (European Commission, 2021a) and where will the EU head by maintaining this mitigation effort, the second analysis assesses the Members States' long-term strategies for the agriculture, forestry and land use (AFOLU) sectors, and finally, the third presents an assessment of different implementations of an EU carbon border adjustment mechanism realised with the GEMINI-E3 model. We then conclude the report with a synthesis of the results.

2 Insights from 1st run of global mitigation pathways

In a first step, global models have run two sets of scenarios: the first ones are forecasting scenarios showing what emission levels will be according to current policies and NDCs and the second are back-casting scenarios in which models either define optimal paths according to different carbon budgets or capping emissions to be compliant with these carbon budgets. We shortly present below the deep mitigation pathways to confront them with the European Union's (EU) current climate action and ambition. For a detailed analysis of where the EU heading with its current climate policy see Nikas et al. (2021a) or Deliverable D.5.3¹.

2.1 WP7 mitigation pathways

In addition to the forecasting modelling exercise realised by global models (Sognaes et al., 2021), based on a harmonised set of assumptions (Giarola et al., 2021), WP7 delivered deeper mitigation scenarios aiming at limiting temperature increase to 1.5, 1.75 or 2°C compared with pre-industrial temperature. We present below a summary of the scenario protocol (see deliverable D7.6 for further details)².

For models running up to 2100, it applies end-of-century CO₂ budgets consistent with three temperature outcomes by 2100. The socioeconomic drivers are the same as those used for the reference scenarios (Giarola et al., 2021).

The scenarios have these design characteristics:

1. They will follow current policies to 2025 (as per the reference scenario), and then apply that level as a minimum ambition level thereafter.
2. They will deliver cumulative emissions end-of-century budget targets consistent with 2°C, 1.75°C and 1.5°C budgets as outlined in Table 1 (3 variants). These emission budgets are supposed to achieve the said temperature targets with a 50% certainty.
3. The fourth scenario will be a variant of the 1.5°C scenario, including the additional constraint of global net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 (1 variant).

The SR15 budgets, budgets identified as compatible with a limitation of global temperature raise of 1.5°C (Roglej, et al., 2018) include CO₂ emissions from land use and forestry (FOLU) that assume a net-zero FOLU end-of-century cumulative emissions budget. This means that post-2050, FOLU becomes a sink absorbing all 2000-2050 CO₂ emissions from FOLU. Finally, non-CO₂ emissions, for example from agriculture, are assumed to follow a path that is consistent with the emission budgets and temperature targets mentioned in Table 1, but they are not part of the model comparison exercise.

Models that only run to 2050 will have to apply carbon prices at a level sufficient to place their emissions trajectories within the range of 2050 emissions from the models that do go to 2100 (GCAM, MUSE, and TIAM) in each scenario. Then, the three 2100 models that ran the Transient Climate Response to cumulative CO₂ Emissions (TCRE) budgets for each temperature outcome will provide the range of 2050 emissions from each run. Based on these ranges, the 2050 models will apply the 2018-2050 budgets informed by the models that go to 2100 by taking the average of those models.

¹ Deliverable "D5.3 - Global pathways & EU response: a 1st European regional, national and sectoral assessment"

² Deliverable "D7.6 - Report on the reference and policy scenario modelling results"

Table 1 summarises the scenario names and carbon budgets of the four scenarios.

Table 1: Constraints in each scenario on i) emissions and ii) year of net-zero, to be run by models going to 2100.

Scenario name	Approx. warming since 1850-1900 (°C)	Remaining CO ₂ emissions budget (GtCO ₂ from 1.1.2018) (50 th TCRE percentile*)	Year of net-zero CO ₂
CP_1p5	1.50	580	none
CP_1p75	1.75	1040	none
CP_2deg	2.00	1500	none
CP_1p5_net0	1.50	580	2050

* TCRE: transient climate response to cumulative emissions of carbon, assessed by AR5 to fall likely between 0.8–2.5°C/1000 PgC (Collins et al., 2013), considering a normal distribution consistent with AR5 (Stocker, 2014). Values are rounded to the nearest 10 GtCO₂. Source for emissions budgets: IPCC SR15 Ch 2, Table 2.2

2.2 Key figures

Figure 1 shows the global CO₂ emissions projections in three scenarios (CP_1p5, CP_1p75 and CP_2deg) for all models involved. In the stringent scenario limiting the temperature rise to 1,5°C (CP_1p5), the CO₂ emissions decline from 2020 across all models. However, the speed of decline differs. Emissions declined from 34.8 GtCO₂ in 2020 to 22.4 GtCO₂ in 2030 (TIAM) and 31.4 GtCO₂ in GCAM. In 2050, global CO₂ emissions range from 10.9 GtCO₂ in ICES (all covering emissions from energy) up to 15.2 GtCO₂ in GCAM representing a reduction of about -68% and -56% in comparison to 2020 respectively.

After 2050, all models running up to 2100 mobilise net negative emissions from 2070 to respect the carbon budget of the CP_1p5 scenario. In 2100, CO₂ emissions from energy and processes are about -23.4 GtCO₂/y. in GCAM (the model with the largest negative emissions), -15.6 GtCO₂ in TIAM, and -11.5 GtCO₂ in MUSE.

Compared with other scenarios, the CP_2deg scenario that limits temperature rise to 2°C (with 50th TCRE percentile), sees global CO₂ emissions remaining relatively stable for two models (TIAM and GCAM) up to 2030 (around 35 GtCO₂/y.) and declining more slowly for the other models. The weakest value is for ICES, at 21.6 (energy only). In 2050, the global CO₂ emissions range between 27.5 (GCAM) and 18 GtCO₂ (ICES), representing a reduction of -20% and -48% respectively with respect to 2020. After 2050, only GCAM shows negative CO₂ emissions by the end of the century.

Figure 1: Global CO₂ emissions from energy and processes in WP7 first run of deep mitigation scenarios

*: ICES CO₂ emissions cover only energy-related CO₂ emissions, Historical values from Friedlingstein et al. (2021) and cover all fossil CO₂ emissions.

At an EU level, global CO₂ emissions also decline. In 2030, the CP_1p5 scenario shows CO₂ emissions from energy and industrial processes ranging between 2.92 (TIAM) and 1.8 GtCO₂ (MUSE) that corresponds to a respective reduction of about 35% and 60% with respect to 1990 (Figure 2). In 2030, the median value is approximately 2.6 GtCO₂ *i.e.* -40% w.r.t. 1990. In both the CP_1p75 and CP_2deg scenarios, these median values are slightly higher at 2.7 GtCO₂/y. In 2050, the deviation between models becomes more apparent with the CP_1p5 scenario showing a maximum CO₂ emission level of 1.6 GtCO₂ (ICES) and a minimum of -0.1 GtCO₂ (MUSE), and a median of approximately 1 GtCO₂, *i.e.*, -75% w.r.t. 1990. In the CP_1p75 scenario, this median value is significantly higher at 1.75 Gt, *i.e.*, -60% w.r.t. 1990. In the CP_2deg scenario, the emissions reduction is much less pronounced, with emission levels of 2.1 GtCO₂, *i.e.*, -50% compared to 1990. Once again, the models deliver a relatively large range of CO₂ emissions reduction in 2050 in the EU for the 2°C scenario. TIAM shows a very limited reduction of approximately -30% w.r.t. 1990 (3.2 GtCO₂) and MUSE shows more than double with -65% (1.5 GtCO₂).

Figure 2: CO₂ emissions from energy and processes in EU28 in WP7 first run of deep mitigation scenarios

*: ICES emissions only cover energy-related CO₂ emissions

Comparing the CO₂ emissions results from the global models with the European Union's current climate ambition demonstrates that the EU commitments are beyond the optimal mitigation burden found by the models up to 2050 and that relies on important negative emissions in the second part of the century (see Deliverable "D7.6 - Report on the reference and policy scenario modelling results"). It shows that EU climate ambition considers its historical responsibility (Rocha et al., 2015; Leimbach and Giannousakis, 2019), creates a fairer climate transition (Raupach et al., 2014; Robiou du Pont et al., 2017) and assumes a leading role (Oberthür and Dupont, 2021; Schreyer et al., 2018). Indeed, the European Union has fixed a net zero emissions target in the Long-Term Strategy (European Union, 2020a) that implies close-to-zero CO₂ emissions from energy and processes in 2050 (Capros et al., 2019). Excluding MUSE in the CP_1p5 scenario (and to a lesser extent in the CP_1p75 scenario), all other models deliver less stringent CO₂ emissions mitigation pathways than the EU Long-Term Strategy (Figure 2).

3 Core scenarios

Since 2015, many regions around the world have revised their National Determined Contributions (NDCs) to comply with the Paris Agreement (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2015; Climate Action Tracker, 2022). The EU has therefore scaled up its GHG emissions reduction target for 2050, with its Long-Term Strategy (European Union, 2020) striving for Net Zero Emissions (NZE), and for 2030, with the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019a) and the subsequent “Fit for 55” proposal (European Commission, 2021a) aiming to achieve 55% emissions reduction compared to 1990, replacing the previous 40% target (European Council, 2014).

Achieving these ambitious targets in the EU will imply large changes for European economies, particularly in their energy systems. The exploration of how this transition towards a carbon-neutral economy could take place has been assessed in several modelling studies such as by Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) that have been completed by Hainsch et al. (2022) for scenarios focusing on the power sector. The European Commission (2018a) assessed different pathways toward NZE in the EU by combining different sector-specific modelling tools and Kattelmann et al (2021) coupled an energy-system model with a macroeconomic model. Other studies have developed scenario-based assessments grounded in a single model (e.g. Nijs et al., 2019) whereas some have relied less on modelling tools and have instead combined multiple different approaches (e.g. IRENA, 2018; Matthes et al., 2017). None of these studies, however, deliver a detailed multi-model analysis that incorporates several different models, that differ in their theoretical backgrounds, granularity and technological representations and details, thereby missing the opportunity to offer a diverse set of potential pathways and to better highlight critical issues (Nikas et al, 2021b).

We intend to achieve this by mobilising seven different modelling tools: one global partial equilibrium model (GCAM), two global general equilibrium models (GEMINI-E3 and ICES), one European macro-econometric model (NEMESIS), one European energy-system model (EU-TIMES) and two sector-specific models on buildings and industry (FORECAST) and transport (ALADIN) in order to assess backcasting scenarios for GHG emissions pathways that make the EU towards NZE by 2050.

3.1 Methodology

WP5 previously produced scenarios based on the “Where are We Headed” (WWH) scenario protocol developed by Sognaes et al. (2021), using a set of harmonised socioeconomic parameters (Giarola, et al., 2021). Part of these scenarios has been published in Nikas et al. (2021a) and further details can be found in deliverable D5.3. These scenarios deliver CO₂ emissions and energy consumption pathways considering current climate change mitigation policies, up to 2030, and maintaining (or continuing, depending on the scenario design) the mitigation effort thereafter. These WWH scenarios were used as reference scenarios for the rest of the project’s modelling exercises. They were designed before the COVID-19 pandemic; therefore, we updated them using input from Cassetti et al. (under review), where post-COVID-19 GDP data was produced for EU countries with the NEMESIS model using updated fossil fuel prices projections, showcasing potential impacts of the pandemic on the EU energy system and the subsequent GHG emissions trajectory to 2030 (see deliverable D5.3 for details).

To go beyond these WWH scenarios, we explored deeper climate change mitigation scenarios in the EU and, particularly, scenarios that are compliant with the Paris Agreement.

As stated, the European Union (2020a) has revised its Long-Term Strategy with the objective that the European economy becomes carbon-neutral in 2050 (or zero net GHG emissions, including carbon sink from Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry, LULUCF). Furthermore, to reinforce its 2030 climate change mitigation action, the

European Commission has launched the 2030 Climate Target Plan (European Commission, 2020a), in the framework of the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019a) that puts a reduction target for the EU GHG emissions of at least 55% in 2030 compared to 1990, as well as developing a set of policy proposals, the “Fit for 55” package (European Commission, 2021a), to comply the EU climate policy framework with this new objective.

To deliver an assessment of how the EU could achieve these ambitious targets, we developed a set of Paris Agreement-Compliant (PAC) scenarios for the EU that reflect these updated EU climate ambitions named “PAC core scenarios”. Table 2 summarises the European GHG emissions reduction targets in all scenarios³. As discussed previously, in the *WWH21* scenario, the EU objectives are based on existing policies in the European legislation (in October 2021) of which the aim is a reduction of GHG emissions by at least 40% in 2030 compared to 1990. This includes a cap of -43%, in the EU-Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS) sector and -30% in the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) sector in comparison to 2005. We developed two more ambitious scenarios, the “*NZE Benchmark*” scenario, in which the EU ambition is to achieve 55% GHG emissions reduction in 2030 compared to 1990 and net zero emissions in 2050. In this scenario, each model reaches the target with the least-cost mitigation options. In the “*NZE EU Policy standard*”, the overall EU targets for GHG emissions mitigation are the same but incorporate upgraded burden sharing of -61% (w.r.t 2005) in the EU-ETS sector and -40% in the ESR sector, as in the “Fit for 55” proposal. We detail a bit more each scenario below. Further details of each scenario are described below.

Table 2: Synthesis of the main GHG emissions reduction targets of the EU27 in the PAC core scenarios

	WWH21*		NZE Benchmark**		NZE EU Policy standard**	
	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050
GHG emissions reduction (w.r.t 1990)	-40%		-55%	Net Zero Emission	-55%	Net Zero Emissions
EU-ETS GHG emissions reduction (w.r.t. 2005)	-43%	carbon price equivalent			-61%	Adjusted to reach NZE EU-level target
ESR GHG emissions reduction (w.r.t. 2005)	-30% (w. national targets)				-40% (wo. national targets)	-80%

*: GHG emissions scope excludes LULUCF and includes intra-EU aviation in EU-ETS; **: GHG emissions scope includes LULUCF and international transports.

3.1.1 The WWH21 scenario

We updated the GDP projections for EU27, the United Kingdom, Norway, Iceland and Switzerland as well as the international fossil fuels prices following Cassetti et al. (under review)⁴.

- GDP projections, from 2021 onwards, have been generated by the NEMESIS model in April 2021 for each

³ Specific assumptions have been implemented in sector-specific models, they are available in Annex I.

⁴ The paper is available in the deliverable D5.3, section 3.2.

Member States (MS) individually,

- Fossil-fuel price projections were generated in May 2021, combining IEA (2019) and IEA (2020a) forecasts (see Annex I for additional details)

Table 2 summarises the main EU GHG emissions reduction objectives in the *WWH21* context, and Table 27 in Annex I describes the indicative CO₂ emissions caps for models that do not cover LULUCF and/or non-CO₂ emissions.

For models in which the UK is individualised, we refer to Table 28 and Table 29 to implement a specific UK mitigation pathway in the *WWH21* context. In comparison with the previous *WWH* scenario (Nikas et al., 2021), the only noticeable difference is the removal of the UK from the EU-ETS market and the implementation of a UK-ETS market in which the caps differ from what we could expect from national UK caps in the EU-ETS (ICAP, 2021). Besides the UK-ETS has similar sectoral coverage and function⁵ and the ESR target is assumed to be the same.

This *WWH21* scenario is used as the counterfactual for all other PAC scenarios when relevant, mainly for the socio-economic impact assessment of NZE scenarios.

3.1.2 The NZE Benchmark scenario

Models use the pre-defined set of socioeconomic and technoeconomic parameters developed for the *WWH21* scenario. The "*NZE Benchmark*" scenario implements the current most ambitious GHG emissions reduction targets proposed by the EU, *i.e.*, -55% in 2030 compared to 1990 and NZE in 2050 as EU emissions caps. The models that cover all GHG emissions include the GHG emissions caps detailed in Table 2. For models with limited emissions coverage, we propose three sets of assumptions for the non-covered emissions by combining different levels of non-CO₂ and LULUCF emission contributions to the global GHG reduction targets: low, medium and high. The more the non-CO₂ and LULUCF emission reductions contribute to the total GHG emissions targets, the lower the CO₂ emissions cap is (see Table 3).

In this scenario, the GHG emissions cap is reached by the implementation of the least-cost option in each model, (*e.g.* a unique carbon price or the least-cost mitigation options), and no other specific climate policy should be implemented (no EU-ETS, etc.) from 2020 to 2050 (as far as the policies could be identified and removed). Thus, this scenario will deliver the model-optimal GHG (or CO₂) mitigation pathway to reach the 55% GHG emissions reduction and NZE targets in 2030 and 2050, respectively.

For models that include the UK as a separate region, we still refer to Table 28 and Table 29 in Annex I (for models limited to CO₂ emissions) to implement the UK NZE mitigation pathway. This path is based on the "*Balanced Net Zero Pathway*" scenario of the 6th Carbon Budget report of the Climate Change Committee (2020) that set a GHG emissions reduction of 55% in 2025, 68% in 2030, 78% in 2035 and NZE in 2050, including LULUCF emissions and international bunkers after 2030.

As models do not deal with GHG emissions from "international bunkers", the scope is limited to GHG emissions from intra-EU aviation in this scenario.

Finally, by default, we assumed no change in the rest of the world in comparison with the *WWH21* scenario.

⁵ In fact, there exists some small differences, such as the introduction of a floor price (see ICAP, 2021).

Table 3: Detailed emissions caps for the EU27 in the WWH21 and “NZE Benchmark” scenarios

GtCO ₂ eq.			WWH21 (-40% wo LULUCF & w intra-EU aviation)	2030			2050		
	1990	2005		2030 Climate Target Plan (-55% w.r.t 1990)			Net Zero Emissions		
				Contribution of non-CO ₂ and LULUCF emissions to GHG mitigation			Contribution of non-CO ₂ and LULUCF emissions to GHG mitigation		
				Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
CO ₂ (wo LULUCF & w in't transport)	4.05	4.00		1.81	1.90	1.99	-0.27	0.01	0.22
CO ₂ (wo LULUCF & w intra-EEA aviation*)	3.91	3.79	2.58	--	--	--			
Non-CO ₂ (wo LULUCF & w in't transport)	0.98	0.80	0.58	0.58	0.54	0.49	0.50	0.30	0.25
LULUCF	-0.21	-0.31	-0.23	-0.23	-0.27	-0.31	-0.24	-0.31	-0.47
Total (w LULUCF & w in't transport)	4.82	4.48		2.17	2.17	2.17	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total (wo LULUCF & w intra-EEA aviation*)	4.89	4.58	2.94						

Source: historical values (EEA, 2021a); LULUCF emissions authors' calculation based on: 2030-low: current LULUCF regulation (European Commission, 2018b) 2030-medium: average of low and high, 2030-high: new objectives from 'Fit for 55' (European Commission, 2021b), 2050-low: scenario "Baseline" in European Commission (2018a), 2050-medium: idem 2030-high and 2050-high: scenario "Life1.5LB" in European Commission (2018a); Non-CO₂ emissions authors' calculation based on: 2030-low: scenario "Mix-50" from European Commission (2020a), 2030-medium: average of low and high, 2030-high: "All bank" from European Commission (2020a), 2050-low: EU reference scenario 2020 (European Commission, 2021c), 2050-medium: scenario "Combo" in European Commission (2018) and 2050-high: scenario "Life1.5LB" in European Commission (2018a)

*: GHG emissions from intra-EEA aviation are assumed to represent 40% of total GHG emissions from international aviation in 1990, and 2005: the average value from 2015 to 2019 based on EEA (2021a; 2021b).

NB: Original data have been corrected from the UK when relevant.

3.1.3 The NZE EU Policy Standard scenario

Similarly to the “NZE Benchmark” scenario, the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario explores the EU GHG emissions mitigation pathway proposed by the EU (-55% in 2030 and NZE in 2050) but, in addition, it implements the EU-level policy instruments as proposed in the “Fit for 55” policy package (European Commission, 2021) regarding burden sharing between the EU-ETS and ESR sectors. To do so, in all models, the GHG emissions cap in the ESR sector in 2030 is set at -40% in comparison to 2005 and -80% in 2050 (i.e. -20 pp per decade) and the GHG emissions caps in the EU-ETS sector are then deduced to reach the total EU GHG emissions targets (see Table 2). In models that do not cover LULUCF emissions, the “medium” case of emissions projections from the “NZE benchmark” scenario is used. This method is also used for models that do not cover non-CO₂ emissions. With these assumptions, the EU-ETS emissions reduction leads to -61% compared to 2005 in 2030 and negative emissions in 2050 (see Table 4)

Again, for models that individualise the UK, we refer to Table 28 and Table 29 (for models limited to CO₂ emissions) to implement the UK NZE mitigation pathway. We do not define specific burden-sharing between UK-ETS and non-UK-ETS, thus the UK pathways are similar to the “NZE Benchmark” scenario.

Once more, the scope is limited to GHG emissions from intra-EU aviation.

Finally, by default, we assume no change in the rest of the world in comparison with the *WWH21* scenario.

Table 4: Detailed GHG emissions caps in EU27 for the “NZE EU Policy standard” scenario

<i>GtCO₂eq./y.</i>	1990	2005	2019	2030	2050
EU-ETS	-	2.07	1.44	0.81	-0.24
EU-ETS (incl. NO+IS+LI)	-	2.09	1.47	0.82	
ESR (w. In't transports)	-	2.73	2.44	1.64	0.55
LULUCF	-0.21	-0.31	-0.25	-0.27	-0.31
Non-CO ₂ emissions (wo. LULUCF and w. in't transport)	0.98	0.79	0.69	0.54	0.30
Total (w. LULUCF & w. in't transport)	4.82	4.48	3.63	2.17	0.00

Source: historical values (EEA, 2021a and 2021b); *LULUCF and non-CO₂ emission: same as “medium” case in the “NZE-benchmark” scenario*

NB: Original data have been corrected from the UK when relevant.

3.1.4 Modelling armoury

Among the models involved in the PARIS REINFORCE project, seven of them are used to run the PAC core scenarios in this exercise. Table 5 presents each model and summarises its main characteristics⁶.

⁶ For more details, please refer to the I2Am PARIS Platform (www.i2am-paris.eu) or Deliverable D5.1 and D7.1,

Table 5: Main characteristics of the models' armoury

		ALADIN	EU-TIMES	FORECAST	GCAM	GEMINI-E3	ICES	NEMESIS
Type of model		Bottom-up sector perspective	Energy system model	Bottom-up sector perspective	Partial equilibrium	General equilibrium model	General equilibrium model	Macro-econometric
Team running the model		Fraunhofer ISI	E4SMA	Fraunhofer ISI	BC3	EPFL	CMCC	SEURECO
Version used		--	E4SMA-EU-TIMES 1.0	--	GCAM-PR 5.3	GEMINI-E3 7.0	ICES-XPS 1.0	NEMESIS 5.1
Geographical coverage for EU		EU27 (MS-level) +UK+NO+CH	EU27 (MS-level) +UK+NO+CH	EU27 (MS-level) +UK+NO+CH	EU15+EU12 (excl. HR)	EU-28 (region)	DE+Benelux+GR+FI+ CZ+IT+FR+ES+PL+ SE+Rest of EU+UK	EU27 (MS-level) +UK+NO+IS
Sectoral granularity	Macroeconomic	No	Exogenous (as drivers)	Exogenous (as drivers)	Exogenous (as drivers)	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Agriculture	No	Energy requirements only	No	Detailed	As an economic activity with non-CO ₂ emissions	As an economic activity	As an economic activity
	Energy supply	No	Very detailed	No	Very detailed	Detailed for PG	Detailed for PG	Detailed for PG
	Industry	No	Detailed	Very detailed	Detailed	As economic activities	As economic activities	As economic activities
	Transportation	Very detailed	Detailed	No	Detailed	As economic activities and Households expenditures	As economic activities and Households expenditures	As economic activities and Households expenditures
	Buildings	No	No	Very detailed	Detailed	As economic activities and Households expenditures	As economic activities and Households expenditures	As economic activities and Households expenditures
	Land uses	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No

Table 6 indicates which scenarios have been run by each of the models. Not all models can run all scenarios. Sector-specific models did not run the “NZE Benchmark” scenarios, because their sectoral focus does not allow differentiating between both NZE scenarios. Furthermore, it was infeasible for the ICES model to run the “Benchmark – Low” and “Benchmark – Medium” cases due to limited mitigation options. Finally, as GCAM deals with LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions, it was not relevant to run all three “NZE Benchmark” cases.

Table 6: PAC core scenarios run by the models

	WWH21	NZE Benchmark			NZE EU Policy Standard
		Low	Medium	High	
ALADIN	✓				✓
EU-TIMES	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FORECAST	✓				✓
GCAM	✓		✓		✓
GEMINI-E3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ICES*	✓			✓	✓
NEMESIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

*: ICES has limited mitigation options compared with other models and it only covers CO₂ emissions from energy. Thus, it only ran the “NZE Benchmark – High” scenario with lower CO₂ emissions reduction targets and it does not fully reach emissions targets in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario with CO₂ emissions of 414 MtCO₂ in 2050 instead of a target around net zero emissions. Consequently, we do not comment on ICES results for the emissions.

We present below the results of the PAC core scenarios. Starting with a detailed exploration of the EU emissions pathways by looking at the burden sharing between the EU-ETS and ESR sectors, the speed of sectoral decarbonisation, the penetration of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and carbon prices, we continue by showing how the EU energy system evolves in terms of primary and final energy consumption and fuel mix. Thereafter, an in-depth analysis of how decarbonisation takes place in several sectors (power generation, H₂ production, industry, buildings, and transport) delivers a general picture from the entire modelling ensemble, followed by a more detailed analysis supported by a sector-specific model. Our analysis continues with an assessment of the socioeconomic impacts, mainly regarding GDP and employment impacts. Finally, we conclude our analysis of the PAC core scenarios by looking at some key results at a Member State level.

3.2 Economy-wide level

3.2.1 GHG burden sharing

In GCAM which includes all GHGs and LULUCF, the latter's contribution to GHG emissions reduction in NZE scenarios ("NZE Benchmark" and "NZE EU Policy Standard") is expected to be lower than the assumptions used by other models. This reduction is between 158 and 198 MtCO₂eq/y in 2030 in comparison to 220 and 310 MtCO₂eq/y and between 56 and 156 in comparison to 236 and 472 MtCO₂eq/y in 2050, respectively (numbers referring to EU27+UK perimeter). Non-CO₂ emissions projected by GCAM are close to the pessimistic case of the assumptions, *i.e.* the "NZE Benchmark Low" scenario. Whereas in GEMINI-E3, non-CO₂ emissions are in line with the medium values used in the "NZE Benchmark Medium" scenario. In 2050, NZE scenarios show non-CO₂ emissions in the range of 522-554 MtCO₂eq/y (GCAM) and 286-311 MtCO₂eq/y (GEMINI-E3). Models' projections are in the range of our assumptions (286-564 MtCO₂/y, EU-27+UK perimeter).

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 show some differences in the potential pathways of non-CO₂ emissions (excl. LULUCF). Indeed, in the NZE scenarios, GEMINI-E3 indicates that CH₄ emissions, of 583 MtCO₂eq in 1990, can be reduced by up to 75% in 2050 whereas this potential is limited to 45% in GCAM. Similarly, N₂O emissions, at 342 MtCO₂eq in 1990, declined by about 60% in GEMINI-E3 in the NZE scenarios and by about 40% in GCAM. Both models agree on the potential for F-Gases mitigation of -90% in the NZE scenarios.

Figure 3: EU GHG emissions by gas in PAC core scenarios

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. Filled bars are model results and empty bars are exogenous assumptions from Table 3 and Table 4. Historical values come from EEA (2021a). ICES is not included because it delivers only CO₂ emissions from energy.

The results for the burden sharing between gases show that the assumptions used for the LULUCF contribution

to NZE in 2050 (with carbon sinks between -235 and -420 MtCO₂eq) are out of GCAM's emissions range, with a maximum contribution of -155 MtCO₂eq. Similarly, the mitigation of non-CO₂ emissions projected by GCAM is less ambitious than our assumptions, but it is in line with the pathway foreseen by GEMINI-E3. The large difference between the assumptions based on the literature review for LULUCF emissions (see Section 3.1 in deliverable D.5.3) and GCAM projections in NZE scenarios is explained by the large deployment of biomass energy in GCAM resulting in increased biomass at the expense of the LULUCF sink. Furthermore, the LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions in the NZE scenarios, between 367 and 490 MtCO₂eq in 2050, imply negative CO₂ emissions. In our assumptions, these emissions (between -220 and +268 MtCO₂ with a medium case at almost zero) do not necessitate mobilising systematically Negative Emissions Technologies (NETs).

3.2.2 EU-ETS Burden sharing

Besides the burden sharing of the GHG emissions between gases, another major question regarding EU climate policy is the emissions caps in the EU-ETS and ESR sectors. Before the EU's ratcheting of the climate ambition, the 2030 target for EU-ETS and ESR were -43% and -30% respectively in comparison to 2030, corresponding to the global GHG emissions reduction of 40% compared to 1990. With the increased ambition of at least 55% emission reduction in 2030 compared to 1990 (European Commission, 2019), the European Commission has proposed the 'Fit for 55' proposal to cap the EU-ETS and ESR emissions at -61% and -40% respectively in 2030 with respect to 2005 (European Commission, 2021d and 2021e). These values come from the impact assessment realised by the European Commission (European Commission, 2019) which assessed different scenarios regarding mitigation and policy options. In a comparable scenario, the emissions reduction ranges between -57% and -67% in the EU-ETS sector and from -39% to -41% in the ESR sector. Alternatively, Zaklan et al. (2021) proposed a new cap for the EU-ETS sector to be compatible with the goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C based on the IPCC SR1.5 emission pathways (Rogelj, et al., 2018). In a cost-optimal scenario, the authors found a reduction of 61% in 2030 in the EU-ETS sector compared with 2005.

Figure 4: EU-ETS and ESR emissions reduction in 2030 and 2050 (w.r.t. 2005) in the "NZE Benchmark" scenarios

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. Non-CO₂ emissions in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS are exogenous assumptions from Table

3.

Figure 4 shows the emissions reduction in the “NZE Benchmark” scenarios in the EU-ETS and ESR sectors in 2030 and 2050. In 2030, models deliver GHG emissions reductions relatively in line with the European Commission proposal, with emissions declining between 57 and 75% (60% as median value) in the EU-ETS sector, and between 37% and 45% in the ESR sector (median value of 40%). In 2050, models show great divergence: GCAM significantly favours emissions reduction in the EU-ETS sector with a large deployment of NETs, with -158% compared to 2005 in the EU-ETS and -55% in the ESR. On the other hand, NEMESIS shows more moderate emissions cuts in the EU-ETS, whilst still mobilising NETs (between 104% to 120% in 2050), and between 74% and 79% compared to 2005 in the ESR sector. The median value of the EU-ETS emissions reduction in 2050 is 118%, *i.e.* around 370 MtCO₂ (EU27 perimeter), and 76% in the ESR sector (*i.e.*, around 650 MtCO₂).

All models show that, in scenarios with lower emissions mitigation from LULUCF and non-CO₂, the EU-ETS emissions reductions are higher: first, to balance non-CO₂ emissions (included in the ESR sector) and, second, because reducing emissions in the EU-ETS sector through NETs seems more cost-efficient in the models.

3.2.3 CO₂ emissions per sector

Figure 5 presents information on the speed of decarbonisation by sector, model and scenario. In economy-wide models, the decarbonisation of the economy is driven by a rapid reduction of CO₂ emissions in the energy supply sector. This reduction is primarily caused by the rapid decarbonisation of the power sector, as well as, a global reduction of fossil-fuel consumption. In the “NZE Benchmark” scenarios (only the “Medium” case is plotted in Figure 5), the energy supply sector becomes carbon-free between 2035 and 2045 (except for ICES, where it reaches 95% in 2045 in the “NZE Benchmark – High” scenario). In EU-TIMES, GCAM and GEMINI-E3, NZE is achieved in the supply sector in 2035 in all the “NZE Benchmark” scenarios. In NEMESIS, NZE occurs between 2040 and 2045. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, in which the EU-ETS emissions mitigation pathway is more constrained, the supply sector reaches carbon neutrality marginally later, with NZE being achieved between 2035 and 2040 for EU-TIMES, GCAM and GEMINI-E3 and between 2040 and 2045 in NEMESIS.

As GCAM relies largely on negative emissions in the supply sector, the mitigation burden within the other sectors is significantly reduced. For instance, in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario, GCAM reaches a decarbonisation rate of -200% in 2050 (*w.r.t* 1990), allowing more moderated rates of decarbonisation in buildings (-65%) and especially transportation (+7%). Nevertheless in industry GCAM shows a similar decarbonisation rate to the other models. Although to a lesser extent, we also find a similar burden sharing between sectors in the other models. In the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario, the decarbonisation rate of transport reaches -29% in GEMINI-E3 in 2050 (mobilising NETs the most after GCAM); -56% in EU-TIMES; and -79% in NEMESIS⁷. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, CO₂ emissions cuts in the transport sector are slightly bolder, with -9% in GCAM, -49% in GEMINI-E3, -67% in EU-TIMES and -76% in NEMESIS. In ALADIN, the CO₂ emissions pathway shows a more marked evolution, with an important rebound in the post-COVID19 period: 2020- 2025 (+27% in 2025 *w.r.t* 1990), followed by a rapid decline thereafter that continues up to 2050 (-3% in 2030, -74% in 2040 and -94% in 2050).

In the buildings sector, emissions cuts in 2050 in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario are -65% in GCAM, -71% in GEMINI-E3, -92% in EU-TIMES and -94% in NEMESIS, compared to 1990. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, these reductions are significantly stronger in GCAM (-96%) as well as in GEMINI-E3 (-85%), NEMESIS (-92%), and EU-TIMES (-93%). The sectoral model, FORECAST, shows a strong decarbonisation rate of -100% in 2050

⁷ The CO₂ emissions of the transportation sector shown in Figure 5, do not account international bunkers.

with -58% in 2030 and -86% in 2040.

Emissions mitigation in industry nears -90% in 2050 for all models in the NZE scenarios with a range between -60% (NEMESIS) and -73% (GEMINI-E3) from 2030. In FORECAST, CO₂ emissions from industry and processes decline significantly from -27% in 2015 (w.r.t. 1990), reach -55% in 2020, -70% in 2030, -92% in 2040 and -102% in 2050. Thus, compared to the other models, FORECAST shows relatively more ambitious emissions mitigation. It is also the only model that presents negative emissions around the middle of the century.

Finally, in the Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (AFOFI) and other sectors, the models converge towards a CO₂ emission reduction of approximately 85-95% in 2050.

Additional in-depth analyses of the sector-specific emission mitigation are presented in Section 3.3.

Figure 5: EU sector reduction of CO₂ emissions from energy and industrial processes (w.r.t. 1990) in the PAC core scenarios.

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. ICES does not cover CO₂ emissions from Industrial processes. AFOFI: Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (only energy-related emissions).

3.2.4 CCS deployment

Previous analyses of the burden sharing at a sectoral level have shown that the role of NETs in the NZE scenarios is central. Among our models, the use of NETs is limited to Bioenergy with Carbon, Capture and Storage (BECCS). Models do not mobilise or describe other nature-based NETs (e.g. land management) or Direct Air Capture and Carbon Storage technologies (DACCS), nor do they deploy Carbon Capture, Usage and Storage (CCUS) technologies.

The strong reliance of Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) on BECCS to reach deep mitigation pathways that

are Paris Agreement-compliant is well established and at the heart of important scientific debates (e.g Fuss et al., 2014; Anderson and Peters, 2018, Butnar et al., 2020, Fajardy et al., 2019). Below, we explore the results of our analyses, confronting the usage of BECCS with both the geological potential in Europe and existing results for the EU.

Figure 6 shows the deployment of CCS⁸ and BECCS in all PAC core scenarios. In *WWH21*, (BE)CCS deployment is limited in the majority of models. The exception to this limitation is GCAM, where (BE)CCS occurs already in 2030 with 156 MtCO₂. Of this, BECCS makes up 100 MtCO₂ and CCS 35 MtCO₂, with 10 MtCO₂ in industry. In GCAM, (BE)CCS reaches 746 MtCO₂ in 2050, (with BECCS accounting 505 MtCO₂, and CCS accounting for 241 MtCO₂). CCS deployment is much lower in the other models in *WWH21* reaching just 85 MtCO₂ in 2050 in EU-TIMES and zero elsewhere.

Figure 6: Carbon capture and storage of CO₂ emissions in EU in the PAC core scenarios.

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. ICES is excluded because CCS is not an available mitigation option.

Similarly, GCAM shows the substantial deployment (BE)CCS in NZE scenarios with a maximum of 1.9 GtCO₂/y in 2050 in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario (1.6 GtCO₂ of BECCS and 0.3 GtCO₂ of CCS). This represents two-fifths of the EU28’s CO₂ emissions from energy and processes in 1990 and more than half of 2015 overall CO₂ emissions. GEMINI-E3 also deploys a substantial quantity of (BE)CCS technologies with up to 1 GtCO₂/y in 2050 in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario (0.94 GtCO₂ of BECCS and 0.06 GtCO₂ of CCS). EU-TIMES and NEMESIS also mobilise (BE)CCS to decarbonise power generation and industry. However, these models project a lower deployment in the “NZE Benchmark” scenarios, with 500 MtCO₂/y in 2050 in the “Low” case (NEMESIS) and 490 MtCO₂/y in the “High” case (EU-TIMES). Covering only industry, FORECAST also shows important CCS deployment,

⁸ We use CCS for Fossil Fuels Carbon Capture and Storage to differentiate with BECCS.

with 75 MtCO₂ in 2050 the highest value for the sector among models that include this mitigation option. These results, alongside the relationship between CO₂ emissions reduction and (BE)CCS deployment (as plotted in Figure 7), confirm that (BE)CCS constitute an important mitigation option in NZE scenarios. However, they also highlight that there are substantial differences surrounding its deployment between models.

Among the wider literature, Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) compared thirteen scenarios from ten different studies that reached at least 90% emissions reduction in the EU by 2050. In 2050, the total CO₂ captured and stored underground ranges between 0 and 466 MtCO₂/y, which is in line with our EU models (EU-TIMES, FORECAST, and NEMESIS), yet well-below estimates from our global models (GCAM and GEMNI-E3). Capros et al.'s (2019) scenarios that reach NZE in the EU by 2050, which are currently used as reference scenarios by the European Commission (2018) as well as being included in Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), mobilise up to 400 MtCO₂/y of (BE)CCS in 2050. However, DAC technologies contribute an additional 200 MtCO₂/y. Of this 600 MtCO₂/y of captured emissions, half is stored underground, and approximately 250 MtCO₂/y is used to produce synthetic fuels. The rest (around 50 MtCO₂/y) is stored in materials. In an EU power-sector modelling analysis, Pietcker et al. (2021) find no impact of the unavailability of fossil-fuel CCS technologies on the cost of decarbonisation and a very moderate impact on the availability of BECCS. They attribute (Annex III) this result to relatively pessimistic assumptions surrounding plant efficiency and emissions factors of BECCS. Finally, Fragkos et al. (2021) and Kattelman et al. (2021), without detailing the explicit contribution of (BE)CCS, reaffirm its critical role to achieve deep decarbonisation in the EU.

Figure 7: Relationship between carbon capture and storage of CO₂ emissions in EU in the PAC core scenarios (MtCO₂/y.) and CO₂ emissions mitigation effort (% w.r.t. 1990).

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. ICES is excluded because it does not model CCS.

In terms of dynamics, in all models but GCAM (and FORECAST⁹), the deployment of (BE)CCS is relatively marginal in 2030, before accelerating significantly between 2030 and 2040 in GEMINI-E3 and EU-TIMES and between 2040 and 2050 in NEMESIS. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, the cumulative CO₂ emissions captured and stored between 2020 to 2050 are approximately 21.8 GtCO₂ in GCAM, 12.4 in GEMINI-E3, 4.8 in EU-TIMES, 2.7 in NEMESIS, and 1.1 in FORECAST (for industry only). To compare against the estimated potential geological storage in Europe (excluding Russia), Fuss et al. (2018) estimate a range between 20 and 60 GtCO₂. A more optimistic assessment comes from the International Association of Oil & Gas Producers (2019), reporting a CCS geological potential in Europe of about 300 GtCO₂. Of this, Norway accounts for 70 GtCO₂, the UK accounts for 80, and Denmark accounts for 60. More recently, Rosa et al. (2021), considered the issue of the distance between emissions sources and storage sites in Europe, finding that even 200 MtCO₂/y of CCS will prove challenging. GCAM CCS requirements already hit this potential, but the other models also contest the realism of GHG pathways relying too much on CCS. For instance, with around 450 MtCO₂/y of CCS when the NZE target is achieved, projecting NEMESIS results forward leads to 11 GtCO₂ stored in 2075 and 22 Gt in 2100, on the lower end of the Fuss et al. (2018) range.

Furthermore, besides technological and physical limitations, current legislation at the EU level (Nehler and Fridahl, 2022; Geden et al., 2018) and in some EU countries, such as Germany (Beck, 2021), limit or even ban carbon storage on the ground. Some of our models (e.g. EU-TIMES) include these restrictions whereas others do not (e.g. NEMESIS).

3.2.5 Carbon prices

An important indicator provided by models is carbon price(s). According to scenarios and models, carbon pricing can be used when accounting for climate change damages to assess the “social cost of carbon” (e.g., see Nordhaus, 2017 or Wang et al., 2019 for a review), defined as the present-value cost of an additional ton of CO₂ emissions (Pearce, 2003). In our case, the carbon price refers to the marginal cost of GHG emissions mitigation, or like the shadow price of the GHG emissions constraints (Duong and Mainguy, 2009). This is particularly the case in the “NZE Benchmark” scenarios in which no specific EU climate policy is included, even where the models cannot entirely remove all existing climate policies as they cannot identify them, or due to policy overlapping (e.g., energy taxation, vehicles emissions standards, etc.). In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, carbon prices reflect the marginal cost of the mitigation action in the ESR sector and a market price in the EU-ETS sector. Nevertheless, the employed modelling ensemble as a whole cannot deal with endogenous carbon prices, particularly the sector-specific models (ALADIN and FORECAST) in which a mixed approach is used to run the “EU Policy Standard” scenario. Furthermore, in the *WWH21* scenarios, all EU climate policies up to 2030 are included, according to each model’s capability. Thus, the carbon prices, shown in Table 7, are the “carbon price equivalent” as defined in Nikas et al. (2021a), measuring the carbon price(s) allowing to reach the same level of GHG emissions reduction(s) as if all EU climate policies were implemented.

In some scenarios, different carbon prices in the EU exist, such as national ESR carbon prices in the *WWH21* scenario, or European ESR and EU-ETS carbon prices in the “EU Policy Standard” scenario (see Box 1 for a specific calculation of average carbon prices, especially for the NZE cases). Instead, we used the emissions mitigation effort from 2015, rather than the current level of emissions, to avoid issues when emissions tend to zero or become negative.

⁹ FORECAST is not illustrated in Figure 7, and features 12 MtCO₂ in 2030 – already over the 75 Mt deployed in 2050

The calculation of the weighted average carbon prices when emissions tend toward zero (and become negative) causes a problem when the weights are on emissions. To deliver average carbon prices that properly reflect the GHG mitigation burden in NZE scenarios, we proposed a particular calculation that considers the emissions deviations from a reference point as weight. The formula is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{If } Em_{i,2015} - Em_{i,t} > 0 \\ & \text{then } \Delta Em_{i,t} = 0 \\ & \text{else } \Delta Em_{i,t} = Em_{i,2015} - Em_{i,t} \\ Pcarb_t^{av} &= \frac{\sum_i \Delta Em_{i,t} \cdot Pcarb_{i,t}}{\sum_i \Delta Em_{i,t}} \end{aligned}$$

With: $Em_{i,t}$: the emissions in country/sector i at time t ; $Pcarb_i$: the carbon price in country/sector i and $Pcarb^{av}$:

Box 1: Average carbon prices calculation for NZE scenarios

Table 7 shows the average carbon prices in the core scenarios in 2050. As mentioned previously, the two sector-specific models (ALADIN for transport and FORECAST for industry and buildings) do not calculate endogenous carbon prices. The ICES model delivers the highest carbon values among models in *WWH21*, with 2,400€₂₀₁₀/tCO₂eq, owing to the relatively low availability of mitigation options in the model compared to others, and the limited representation of (BE)CCS, hydrogen and synthetic fuels. Further, it emphasises how models must adopt a particular mitigation strategy in order to reach the desired emissions reductions (we develop that point in Section 3.4.1).

In the *WWH21* scenario, the average carbon prices range between 41€₂₀₁₀/tCO₂eq in GCAM to 112€ in NEMESIS. Among the three models that separate the ESR and EU-ETS sectors up to 2050, EU-TIMES and NEMESIS show a higher average carbon price in the ESR sector than in the EU-ETS, with 153€₂₀₁₀/tCO₂eq and 176€ respectively against 52€ and 60€ in the EU-ETS sector. Oppositely, GEMINI-E3 displays a slightly lower price in the ESR sector than in the EU-ETS (32€ compared to 46€). Inter-model comparison in the *WWH21* scenario proves challenging due to heterogeneous emission mitigation efforts among models (see Figure 3).

In the “*NZE Benchmark*” scenario, with a single carbon price in the EU, the carbon values increase when the contribution of LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions to GHG emissions reduction declines. For instance, in EU-TIMES, when this contribution is “high”, the European carbon price reaches 726€₂₀₁₀/tCO₂eq in 2050. This increases to 744€ in the “medium” case and climbs to 2,487€ in the “low” case. Considering that the difference between the “High” and “Low” cases is 480MtCO₂eq in 2050 (*i.e.* 10% of 1990 EU GHG emissions), the influence of these variables showcases the importance of carbon sinks from the LULUCF sector and non-CO₂ emission mitigation in alleviating the marginal mitigation cost in the other sectors. Focusing on the “Medium” case, carbon prices range between 128€ in GCAM and 1,334€ in NEMESIS, with a median value of 824€₂₀₁₀/tCO₂eq.

Average carbon prices in the “EU Policy Standard” scenario are higher than in the “*NZE Benchmark – Medium*” scenario, indicating that, from a modelling perspective, burden-sharing between the EU-ETS and ESR sectors in this scenario is not cost-optimal. All models present different carbon prices in the ESR and EU-ETS sectors, with a price in the EU-ETS being higher than in the ESR sector in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS. Both of these models also place a lower importance on (BE)CCS than either GCAM or GEMINI-E3. In these models, the emissions reduction cap in the EU-ETS sector is too stringent, rendering further mitigation efforts necessary in the ESR sector. This is in contrast to GCAM and GEMINI-E3, for which it is more cost-efficient to reinforce the emissions reduction in the EU-ETS sector and alleviate it in the ESR.

Table 7: Average carbon prices in the core scenarios in 2050

€ ₂₀₁₀ /tCO ₂	WWH21			NZE Benchmark			EU Policy Standard		
	Total	EU-ETS	ESR	High	Medium	Low	Total	EU-ETS	ESR
ALADIN	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
EU-TIMES	102	52	153	726	744	2,487	1,474	1,658	1,225
FORECAST	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
GCAM		41			128		223	85	411
GEMINI-E3	41	46	32	639	904	1,029	2,420	404	4,398
ICES		2,397		45,026	--	--	33,964	23,239	78,652
NEMESIS	112	60	176	871	1,334	2,851	1,920	2,508	1,041

Overall, carbon prices differ significantly between models. When excluding ICES, the European models EU-TIMES and NEMESIS produce relatively homogeneous results with closed prices in the “NZE Benchmark” scenario, and deliver the same message regarding the burden-sharing between the EU-ETS and ESR sectors in the “EU Policy Standard” scenario, asking for a more ambitious ESR cap. On the other hand, the global models GCAM and GEMINI-E3 produce differing results. In GEMINI-E3, average carbon prices are relatively congruent with the European models. Carbon prices from GCAM are significantly lower, with 128€/tCO₂eq in 2050 in the “NZE Benchmark” scenario and 223€ in the “EU Policy Standard”. As shown previously, (BE)CCS is a backstop technology in GCAM (Marcucci and Fragkos, 2015) that limits the marginal cost of emissions abatement at the cost of this technology. Finally, both global models agree on the fact that, with a large mobilisation of NETs, particularly in power generation, the mitigation effort assumed by the EU-ETS sector could be increased for more cost-optimal emissions reduction.

3.2.6 Total primary energy consumption

The deep decarbonisation of the EU implies a substantial impact on its energy system, starting from its total energy consumption. Figure 8 presents the level of Primary Energy Consumption (PEC) in the EU in the core scenarios. In GCAM, the EU PEC is expected to grow in all scenarios between 2020 and 2050, however, this growth is less rapid in the *WWH21* scenario than in the NZE scenarios. EU-TIMES shows relatively moderate energy efficiency improvements in all scenarios. In *WWH21*, the EU PEC is relatively stable between 2020 and 2050, whereas, in the NZE scenarios, EU-TIMES projects PEC reduction between 2020 and 2030, relative stability between 2030 and 2040, and then a slight increase until 2050. NEMESIS shows a similar profile, despite displaying more important energy efficiency gains from 2020 until 2040. Between 2030 and 2040, NEMESIS continues to project a reduction of total EU PEC, with 1,070 in *WWH21* and between 890 and 920 Mtoe/y in NZE scenarios. Thereafter, NEMESIS assessments of EU PEC in 2050 slightly differ between the scenarios. In *WWH21*, PEC shows a continued decline, yet in NZE scenarios, PEC rebounds from 970 up to 1,110. An exception is the “EU Benchmark – High” scenario that sees PEC remaining stable. The ICES model presents energy efficiency gains between 2020 and 2030 in all scenarios, which continues only in NZE scenarios, whereas *WWH21* shows an increase in EU PEC. Finally, GEMINI-E3 presents consistent energy efficiency gains in all scenarios throughout the time period, although this gain is less marked in the *WWH21* scenario. In 2050, the difference between the NZE scenarios is evident, with a minimum of 750Mtoe/y in the “EU Policy Standard” scenario (the lowest value of all models and all scenarios) and a maximum of 890 in the “NZE Benchmark – High” scenario. Nevertheless, this remains lower than PEC projections from the other models. GEMINI-E3 in particular shows important energy efficiency gains compared to the other models, particularly as its EU aggregate includes the UK. Only NEMESIS presents comparable energy savings up to 2040 across all scenarios, but values begin to diverge thereafter.

Energy efficiency is an important pillar of EU climate policy packages, with the Energy Efficiency Directive (RED II

-- European Union, 2018) setting a target of at least a 32.5% improvement in EU energy efficiency for 2030. As the calculation of this target is complex, as it considers “projections of the expected energy use in 2030”, the EU also provides PEC targets in absolute values of 1,273Mtoe for EU27+UK, and 1,124 for EU27. In 2021, upon ratcheting climate ambition as part of the “Fit for 55” package, the European Commission proposed to raise this energy efficiency target to 39% (European Commission, 2021f, corresponding to an absolute target of 1,023Mtoe in 2030 for EU27 (approximately 1,160Mtoe for EU27+UK, own calculation). Based on our models, only PEC projections from NEMESIS are near compliant with the previous European target – with 1,140Mtoe/y in the *WWH21* scenario. In the NZE scenarios, GEMINI-E3, ICES, and NEMESIS reach the -32,5% target in 2030, but only NEMESIS projects PEC compatible with the EU updated target. GEMINI-E3, after correcting for the UK, also appears relatively close to the target yet still falls short.

Figure 8: Total EU primary energy consumption in the core scenarios.

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. Nuclear is harmonised among models and accounted as nuclear heat like in Eurostat, with an efficiency factor of 33%.

To summarise, all models but GCAM project energy savings in the EU between 2020 and 2040, although to different extents. Energy savings are moderate in EU-TIMES (especially post-2030) and higher in NEMESIS, ICES (NZE only), and GEMINI-E3. Between 2040 and 2050, when models mitigate emissions in the harder-to-decarbonise sectors, EU-TIMES, ICES and NEMESIS show a stabilisation or increase of European PEC, due to a high level of penetration of carbon-free electricity. By comparing the different cases of the “NZE Benchmark” scenario in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS, when carbon neutrality in the EU requires stronger CO₂ mitigation effort, namely in the “Low” case, both models project a higher total EU PEC in 2050 than in the other cases. In 2030, EU PEC projections for NZE scenarios range between 1,120 and 1,280Mtoe/y (excluding GCAM, where it reaches 1,800 Mtoe/y). This is in line with scenarios compiled by Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), ranging between 1,176 and

1,428Mtoe/y in 2030 (including the UK, of which the PEC can be estimated at around 150Mtoe in 2030)¹⁰. Similarly in 2050, when excluding GCAM (around 2,150Mtoe), models project a European PEC between 750 (GEMINI-E3) and 1,410Mtoe (EU-TIMES). This range is relatively large but remains comparable with existing scenarios in Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) that show a range of 794-1,451Mtoe in 2050. Finally, the two NZE scenarios, used as reference by the European Commission (2018a), give a European PEC of 1,100 and 1,295Mtoe in 2050 (Capros et al., 2019).

3.2.7 Primary energy by fuel

Here, we present primary energy consumption by fuel for the core scenarios in ten-year increments (see Figure 8). In the *WWH21* scenario, fossil fuels remain dominant in the energy mix across models up to 2050. Nevertheless, oil consumption declines in all models, considerably in GEMINI-E3 (from 638 Mtoe in 2020 to 425 in 2050) to moderately in EU-TIMES (from 465 Mtoe in 2020 to 435 in 2050). This trend is similar for natural gas consumption but with a less marked reduction in all models except ICES (in which reduction is larger at 60% in 2050 w.r.t. 2020). All models converge towards a large reduction of coal consumption in the EU in the *WWH21* scenario between 2020 and 2050. Projections for nuclear consumption show relative stability, except in GCAM, where nuclear increases from 243 Mtoe in 2020 to 413 in 2050 with homogeneous deployment throughout the decades. All other models show either a slight increase in nuclear consumption (EU-TIMES, from 158 Mtoe in 2020 to 190 in 2050) or a moderate decline (NEMESIS, from 190 to 147). All models project relative stability of hydro consumption in *WWH21*, between 28 and 35 Mtoe, except in ICES expecting important growth (from 41 Mtoe in 2020 to 69 in 2050) and seeing hydropower reaching a remarkable 102 Mtoe in 2030. Projections for biomass are significantly different among models —ICES and GEMINI-E3 do not deal explicitly with biomass due to GTAP database restrictions (Aguilar *et al.* 2019 and therefore cannot be commented on. Nevertheless, the other models indicate a growth of biomass in PEC, with a moderate increase in NEMESIS, a marginally greater increase in EU-TIMES, and GCAM showing the most rapid growth. Solar power increases significantly in all models in *WWH21*, except for ICES, in which values are particularly low in comparison. Broadly, the models show solar energy increasing three- to five-fold by 2050. The majority of models display the most rapid development of solar between 2020 and 2030, which is then followed by smaller growth rates. Finally, wind consumption is also expected to grow rapidly in the *WWH21* scenario across all models. The largest deployment (243 Mtoe in 2050) is in ICES; other models, whilst seeing slower growth, still see wind consumption almost doubling by 2050 w.r.t. 2020.

¹⁰ In Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) and Capros et al. (2019) refer to Gross Inland Consumption (GIC) which also includes gross inland consumption from ambient heat and final non-energy consumption from all products total (EEA definition). Thus, GIC is a bit higher than PEC. For instance, in Eurostat (2022a), EU27 GIC equals 1,326Mtoe in 2020 whereas the PEC is 1,236.

Figure 9: EU primary energy consumption by fuel in the core scenarios.

*GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. GEMINI-E3 and ICES do not account for biomass energy. Nuclear is harmonised among models and accounted as nuclear heat like in Eurostat, with an efficiency factor of 33%. *: For ICES, the scenario "NZE Bench. High" replaces the "NZE Bench. Med." scenario.*

In the NZE scenarios, fossil fuel consumption declines rapidly and significantly in all models. Here, we present the values for the "NZE Benchmark – Medium" scenario; the differences among NZE scenarios will be discussed further below. Coal is almost entirely phased out of the energy mix in EU-TIMES, GEMINI-E3, ICES, and NEMESIS. In GCAM, coal consumption declines but not as radically. EU-TIMES, NEMESIS, and ICES also project strong declines in gas consumption. GEMINI-E3 and GCAM display lower gas cuts, due to larger fossil-fuel CCS deployment. In the NZE scenarios, the reduction in oil consumption is less marked than for gas and coal across all models. EU-TIMES and NEMESIS see a partial growth of nuclear from 2020 to 2050 (+37% and +25%, respectively). The role of nuclear is greater in ICES (+50%) and GCAM (+121%), while GEMINI-E3 projects a moderate decline (-20%). Expectedly, renewable energy is considerably exploited to decarbonise the EU energy system. In all models but ICES, the use of hydro in PEC does not grow as rapidly as the other renewables: in EU-TIMES, NEMESIS, and GEMINI-E3, whereas it stabilises in GCAM. In ICES, hydro consumption triples until 2050 (134Mtoe). In all models, biomass consumption increases significantly. This is particularly true for GCAM, which relies strongly on BECCS to reach the net-zero target, and biomass uses for energy represent 235 Mtoe in 2020, 313 in 2030, 511 in 2040, and 802 in 2050. In EU-TIMES, biomass doubles in 2020-2040, reaching 252 Mtoe, and then remains relatively stable until 2050 (267Mtoe). In NEMESIS, the growth of biomass consumption is slower during the two first decades (from 118 Mtoe in 2020 to 176 in 2040) but accelerates onwards to reach 298 Mtoe in 2050. Similarly to other renewables, wind energy is deployed extensively in all models. The largest deployment can be seen in ICES with 370 in 2050, followed by EU-TIMES (254). In NEMESIS and GEMINI-E3, wind energy is also significantly mobilised, however, to a relatively lesser extent (122 and 12 Mtoe, respectively in 2050, *i.e.* around four times more than in 2020). Finally, in GCAM, the deployment of wind in PEC grows slowly (from 64 Mtoe in 2020 to 89 Mtoe in 2050).

Noticeable differences between scenarios stem from different burden sharing between ETS and ESR sectors in the “NZE Benchmark” and “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenarios. For the models in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, in which EU-ETS mitigation effort is more important than ESR mitigation effort (namely EU-TIMES, ICES, and NEMESIS), we observe higher mobilisation of solar and wind, and slightly greater reduction of coal and gas.

In summary, in the NZE scenarios, models achieve EU energy-system decarbonisation by the widescale deployment of renewable energy sources (see Figure 10), with wind, solar and biomass playing a major role, and hydro a limited one. Nuclear is also mobilised, yet its contribution is marginal, and fossil fuel consumption declines significantly (up to -95% for coal, between -60% and -90% for gas, and between -45% and -75% for oil). In addition to cross-model insights, we also see a large divergence between models. This is particularly the case for GCAM, which relies strongly on BECCS to mobilise huge chunks of biomass and expects an important contribution from nuclear while keeping a relatively high consumption of fossil fuels in comparison with the other models and thereby showcasing a lower development of solar and wind. The latter increases most substantially in ICES (45% of total PEC in 2050). In GEMINI-E3, the European energy mix is more balanced, primarily due to greater energy efficiency gains compared with other models, allowing for a lower substitution of carbon-free energy sources for fossil fuels. In EU-TIMES and NEMESIS, the evolution of the EU’s energy system is relatively similar, mobilising all available non-emitting energy sources in a relatively balanced path. Nevertheless, EU-TIMES leans more on solar and wind energy, whereas NEMESIS relies more heavily on biomass whilst displaying lower overall energy needs.

Figure 10: Evolution of the mix of EU primary energy consumption in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario (in %).

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. Arrows indicate the evolution over time, from 2020 to 2050 in 10-year intervals. The “Renewables share” includes biomass, hydro, solar, wind, ocean and geothermal. Other renewable energy sources are included in “Nuclear and other”. Nuclear is harmonised among models and accounted as nuclear heat as in Eurostat, with an efficiency factor of 33%.

		Natural gas primary consumption*		Natural gas imported from Russia**		Gas primary energy consumption in the "NZE EU Policy standard" scenario" in 2025					Gas primary energy consumption in the "NZE EU Policy standard" scenario" in 2030				
		2019	2020	2019	2020	EU-TIMES	GCAM	GEMINI-E3	ICES	NEMESIS	EU-TIMES	GCAM	GEMINI-E3	ICES	NEMESIS
EU-27	Mtoe	320	313	154	142	329	--	--	146	262	282	--	--	119	195
	bm ³	350	343	169	155	360	--	--	160	287	309	--	--	130	213
EU-28	Mtoe	386	--	154	--	--	233	337	--	--	--	219	297	--	--
	bm ³	422	--	169	--	--	256	369	--	--	--	240	325	--	--

Table 8: Comparison of natural gas imported from Russia and European consumption in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario in 2025 and 2030

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. *: natural gas primary energy consumption: Eurostat (2022a); **: natural gas imported from Russia: Eurostat (2022b). In italic, values converted either in Mtoe or in Bm³, with the following calorific value of 38,27 MJ/m³

Our scenarios were designed prior to the military conflict between Russia and Ukraine and therefore before the EU response to this crisis, including the REPowerEU Plan (European Commission, 2022a). Thus, we do not consider any specific policy or action towards the reduction of EU energy dependency on Russian fossil fuels, particularly Russian gas. Nevertheless, NZE scenarios show non-negligible reduction of gas consumption, essentially treating it as a transitional fuel. Table 8 compares 2019 and 2020 imports from Russia with the projected values by the models. In 2025, models show a variation of gas consumption between +10bm³ in EU-TIMES and -190 in ICES, comparable to EU primary consumption in 2019. On average, the reduction in gas consumption is approximately -90bm³/y in 2025 with respect to 2019. In 2030, all models project a reduction of gas consumption in the EU, with a minimum of -41 bm³, a maximum of -240 bm³, and an average of -135 bm³/y — i.e., almost 80% of 2019 natural gas imports from Russia.

Box 2: Gas consumption reduction in the EU in 2025 and 2030 in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario

These projected evolutions of the EU energy mix raise different questions on the reliability of such deployment in the coming decades, we address some of them below.

Regarding the future of nuclear energy in the EU, there exist different dynamics among EU Members States (Hanger-Kopp et al., 2019), with a planned phase-out in States such as Germany, Belgium, or Spain, and planned to commission of new power plants in States such as in Poland, Romania, Czech Republic (now Czechia), and the UK. The European Commission (2021c), in its 2020 reference scenario for the EU energy system, projects a declining nuclear gross inland consumption up to 2050 (with 171 Mtoe in 2020, 135 in 2030, 119 in 2040, and 105 in 2050), which is marginally more conservative than in our results from the *WWH21* scenario (from 147 Mtoe in NEMESIS to 413 in GCAM). In deep decarbonisation scenarios, Capros et al. (2019) show a stronger contribution of nuclear (210-238 Mtoe/y in 2050), loosely in the range of our models' projections in NZE scenarios (excluding GCAM). For hydroelectricity potential in Europe, our models' projections (except ICES) further substantiate the capacity limitations for increasing production, as confirmed by the 2020 reference scenario of the European Commission (2021c), in which hydro gross inland consumption grows slightly in 2020-2030 (29-31 Mtoe) and remains relatively stable thereafter.

In our results, biomass plays a key role in the decarbonisation of the European energy system. This role is particularly substantial in GCAM (up to 800 Mtoe/y in the "*NZE Benchmark*" scenario), followed by EU-TIMES and NEMESIS (270-310 Mtoe). Ruiz et al. (2019) have assessed the biomass potential for each EU28 country and type of biomass; their aggregated figures for the EU yield 123-457 Mtoe (132-479 for EU27+UK) in 2030 according to more or less optimistic scenarios, and 127-485 Mtoe in 2050 (134-505 for EU27+UK), while their medium estimates are around 270 Mtoe/y in 2030-2050 (285 for EU27+UK). Mandley et al. (2022) also synthesised supply-side studies for biomass in the EU and found a range of 120-450 Mtoe/y in 2050. The range of our models for 2030 (130-338 Mtoe) matches Ruiz et al. (2019) medium and high estimates. In 2050, GCAM projections for biomass use outperform Ruiz *et al.*'s (2019) optimistic projections for the EU's biomass potential, indicating substantial future biomass imports in the EU¹¹. It is relatively difficult to find quantified figures on potential biomass imports in deep decarbonisation scenarios. Nevertheless, based on different IAMs for 2°C scenarios, Mandley et al. (2022) showed that almost all models project that the EU will be a net importer of biomass in 2030 and 2050, with the highest imports value of about 180 Mtoe/y in 2030 and 220 in 2050. For NEMESIS and EU-TIMES, biomass consumption in NZE scenarios ranges between 250 and 310 Mtoe/y, which is compatible with the medium and high estimates of Ruiz et al. (2019).

Finally, our models project that solar and wind will be massively deployed in all NZE scenarios. Compared with technical potentials from Ruiz *et al.* (2019), our results are well below their estimates, which are equivalent to three times the EU's 2016 electricity demand. From a societal perspective, renewable deployment in Europe faces a number of barriers, particularly regarding wind farms (Ellis and Ferraro, 2016; Doukas et al., 2022) and requires particular involvement of local citizens and stakeholders to favour their acceptance (Enevoldsen and Sovacool, 2016). Such large-scale deployment also raises questions about potential environmental impacts (Capellá-Pérez et al., 2017) on biodiversity (Hernandez et al., 2014; Dhar et al., 2019) or land use (Doukas et al., 2020). In a recent paper, van de Ven et al. (2021) assessed the potential land impacts in the EU of large solar power plant deployment. With solar consumption between 100 and 220 Mtoe/y from our models' projections, land use (excluding rooftop

¹¹ Such large EU imports of biomass in the EU NZE scenarios in the GCAM model are feasible because we assumed that the rest of the World remains on its current climate policies, *i.e.* a moderated mitigation effort (see Sognaes et al. 2021). In scenarios with deep decarbonisation in the other regions of the world, the GCAM picture of biomass use in the EU may significantly change (see e.g. Mandley et al., 2022).

spaces, deserts, and dry scrublands) for solar reaches 21,000-69,000 km², i.e. 20%-66% of 2010 urban areas in the EU (0.5% to 1.7% of total land area). Similarly, Chen et al. (2022) show, in a least-cost scenario, that deep decarbonisation of the power generation in Northern Europe is 1.14% of total land area and up to 3% in some countries. This land consumption can be reduced by increasing the reliance on offshore wind instead of onshore but at the expense of higher mitigation costs.

3.2.8 Share of renewable energy sources

Figure 11: Share of renewable energy sources in total primary energy consumption in EU in NZE scenarios.

GCAM cover EU27+UK. The "Renewable share" includes biomass, hydro, solar, wind, ocean and geothermal. Nuclear is harmonised among models and accounted as electricity equivalent. GEMINI-E3 and ICES are excluded because they do not account for biomass energy. NB: our calculation of the renewable energy sources share (RES share) differs from the official calculation for EU RES shares because our models do not deliver enough details to use Eurostat (2020a) calculation method. Our calculation underestimates the RES share compared with Eurostat (2020a).

Figure 11 shows the share of renewable energy (RES) in the NZE scenarios for EU-TIMES, GCAM, and NEMESIS. This RES share differs from the official calculation for the EU RES share target. Models do not deliver enough detail to use the Eurostat (2020a) calculation method. Thus, our calculation underestimates the RES share, for instance, the difference is about 4 ppt in NEMESIS in 2015. Therefore, we refrain from comparing our results with EU targets.

In all models, the RES is shown to increase. Starting in 2020 at 15.7% (EU-TIMES), 17.2% (NEMESIS), and 21.7% (GCAM), and reaching 27-29.2% (EU-TIMES and NEMESIS) and 32-33.9% (GCAM) in 2030. RES continue to grow onwards in NZE scenarios. In NEMESIS, renewables are expected to represent 42-51.1% of EU primary energy in 2040. These values are marginally lower in EU-TIMES (38.9-44.2%) and GCAM (43.9-47.6%). In 2050, NEMESIS shows the highest RES share (66.6-77.5%), followed by EU-TIMES (58-71.5%) and GCAM (57.9-60.9%).

Between NZE scenarios, the RES share increases with mitigation effort. In NEMESIS, between the “NZE Benchmark – High” and the “Low” cases, the share of renewables in 2050 grows by 10.9 ppt, from 66.6% to 77.5%. Similarly, in EU-TIMES, the difference is about 13,5 ppt with 58% in the “High” case to 71.5% in the “Low” case.

3.2.9 Final energy consumption by sector

This section presents the evolution of the EU final energy by sector in the PAC scenarios (see Figure 12). In the *WWH21* scenario, all models show moderate variations of total final energy. EU-TIMES projects a moderate increase in final energy consumption (FEC) in the EU, from 1,000 in 2020 to 1,170 Mtoe in 2050. In all other models, FEC sees an overall decrease from 2020 to 2050. FEC experiences a predominant decline between 2020 and 2030 in GCAM (from 1,142 to 1,023 Mtoe) and ICES (from 1,295 to 1,072 in ICES); before increasing 1,047 Mtoe in GCAM and 1,160 in ICES in 2050. In GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS, FEC undergoes consistent declines, from 1,102 Mtoe in GEMINI-E3 and 936 in NEMESIS in 2020 to 980 and 801 in 2050, respectively. Sectoral dynamics of FEC also differ slightly among models in *WWH21*. In buildings, FORECAST and ICES expect a significant decrease until 2050 (20% and 16%, respectively), whereas all other models present relative stability with -7% in GCAM, -2% in EU-TIMES, -1% in GEMINI-E3, and +5% in NEMESIS. This suggests that four out of six models expect limited savings in the built environment with existing measures, whereas the other two project more important energy gains (15-20% in 2050). The differences among models are larger for industry, with an increase of FEC by 29% by 2050 in EU-TIMES, relative stability in FORECAST and ICES, and significant energy savings in GCAM (-11%), GEMINI-E3 (-23%), and NEMESIS (-34%). Finally, in the *WWH21* scenario, all models but EU-TIMES show a reduction in energy consumption in EU transport. The sectoral model, ALADIN, shows the largest FEC reduction in transportation (47% between 2020 and 2050), while the projections are more conservative in NEMESIS (19%), ICES (18%), GEMINI-E3 (18%), and GCAM (7%). In EU-TIMES, transport FEC is instead expected to grow (+24%).

In the NZE scenarios, all models project either a decline of total EU FEC until 2050, with modest energy savings in EU-TIMES and GCAM and bolder ones in NEMESIS and, particularly, in GEMINI-E3 and ICES. In EU-TIMES, FEC declines from 1,000 Mtoe in 2020 to 928 in 2050 in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario (7%), while in GCAM this decrease is even smaller (3.2%). Total energy savings in NEMESIS reach 24% by 2050, and up to 45% in ICES and GEMINI-E3. By sector, FORECAST and ALADIN continue to project important reductions in energy consumption in their respective sectors. By 2050, FORECAST shows the FEC of buildings declining by 30%, and declining in the industry by 25%. In transport, ALADIN expects 60% lower consumption in 2050 compared to 2020 levels. Both EU-TIMES and GCAM are less optimistic in terms of energy gains, with GCAM showing negligible changes in buildings and industry, and EU-TIMES in transport (which projects -9% and -12% FEC in industry and buildings, respectively). NEMESIS and GEMINI-E3 projections of FEC in the EU buildings sector are close to FORECAST (-26% and -37%, respectively) whereas, in ICES, the FEC decrease reaches 43%. In industry, once again NEMESIS and FORECAST show relatively similar declines (about 23%). However, it is now GEMINI-E3 (48%) that shows higher cuts than FORECAST, with ICES showing the least gains (-17%). Finally, in transport, all models but EU-TIMES show lower FEC in the EU in 2050 (-15% in GCAM, -31% in NEMESIS, -51% in GEMINI-E3, and up to -75% in ICES), while ALADIN projects cuts of -60%.

Figure 12: EU final energy consumption by sector in the PAC core scenarios (in Mtoe/y.)

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. The final energy for Industry includes feedstocks. *: For ICES, the scenario "NZE Bench. High" replaces the "NZE Bench. Med." scenario.

In summary, models show a reduction in energy demand as a valuable mitigation option. All models, except GCAM, project a lower energy consumption in the NZE scenarios in comparison with WWH21 across all sectors. The sectoral differences are most notable for buildings (in GEMINI-E3 and ICES), transport (in GEMINI-E3, ICES, and NEMESIS), and industry (in EU-TIMES), with overall smaller changes in both sector-specific models FORECAST and ALADIN.

Based on the European energy directive RED II (European Union, 2018), the EU targets for FEC in 2030 are 864 Mtoe (956 for EU27+UK), corresponding to a -32.5% energy efficiency target. When comparing these goals against our results, only NEMESIS nears the target in WWH21 (890 Mtoe). However, GCAM and GEMINI-E3 do come relatively close (1,023 and 1,034 Mtoe for EU27+UK, respectively). In the upgraded 2030 targets, the new objective of 787 Mtoe of final energy in 2030 in EU27 (870 for EU28, own estimates) is not achieved in any of the models in the NZE scenarios. However, NEMESIS again comes relatively close (831-853 Mtoe), followed shortly by GEMINI-E3 (955-977 Mtoe for EU28).

In 2030, our FEC projections in the buildings sector range between 305-422 Mtoe in the NZE scenarios. This is in line with the results compiled by Tsiropoulos *et al.* (2020) which show a range of 340-527 Mtoe (EU28). However, our projections show more heterogeneity in the industrial sector (235-380 Mtoe) than those reported by Tsiropoulos *et al.* (2020) which are particularly homogeneous (311-348 Mtoe), adding non-energy use. Finally, for transport, the studies reviewed by Tsiropoulos *et al.* (2020) show FEC between 176 and 307 Mtoe. Some of our projections are moderately higher (215-358 Mtoe in 2030), mainly due to GCAM and GEMINI-E3. For 2050, our more detailed energy models (EU-TIMES and GCAM) project a higher total FEC compared to Tsiropoulos *et al.* (2020), ranging between 419 and 745 Mtoe. Nevertheless, our three macroeconomic models remain within this range (from 618

Mtoe in GEMINI-E3 to 750 Mtoe in ICES) in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” in both cases. Excluding GCAM (which sees values as high as 420 Mtoe), projections from the other four models are relatively homogeneous regarding the FEC of buildings (229-300 Mtoe). In Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), this ranges from 195-386 Mtoe. For transport, except for NEMESIS and ICES producing slightly lower results, the projected EU FEC for 2050 (197-354 Mtoe) is above forecasts of Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), which range from 73-197 Mtoe. Finally, both our projections, as well as those compiled in Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), show a large range of FEC in the industry in 2050. Our projections indicate a range of 135 and 406 Mtoe, and Tsiropoulos *et al.* (2020) projections see a range of 137 and 337 Mtoe.

3.3 Sector level focus

Here we present the results for the PAC scenarios by sector, focusing on those sectors that play a key role in the decarbonisation of the European economy: two supply-side sectors (power generation and hydrogen) and three demand-side sectors (industry, buildings and transport). On the supply side, we detail the results for the five economy-wide models (EU-TIMES, GCAM, GEMINI-E3, ICES, and NEMESIS), with a deeper focus on EU-TIMES as it is best equipped to properly model both sectors. On the demand side, following a brief overview of the results, we perform an in-depth analysis based on the related sector-specific models (ALADIN for transport; FORECAST for industry and buildings).

3.3.1 Power generation

Figure 13: Relationship between the share of electricity in the secondary energy in EU in the PAC Core scenarios (%) and the total CO₂ emissions mitigation effort (% w.r.t. 1990)

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. In ICES, CO₂ emissions exclude industrial processes.

Electrification is a major mitigation option in all models (see Figure 13). In *WWH21*, electricity penetration into the energy mix increases but remains limited, representing around 35% of the total mix in 2050. The exceptions to

this trend are GCAM and ICES, where electrification is more substantial. In the NZE scenarios, all models show the role of electricity growing alongside the effort of CO₂ emissions reduction. In GCAM, this relationship is almost linear, with around 63% of the total secondary energy coming from electricity in 2050. Such rates are also reached in EU-TIMES, but with an acceleration in the last decade. NEMESIS also accelerates the use of electricity between 2040 and 2050 but shows smaller final values in 2050 (~50%). In GEMINI-E3, the deployment of electricity is smoother and reaches around one-third of the mix in 2050. Finally, in ICES, electricity becomes the dominant energy source rapidly under NZE scenarios, representing more than 50% by 2030 and reaching up to 85% by 2050.

Furthermore, when comparing the different cases of the “NZE Benchmark” scenario (Figure 13), NEMESIS and EU-TIMES show important differences in the use of electricity. Indeed, the electrification rate is increasing with the stringency of the mitigation effort. In the “NZE Benchmark – High” scenario (the least constraining), the electrification rate is around 52% in 2050 in EU-TIMES and 44% in NEMESIS. Whereas in the “NZE Benchmark – Low” scenario (the most stringent scenario in terms of CO₂ emissions reduction), EU-TIMES reaches 78% and NEMESIS reaches 62%. This result is not apparent in GEMINI-E3, in which the electrification rate remains almost the same across “NZE Benchmark” variants.

Figure 14 shows the different technologies mobilised by the models to decarbonise the power generation sector, which largely becomes carbon-free between 2035 and 2045 in NZE scenarios (except for ICES). In the WWH21 scenario, there is no major change in the electricity mix up to 2050: renewable sources—mainly solar—deploy progressively, whereas fossil fuels (particularly coal) decline rapidly. Except for GCAM, in which electricity from nuclear power plants grows significantly, none of the other models projects an important evolution of nuclear.

Figure 14: EU electricity production by source in the PAC core scenarios (in Mtoe/y).

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. ICES is excluded from the figures because its mitigation options in the power sector are limited and it affects the readability of the figure.

Under NZE scenarios, the phase-out of coal (without CCS) is accelerated. However, models show this phase-out¹² occurring in different years: between 2025 and 2030 in EU-TIMES, 2030 and 2040 in GEMINI-E3, and 2035 and 2045 in GCAM and NEMESIS. Gas (without CCS) also declines in all NZE scenarios. The share of gas in the European electricity mix remains significant up to 2040 in GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS, with a 5-8% share, but phases out in the last decade. In EU-TIMES and GCAM, phase-out happens earlier (from 2040), except for in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, where EU-TIMES sees its arrival later. Nevertheless, fossil fuel energy remains in the electricity mix in both GCAM and GEMINI-E3 in the NZE scenarios as they are coupled with CCS technologies. This is particularly the case for gas in GEMINI-E3, reaching a 4-7% share in 2050, and for coal in GCAM in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, where coal with CCS accounts for 6% of the power generation mix. Electricity from nuclear shows a marginal increase in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS in absolute terms, but its relative share drops (10-15% and around 17%, respectively). In GCAM, nuclear is an important emissions mitigation option, with a relatively stable share (around 30%), but a large increase in absolute values (186 Mtoe in 2050). ICES also sees an important increase in nuclear, even though its nuclear declines to 14% in 2050. In GEMINI-E3, both the share and level of nuclear decreased in the power sector throughout the decades.

Figure 15: Share of renewable energy sources in power generation in EU in NZE scenarios

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. The “renewables share” includes biomass, hydro, solar, wind, ocean and geothermal. ICES does not account for biomass energy.

The use of bioenergy in the NZE scenarios in the European power sector is expected to increase in all models. This is particularly the case for GEMINI-E3, GCAM, and NEMESIS, where bioenergy represents approximately 12%, 14%, and 18% of the energy share, respectively, in 2050. Penetration of bioenergy-based technology in the power mix

¹² We assume a phase-out when the share in the electricity mix is below 2%.

is milder in EU-TIMES at ~4% in 2050. Almost all models progressively coupled bioenergy plants with CCS, except for NEMESIS, in which biomass without CCS is also used to produce electricity, which reports around half of the bioenergy-powered electricity coming from plants *without* CCS. Variable renewable energies (VRE) are also largely deployed to produce carbon-free electricity in the EU under the NZE scenarios. Hydro deployment is very limited in absolute values in GCAM and EU-TIMES, while NEMESIS and GEMINI-E3 project a moderate increase with a slightly declining share (10% and 11% in 2050, respectively). Only ICES shows important development of hydropower in NZE scenarios, with production tripling in these three decades. Power generation from solar becomes a major source in models under the NZE scenarios, except for ICES, with solar accounting for approximately 20% in GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS, and even 30% in some scenarios in EU-TIMES by 2050. It is the first source to produce electricity in the EU in GCAM. Solar installed capacity is therefore multiplied by a factor of 15 in EU-TIMES and 11 in NEMESIS until 2050 in the "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario (Figure 16). Wind becomes the primary source of electricity in the EU in 2050 in ICES (~60% of the total energy mix), followed by EU-TIMES (~50%), GEMINI-E3 (~33%), and finally NEMESIS (~<25%). As with solar, wind installed capacity is 9 times higher in EU-TIMES in 2050 compared to 2020, and 3.5 times in NEMESIS. As a consequence of the large deployment of renewables to decarbonise the EU power sector, the RES share grows rapidly (Figure 15). Starting from approximately 32% in 2020 in the NZE scenarios, it reaches 52% (median value in 2030), 66% in 2040 and 80% in 2050.

By comparing the different cases of the "*NZE Benchmark*" scenario, we observe that the electricity production is growing with the stringency of the scenarios in terms of CO₂ emissions reduction. Similarly, within the sector, the RES share is also higher in the more stringent scenarios – despite the overall growth of total electricity production (see Figure 15). RES deployment is, therefore, largest in "*NZE Benchmark – Low*", followed by "*Medium*" and then "*High*" (Figure 16). In the "*High*" case, the total power plant installed capacity is around 2,800 GW (EU-TIMES) and 1,860 (NEMESIS), and around 4,820 (EU-TIMES) and 2,610 (NEMESIS) in the "*Low*" case. Of the 2,000 GW of additional capacity in EU-TIMES, 70% comes from solar and 27.5% from wind energy; of the 750 GW of additional capacity in NEMESIS, about 25% comes from solar and 53% from wind.

Figure 16: EU installed power capacity by source in the PAC core scenarios (GW/y.)

NB: only EU-TIMES and NEMESIS deliver reliable data on installed capacity.

Electricity production is expected to grow in all scenarios and more than doubles between 2020 and 2050 under the NZE scenarios. The volume of power generation varies among models, with growth ranges of 20-161% in 2050. In certain cases, the rate of growth is slightly higher compared to Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), where this increase is within the range of 20-95%. Moreover, renewable energy power generation develops rapidly: EU-TIMES and NEMESIS project that renewables will cover 80-89% of power generation in 2050, while a lower share is found in GCAM and GEMINI-E3 of 56-79%. These results are in line with Capros et al. (2019), where renewables attain a share of 85% of power generation. Moreover, in the NZE scenarios, our results show solar and wind producing 55-90% of renewable electricity, which corresponds to approximately 36% and 80% of the overall power mix in 2050. These results, however, do vary per model. With the exclusion of GCAM, models show at least 50% of the production mix coming from solar and wind in 2050. These findings are again in line with Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), where scenario results foresee that the majority of power comes from renewables (75-100%), with wind and solar accounting for between 60% and 90% of renewable electricity sources. A high share of intermittent electricity in the grid means that a considerable amount of ancillary investments will be required. The impact of large penetration of variable renewable energy, or 100% renewable energy, in the power system has been explored in recent literature – such as in Europe (e.g. Child et al., 2019, Zappa et al., 2019, Tröndle et al., 2019) and in some Member States, including France (Cani et al., 2018; Krakowski et al., 2019) and Germany (Hohmeyer and Bohm, 2014). In a large survey, Heptonstall and Gross (2020) show that the aggregated cost (including reserve, capacity, distribution and profile costs) of variable renewable energies (VRE) in the power sector is relatively stable up to a penetration rate of 45% to 55% but it significantly grows thereafter. Similarly, Reichenberg et al. (2018), focusing on Europe, find that the marginal levelised cost of electricity, which they defined as “the cost of substituting 1 MWh of thermal electricity with 1 MWh of VRE electricity”, increases linearly with VRE penetration up to 80%, but increases sharply with stronger penetration rates. In our NZE scenarios, the highest shares of solar and wind (excluding ICES)

are reached in EU-TIMES (70-80%). Regarding other models, this share is around 50% in GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS and around 35% in GCAM. Including hydro pushes the share up to 84% in EU-TIMES, around 60% in NEMESIS and GEMINI-E3, and 41% in GCAM. In ICES, in which mitigation options are limited, the share of VRE reaches around 80% with hydro, and around 60% without hydro. Thus, our models' projections for VRE penetration in the European power sector are in "the feasible at a reasonable cost" range of the literature. EU-TIMES and ICES do reach the upper bounds of this range, above which costs may significantly increase and the stability of the supply be affected.

Finally, carbon capture technologies gain ground post-2030, in particular BECCS, which make up for 6-20% of the generation mix by 2050. The deployment of CCS-powered coal and gas remains limited in EU models (NEMESIS and EU-TIMES), but consists of 5-11% of the power mix by 2050 in the global models (GCAM and GEMINI-E3). The range of BECCS found in the NZE scenarios is in line with the biomass used for electricity generation in the compiled scenarios of Tsiropoulos et al. (2020). The findings on biomass suggest that the deployment of renewables is the fundamental pillar to achieving deep emissions cuts in power generation, followed by nuclear and CCS technologies (particularly BECCS), coupled with a considerable drop in fossil fuels. Nuclear and CCS options currently have significant limitations due to restrictions in place in several EU Member States and the limits on sustainable biomass available in the system (discussed in Section 3.2.7). European models better reflect the impacts of these national policies and supply constraints, which result in lower deployment of these technologies, compared to global models. Finally, the large deployment of wind and solar is also challenging in practice, not only because of their intermittency, but because they can require significant land and stimulate conflicts with other land uses (see discussion in Section 3.2.7).

3.3.2 Hydrogen supply and demand

3.3.2.1 Supply-side

Besides electricity, hydrogen is also viewed as a growing alternative energy vector in the coming decades, with a potential to decarbonise fossil-intensive sectors with limited technology alternatives (such as heavy-industry, heavy-duty trucks and non-road transportation) or for use as energy storage. For hydrogen to take off in the energy system as a valid option to achieve decarbonisation, it needs to be produced with sustainable technologies—thus, either through fossil fuel plants with CCS or with renewable electricity (namely blue or green hydrogen). Thus, we present below an overview of potential hydrogen updates in our model ensemble of four models (ALADIN, EU-TIMES, FORECAST and GCAM), considering hydrogen as a potential mitigation option. When considering the demand side of the sector-specific models ALADIN and FORECAST, it is assumed that hydrogen used in the European transport and industry sectors is carbon-free. In EU-TIMES and GCAM, an explicit representation of the supply side is available and allows for an investigation of the pathways adopted in NZE scenarios that produce hydrogen.

Figure 17: EU hydrogen production by type in the PAC core scenarios (in Mtoe/y).

GCAM covers EU27+UK. Grey hydrogen is produced with fossil fuels with CCS, blue hydrogen with fossil fuels with CCS and green hydrogen with biomass (with or without CCS) and electricity (assuming carbon-free electricity). Hydrogen is not an available mitigation option in GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS.

The model results suggest that hydrogen’s contribution to the decarbonisation of the energy system increases with deeper mitigation effort, thus more H₂ is produced in scenarios with the strictest emission limits—*i.e.*, the “Low” NZE case. Moreover, we observe a moderate switch toward the most sustainable technologies for hydrogen production over time (Figure 17 and Figure 18).

Figure 18: EU hydrogen production capacity by type in the PAC core scenarios (in GW/y).

Only EU-TIMES delivers data on installed capacity. Grey hydrogen is produced with fossil fuels with CCS, blue hydrogen with fossil fuels with CCS and green hydrogen with biomass (with or without CCS) and electricity (assuming carbon-free electricity). Hydrogen is not an available mitigation option in GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS.

Despite achieving deeper mitigation in NZE scenarios, the deployment of H₂ production remains negligible in 2030, thus hydrogen is not expected to be a valid short-term option to achieve 2030 targets. The European Commission defined an EU-H₂ strategy for 2030, which foresees 40 GW electrolyzers installed in the EU by 2030 to produce hydrogen (European Commission, 2020b). Our findings suggest that, without specific market-pull measures, this deployment of hydrogen production will not happen in 2030. Nevertheless, deployment of hydrogen is foreseen from 2040 onwards in the model results. In 2040, hydrogen is produced mainly by blue or grey hydrogen via natural gas in both model results. In EU-TIMES, a complete transition to green hydrogen is achieved in 2050, with produced quantities increasing sharply in scenarios with deeper CO₂ emissions mitigation targets. In GCAM, hydrogen production increases by 2050, but a complete transition to green hydrogen is not achieved. Our results, therefore, suggest that hydrogen will become a leading energy vector to sustain decarbonisation in 2050, even if its production remains marginal compared with electricity production. Hydrogen production is 87-95% lower than electricity in model results because electricity provides more sectoral technology options. This trend is also observed in Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) and Capros et al. (2019), where the volume of renewable electricity production is driven by hydrogen production in 2050. Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) compare thirteen scenarios reaching at least 90% emissions reduction in 2050 in the EU, in which hydrogen production in 2050 is higher than 125 Mtoe/y in 2050 (1,450 TWh) - in line with the results of the EU-TIMES model but higher than GCAM projections.

3.3.2.2 Demand side

Focusing on the final sectors, hydrogen use increases over time in final energy demand as an alternative energy carrier, especially as CO₂ emissions mitigation grows (Figure 19). Hydrogen deployment in final sectors in 2050 in EU-TIMES is between 18 and 80 Mtoe, and between 15 and 20 Mtoe in GCAM. These results are below the estimates found in Capros et al. (2019), whose scenarios reaching NZE in the EU and are used as reference by the European Commission (2018a), that show hydrogen and synthetic fuels used in final energy demand being greater than 150 Mtoe/y in 2050.

Figure 19: EU final hydrogen consumption by sector in the PAC core scenarios (in Mtoe/y.)

GCAM covers EU27+UK. Hydrogen is not an available mitigation option in GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS.

Hydrogen becomes relevant in end-use sectors' energy consumption only after 2040, predominately to decarbonise the industry (EU-TIMES, FORECAST, and GCAM) and transport sectors (ALADIN and EU-TIMES). In industry, hydrogen is deployed mostly in high-energy-intensity industries like iron and steel. EU-TIMES suggests H₂ becomes relevant only in 2050, with the share achieved in total final consumption being between 7% and 11%. GCAM foresees an anticipated deployment in industry by 2040, with its share growing over time, leading to a share of industry final consumption between 3% and 6%. FORECAST, an industry-specific model, confirms this earlier deployment and growth of hydrogen over time. In 2030, hydrogen delivers just 2% of the final energy consumption of the EU industry in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario, as mostly a marginal mitigation option in the sector, while it achieves a share of 27% in 2050. These results confirm that hydrogen remains a niche technology in the industry sector in 2030, but is taken up as a full commercial option in 2050, with its deployment further stimulated by decarbonisation efforts (Figure 21). Hydrogen share in industry is in line with the results from the NZE scenarios compiled by Tsiropoulos et al. (2020), where hydrogen consumption in the industry sector is between 6% and 20% in 2050.

In transport, EU-TIMES shows that hydrogen technologies remain a niche until 2040, even in NZE scenarios, with a share of 2% of sectoral FEC. The technology achieves an important deployment thereafter, with a share of 5-15%, mostly in freight road transport as well as aviation and navigation (5-8% of road and 15% of non-road transport consumption is from H₂). GCAM suggests hydrogen is not a valid option in the transport sector, with energy consumption remaining minimal both as direct fuel and to produce synthetic fuels (~1% of FEC in transport). ALADIN shows a low deployment of hydrogen as direct fuel, with just 3% in 2050, being mostly used for freight road transport. However, it also indicates a relatively substantial usage in producing synthetic fuels (21% in 2050). In comparison, scenarios analysed in Tsiropoulos et al. (2020) show hydrogen and synthetic fuels share in transport energy consumption of between 15% and 50%. These values are higher than in EU-TIMES and GCAM but in line with ALADIN.

Finally, another end-use for H₂ is mixing it in gas pipelines. In EU-TIMES a blending rate of 5% of hydrogen in the pipelines is achieved. This can be considered a valid option to reduce the emission impact of natural gas together with the blending of biomethane and synthetic methane, as confirmed by Capros et al. (2019).

3.3.3 Industry

3.3.3.1 Multi-model analysis of EU Industry decarbonisation

Figure 20: EU industry final energy consumption by fuel in the PAC core scenarios (in Mtoe/y.)

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. Final energy consumptions include feedstocks. For models allowing the split between fossil fuels and bioenergy, their sum equals the respective aggregate (Solids, Gases or Liquids). *: For ICES, the scenario "NZE Bench. High" replaces the "NZE Bench. Med." scenario.

As already presented in Section 3.2.9, the evolution of final energy in industry is very heterogenous across models in the PAC scenarios (see Figure 20). In EU-TIMES, EU energy consumption in industry increases over time in

WWH21 and declines in the NZE scenario. In terms of fuels, the model projects a large deployment of solid biomass up to 2040 in NZE scenarios, and 2050 in *WWH21* (more than tripling in comparison with 2020). However, after 2050 in NZE scenarios, competition with the power sector for biomass energy implies the substitution of biomass in industry, mainly with electricity but also with hydrogen in the "*NZE EU Policy scenario*" and, to a lesser extent, with biogas. In FORECAST, the energy mix evolves slowly in *WWH21*, with a progressive decline of fossil energy (gases -43% in 2050 compared to 2020, solids -70%, and liquids -67%), in favour of solid biomass energy (+90%), heat (+14%) and electricity (14%). In the "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario, FORECAST shows an almost complete phase-out of fossil energy and a large deployment of both electricity and hydrogen alongside a more moderate deployment of solid biomass and heat (further details of these scenarios for FORECAST are developed in the next section). In GCAM, total final energy in industry remains relatively stable up to 2050 in all scenarios. The evolution of the energy mix in industry shows shared features among scenarios, with the development of electricity and hydrogen and a decline of fossil liquids and solids. A noticeable difference is the decline of fossil gases in the *WWH21* and "*NZE Benchmark – Medium*" scenarios, and their increase in the "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario, as a result of a lower emissions reduction target for industry in GCAM (see Section 3.2.3). GEMINI-E3 presents important energy savings in the EU industry up to 2050, particularly in the NZE scenarios, as it is a unique decarbonisation option mobilised by the model to reduce CO₂ emissions in the industrial sector. Indeed, in all scenarios, and especially in NZE, fossil energies decline significantly whereas electricity consumption remains relatively stable (*WWH21* scenario) or even declines (in the NZE scenarios: -20% in 2050 compared to 2020). In ICES, the total energy consumed by the industry sector is also relatively stable over the decades in all scenarios, except between 2020 and 2030, during which ICES projects some energy savings. Decarbonisation takes place through the reduction of fossil fuels and a substantial uptake of electricity, reaching up to 90% of the EU industrial energy mix in 2050. Finally, in NEMESIS, energy efficiency is also relatively important in all scenarios, particularly in the NZE scenarios, with energy use declines of -30% to -35% in the industry sector between 2020 and 2050. Deployment of electricity is also a key decarbonisation option in NZE scenarios, and so is biomass albeit to a lesser extent.

Figure 21: Relationship between the share of hydrogen and electricity in the final energy consumption of the industry in the EU in the PAC Core scenarios (in %).

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS do not model hydrogen.

In summary, of the six models utilised, three mobilise energy savings in the industry sector to deeply reduce CO₂ emissions (to a large extent in GEMINI-E3, and more moderately in FORECAST and NEMESIS). Some models also have a marginal reliance on solid biomass to decarbonise the European industry sector (EU-TIMES and FORECAST, up to 2040, and NEMESIS). However, the largest mitigation option mobilised across all models is electrification, supported by hydrogen in those models considering these mitigation options. This contribution is significant in FORECAST and more marginal in EU-TIMES and GCAM (see Figure 21).

3.3.3.2 Deeper insights into EU industry decarbonisation from the FORECAST model

We follow the analysis with a more detailed analysis of the results of the FORECAST model, which is an energy-specific model for the European industry. In addition to *WWH21* and "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenarios, the FORECAST model has run a variant of the latter, called "*NZE EU PS – H₂*" in which there is a stronger focus on hydrogen as a major decarbonisation option for feedstocks and process heating (see Annex I for further details).

The EU27 industrial GHG emissions were 598 MtCO₂eq. in 2018, including 128 for process-related emissions. In the *WWH21* scenario, the industrial sector reduces GHG emissions by 48% and 66% by 2030 and 2050 respectively compared to 1990. In the "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario, the emissions achieve a reduction of 58% by 2030 compared to 1990. Towards 2050, the reduction in GHG emissions is further accelerated resulting in a reduction of about 94% by 2050 compared to 1990. This includes about 100MtCO₂ in carbon capture and storage (CCS) from cement and lime plants.

In FORECAST, the final energy consumption is detailed in Figure 22 and includes the final energy consumption for heating and cooling as well as other uses like mechanical energy. The final energy consumption in the *WWH21*

scenario decreases slightly by 6% from 2,683 TWh in 2015 to 2,512 TWh in 2050. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenarios, final energy consumption decreases by 16% to 2,265 TWh by 2050. This decrease is driven by the use of the best available technologies and efficiency improvements, but also accelerated circularity and material efficiency play important roles. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, the energy mix changes substantially, fossil fuels are completely phased out by 2050 and electricity is the dominant energy carrier with more than 64% of total FEC increasing from 926 TWh in 2015 to 1,519 TWh in 2050. Biomass shows a very strong increase in the *WWH21* scenario: it almost doubles to 426 TWh by 2050 making biomass one of the most important energy carriers. The strong increase in biomass is driven by the CO₂ price. At these price levels, solutions like hydrogen and (to less extent) direct electrification are not yet cost-effective, so biomass gains large market shares, as possible (domestic and international) limitations to biomass supply are not considered in the *WWH21* scenario. In the “NZE EU Policy Standard” hydrogen is only used to a limited extent in this scenario and reflects the EU Hydrogen Strategy (European Commission, 2020b). Hydrogen is used only in the iron and steel industry as well as chemical feedstock resulting in 161 TWh H₂ demand. In the “NZE EU PS – H₂” scenario most high-temperature heat furnaces are replaced by hydrogen. Resulting in a substantial increase in hydrogen demand by 2030 (106 TWh) and 550 TWh by 2050.

Figure 22: EU final energy consumption in industry (excluding feedstocks) by energy carriers in the PAC core scenarios – FORECAST model

Source: FORECAST model

3.3.4 Buildings

3.3.4.1 Multi-models analysis of the EU buildings sector

Regarding the evolution of the EU's FEC in buildings in the *WWH21* scenario, only FORECAST projects significant energy savings between 2020 and 2050, while GCAM and ICES show energy savings between 2020 and 2030. In the NZE scenarios, we can classify the models into two groups: a) those with stable or b) declining consumption. EU-TIMES and GCAM, on the one hand, project a relatively stable energy consumption in buildings, whereas all others project a significant decline.

In EU-TIMES, the European buildings sector reduces its emissions by replacing fossil fuels with electricity (almost 60% of the buildings' energy mix in 2050), and to a lesser extent by ambient heat (accounted in "Other" fuels), which grows with electricity. In GCAM, electricity (75% of the mix in 2050) is the only mitigation option mobilised in built environments, but remains limited due to stronger mitigation efforts in other sectors.

Figure 23: EU buildings' final energy consumption by fuel in the PAC Core scenarios (in Mtoe/y.)

*GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. For models allowing the split between fossil fuels and bioenergy, their sum equals the respective aggregate (Solids, Gases or Liquids). *: For ICES, the scenario "NZE Bench. High" replaces the "NZE Bench. Med." scenario.*

In FORECAST, energy savings in the buildings sector allow for a reduction of 30% (-108 Mtoe) in energy demand by 2050 in comparison with 2020. The full decarbonisation of the sector achieved in FORECAST is enabled by the large deployment of heat (36% in 2050) and, to a lesser extent, solid biomass. Compared with other models, FORECAST projects a decline in electricity in the "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario. However, this decline is lower than the total energy savings, and thus allows its share to grow in the sectoral mix (see Figure 24). Similarly, GEMINI-E3 also mobilises energy gains in the buildings sector for its decarbonisation, with -37% (-138 Mtoe) in 2050 in comparison with 2020. Electrification is also moderated in absolute terms, but its share goes up to 80% in

2050. In ICES, reducing energy demand is the main option to decrease the CO₂ emissions of the European buildings sector in the NZE scenarios, with -43% (-193 Mtoe) in 2050 compared to 2020. The other decarbonisation option is near complete sectoral electrification, with almost 90% of buildings' energy consumption in 2050 being from electricity. Similarly, in NEMESIS, the energy saved in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario in 2050 is about 26% (-100 Mtoe) in comparison to 2020, coupled with increased electricity consumption (64%). The other fuels (excluding fossils) remain relatively stable, implying a decreasing share.

Figure 24: Relationship between the share of electricity in the buildings' final energy consumption in EU in the PAC core scenarios (%) and the total CO₂ emissions mitigation effort in the buildings (% w.r.t. 1990)

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK.

3.3.4.2 In-depth analysis of the EU buildings sector

This section presents with additional details the results of the FORECAST model, the sector-specific model for the Buildings sector in the EU.

3.3.4.2.1 Policies in the buildings sector

The net-zero emission target of the EU entails that the EU building stock also becomes carbon-neutral. Improving the energy performance of the building envelope, installation of efficient equipment, fuel switching to renewables and green electricity and smart operation of buildings are important measures to reduce emissions in the buildings sector (European Commission, 2018a). With the revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) in 2021, European Commission aims to accelerate building renovation and reduce energy consumption through minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) and energy performance certificates (EPCs). Furthermore, by defining the 'zero emissions building' as the standard for new buildings from 2027 and existing buildings from

2030, it requires buildings to cover their energy demand by themselves or by locally produced renewable energy. The subsidies for fossil heating systems are abandoned after 2027. This way, European Commission also aims to reduce GHG emissions and promote the uptake of renewable energy in buildings (European Parliament, 2022).

3.3.4.2.2 Heating demand for European buildings

The European buildings under the *WWH21* scenario reduce their final energy demand for heating by 28% in 2050 compared to the 2015 level. Despite the increase in water heating needs, in line with the projected population and GDP increase, the overall demand decrease to 2,205 TWh is due to the 34% demand reduction in space heating. Under the implementation of the decarbonisation policies in the "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario, the final energy demand for heating reduces by around 37% in 2050 compared to the 2015 level. Thanks to the realisation of the ambitious compliance rates and the diffusion of higher building standards both in new and refurbished buildings, this improvement in demand reduction is possible. The development of the heating final energy demand can be seen in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Final heating demand of residential and commercial sector in EU27 by energy service type in the PAC core scenario

Source: FORECAST model

The energy carrier composition of the final heating energy demand of the *WWH21* scenario is observed in Figure 26. Despite the efforts to phase out coal in *WWH21*, around 10 TWh remain in the mix due to the slow reduction in the countries that rely on coal today, such as Poland. The demand for fuel oil decreases by almost 80% in 2050; however, it still supplies 5% of the total heating demand of the EU27 in the *WWH21* scenario. There is no EU-wide ban applied for the oil heaters in the scenario, and the individual phase-out efforts of the Member States carry the reduction only so far. Natural gas is still the most important energy carrier in the mix, supplying 47% of the final heating energy demand in 2050. There is a 22% reduction in the absolute demand of the energy carrier by 2050 compared to 2015; however, this is due to the overall final energy demand reduction in buildings. As there

is no EU-wide ban applied for natural gas heaters, and some countries do not apply carbon-tax in the scenario, natural gas slightly increases its share in the mix, replacing the other fossil fuels. District heating and heat pumps are the other heating systems that replace the decreasing coal and oil demand, while, biomass share remains the same in the mix.

The development of the direct CO₂ emissions in the *WWH21* scenario is on the left of Figure 28. The total emission reduces by 184 Mt of CO₂ in 2050 compared to 2015 due to the avoided fossil fuels. The remaining 244 Mt arises from the remaining fuel oil and natural gas. The reduction is gradual from 2020 to 2050, in line with the gradual decrease in fossil fuels.

Figure 26: Final heating energy demand of residential and commercial sector by energy carriers in WWH21 scenario (EU27)

Source: FORECAST model

Figure 27 shows the energy carrier composition of the final heating energy demand of the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario. Fossil fuels are all phased out by 2050, in line with the applied policies. Coal is already phased out by 2040, and fuel oil demand is insignificant by 2045 due to the EU-wide ban on these heating systems starting from 2025. The reduction of natural gas accelerates after 2030, as the EU-wide ban starts in 2030. Biomass, district heating and heat pumps are replacing the fossil fuels in the mix. Biomass and district heating shares increase by around 20% in 2050 compared to 2015, while heat pump share increases by almost 30%. As the heat pump technology was young in 2015, the relative growth of these systems is more significant.

The development of the direct CO₂ emissions in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario is on the right of Figure 28. The total emissions are down to 1 MtCO₂ in 2050 due to the phased out fossil fuels. The reduction is strong up to 2040, when fuel oil and coal are disappearing from the mix. After 2040, the reduction is due to the phase-out of the remaining natural gas in the mix.

Figure 27: Final heating energy demand of residential and commercial sector by energy carriers in “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario (EU27)

Source: FORECAST model

Figure 28: Direct CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels consumed in residential and commercial building heating (EU27)

Source: FORECAST model

Table 9 shows the total direct CO₂ emissions of the buildings in EU27+UK, and the reduction compared to 1990 levels in numbers. It is seen that the sectoral emission reduction targets are reached in 2030 and 2050 in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario.

Table 9: Total direct CO₂ emissions by residential and commercial sector buildings (EU27+UK, MtCO₂/yr)

		1990	2015	2030	2040	2050
WWH21	CO ₂ emissions (Mt)	536	510	433	357	274
	Reduction wrt. 1990		-5%	-19%	-33%	-49%
NZE EU Policy Standard	CO ₂ emissions (Mt)	536	510	294	97	2
	Reduction wrt. 1990		-5%	-45%	-82%	-100%

Source: FORECAST model

3.3.4.2.3 Electricity demand for appliances & processes

Excluding the final energy demand for heating, the remaining final energy demand of buildings stems from the energy consumption of appliances, lighting, and ventilation and cooling processes. The energy efficiency increase in the equipment is well underway as guided by the efficiency standards (e.g., Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC). Even if the electricity consumption does not cause direct CO₂ emissions by the sector itself, it is less burdening to the power generation system and more responsible towards the environment to have reductions in the final electricity demand as well. Figure 29 shows that the final electricity demand is gradually reducing towards 2050 in both scenarios, with the higher decrease in "NZE EU Policy Standard". By 2050, the electricity demand is reduced by 4% in the WWH21 scenario and by 19% in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario compared to 2015. The difference in the strength of the reduction is due to the higher compliance rates with the regulations in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario.

Figure 29: Final electricity demand of appliances and processes in the EU27 buildings sector, excluding heating

Source: FORECAST model

The reduction in the electricity consumption of commercial sector buildings is especially significant, as this consumption makes up 47% of the final energy demand of the sector (Eurostat, 2022a). Therefore, the energy

efficiency increase, and energy demand reduction from the electrical applications have high relevance in these buildings. In Figure 29, it is seen that the majority of the total demand reduction comes from commercial buildings. In 2050, the electricity demand is reduced by 22% compared to 2015 in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario. While the room air conditioning demand increases in buildings and the ICT demand stays almost the same in the commercial sector, the demand for lighting, processes and process heat is significantly reduced.

3.3.5 Transport

3.3.5.1 Multi-models analysis of the EU transport sector

As shown in Figure 30, the evolution of the transport sector's energy consumption differs among models for the *WWH21* scenario. Nevertheless, almost all models (excluding EU-TIMES) project a reduction in energy use. Energy use reductions are most pronounced in the sectoral ALADIN model (-47% between 2020 and 2050), less so in the macro-economic models GEMINI-E3, ICES, and NEMESIS (-15% to -20%), and modestly in the global GCAM model (-7%). EU-TIMES, on the other hand, projects a rise in energy consumption (+24%). In this scenario, oil consumption in the European transport sector declines across all models by 2050. Nonetheless, oil remains the primary fuel in the sector across the majority of models (excluding ALADIN), representing 73-93% of the energy consumption in the sector in 2050. The share of oil is marginally lower in GCAM (58%), and only 28% in ALADIN. In GCAM, biofuels and electricity substitute for oil. This is also the case for ALADIN but complemented by synthetic fuels.

Figure 30: EU transport final energy consumption by fuel in the PAC core scenarios (in Mtoe/y.).

*GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. *: For ICES, the scenario "NZE Bench. High" replaces the "NZE Bench. Med." scenario. GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS do not consider synthetic fuels and hydrogen.*

In the NZE scenarios, the decarbonisation of European transportation is predominantly driven via a reduction in

the total energy consumed (-60% in ALADIN in 2050 with respect to 2020, in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario). This reduction is even larger in ICES (-75%) but weaker in the other models, with -52% in GEMINI-E3, -31% in NEMESIS, -15% in GCAM and stable in EU-TIMES. Electrification is also mobilised by all models to reduce the sector’s CO₂ emissions (see Figure 31, solid lines). Electricity consumption grows in all models in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario between 2020 and 2050, with +56 Mtoe in ALADIN, +108 in EU-TIMES, +71 in GCAM, +46 in GEMINI-E3, +9 in ICES and +42 Mtoe in NEMESIS. The share of electricity in the sectoral mix reaches ranges between 21% (ICES) and 56% (ALADIN). Some models also rely on biofuels to decarbonise European transport, especially NEMESIS, with biofuels covering 32% of total energy consumption in 2050 in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario, followed by 8% in GCAM, 6% in ALADIN, and 5% in EU-TIMES. Hydrogen deployment is heterogeneous in models with this mitigation option. EU-TIMES projects a significant use of hydrogen, reaching up to 8%, while in ALADIN hydrogen plays a marginal role (3%) and in GCAM it is not mobilised entirely (Figure 31, dotted lines). Finally, neither EU-TIMES nor GCAM deploy synthetic fuels, however, they do become a key alternative in ALADIN (up to 21% of the European transport energy) (Figure 31, dashed lines).

Figure 31: Relationship between the share of electricity, hydrogen and synthetic fuels in the final energy consumption of the EU transport sector in the PAC core scenarios (%) and the total CO₂ emissions mitigation effort in the transport (% w.r.t. 1990)

GCAM and GEMINI-E3 cover EU27+UK. GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS do not consider synthetic fuels and hydrogen.

3.3.5.2 In-depth analysis of the EU transport sector

To realise CO₂ mitigation in the transport sector by 2050 the following driving factors are relevant in all transport modes:

- **Alternative drives:** in all road transport, electrification is the dominant driving factor for CO₂-neutral transport. Hydrogen fuel cells for heavy-duty vehicles, buses and trains will only play a minor role for

special niche applications where electrification cannot be realised. Also, hydrogen aircraft for short-distance flights starting from 2035 will not play a crucial role.

- **CO₂ neutral fuels:** blending ratios for fossil, biogenic and synthetic fuels as well as the complete use of hydrogen derivatives like ammonia and synthetic diesel and kerosene are mostly used to decarbonise aviation and shipping. The percentage of sustainable fuels is implemented according to the “Fit for 55 – targets”.
- **Transportation efficiency:** efficiency improvements and general efficiency measures (e.g., aerodynamics) contribute to energy savings per transport kilometre of about 30% till 2050 depending on the different transport modes.
- **Modal shifts** to more energy-efficient modes of transportation: mobility services (e.g., car sharing, autonomous driving), shifts from road to rail and flight bans are only briefly taken into account by reducing passenger car fleets and augmenting rail transport.
- **Transportation demand reduction:** sufficiency, price elasticities in air travel, home office and digital meetings lead to less growth of general transport performances.

Passenger cars and motorcycles

As electric drives are already widely sold on the market for passenger cars the diffusion of plug-in electric vehicles (PEV) is calculable by using empirical data to estimate annual registration numbers. With the registration numbers and the country-specific life cycles, the total car fleet is calculated for each year. Regarding the average driving performances for each nation, the energy demands can be derived.

As the market diffusion depends on national framework conditions, a diffusion curve represented by a logistic growth function, for each country is calculated. Therefore, the market diffusion for PEV (PHEV and BEV) in Norway, a pioneer in e-mobility, with a market share of over 80% PEV in 2022 (ACEA, 2022) was analysed from 2009 to 2021 by regression analysis. The start value for the logistic growth is the country-specific market share of PEV in 2021. The saturation of the growth function is set to be 100% for every country as it is the best fit with the empirical market share data from Norway and it is most probable that PEV will completely substitute conventional drive technologies in passenger cars. With that, we have assumed that in passenger cars fuel-cell electric vehicles (FCEV) will not be available in future due to the high costs of fuel cells and due to the current predominance of battery electric vehicles (BEV) on the market. Therefore, we do not expect any relevant hydrogen demands in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario for passenger cars.

In order to adapt the annual national growth rates to each country, the national fuel-electric energy price ratios and national monetary incentives are taken into account. The impact of the two factors on market share was calculated by a panel analysis from Münzel et al. (2019). Monetary incentives include all cost savings for PEV compared to conventional cars. A European ban on combustion engines starting in 2035 has been taken into account. This also affects plug-in hybrid electric vehicle (PHEV) registration numbers with a complete fade out till 2035. The average electric driving performance of a PHEV was assumed 56 % of total driving performance (Plötz et al., 2021) to calculate electric and fuel energy demands. For all different drive trains, a total efficiency increase of 30% from 2018 to 2050 is assumed. The data for car stocks, registrations, and market shares of alternative drives for all countries from 2011 to 2021 were collected from the European Automobile Manufacturers' Association¹³

¹³ <https://www.acea.be/statistics>

(ACEA, 2022) and the European Alternative Fuels Observatory¹⁴ (EAFO, 2022) and adjusted for future projections.

The strong national differences in historical PEV market shares and stocks make a country-specific analysis for passenger cars in EU27+UK necessary. Northern European countries (Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Denmark), Belgium and the Netherlands have the most advanced market diffusion of PEV whereas the eastern and south-eastern European countries adapt slower to alternative drives. In 2035 the market share of PEV will be 100% in almost all European countries (Figure 32).

The total electricity demands coming from passenger cars will rise quickly in the European Union till 2040 with a total amount of about 34 Mtoe. This leads to almost zero direct emissions in passenger cars already in 2045.

Figure 32: Market share of passenger electric vehicles (PEV) in car registrations by a selection of EU27+NO+UK countries.

Source: ALADIN model; Historical values till 2021 (ACEA, 2022).

Light, heavy-duty vehicles and buses

ALADIN distinguishes between seven drive alternatives: (1) diesel vehicles, (2) gasoline vehicles, (3) PHEV, (4) BEV, (5) FCEV and catenary vehicles that are either equipped (6) with an additional battery or (7) with an additional combustion engine (Diesel). A distinction is also made between three vehicle classes: (1) light vehicles with a gross vehicle weight of less than 3.5 t, (2) vehicles with a gross vehicle weight of 3.5 t to 12 t and (3) heavy vehicles with a gross vehicle weight greater than 12 t. In the first step, based on vehicle usage data from 6,098 vehicles (KiD 2010; Truck-scout24 2016), the technical feasibility in terms of range and electric driving share is checked. This is followed by a total cost of ownership (TCO) analysis since the total costs of commercial vehicles have the greatest influence on the purchase decision (Kluschke et al. 2019). In the third step, a market ramp-up scenario is calculated based on the individual vehicle selection that is optimal for the user. Further information on the procedure for commercial vehicles can be found in Wietschel et al. (2017) and Gnann et al. (2017). The battery capacities were

¹⁴ <https://www.eafo.eu/countries>

selected so that BEVs have a gross vehicle weight of less than 12 t and have a range of 300 km by 2050. BEVs over 12 t have a range of 400 km. This is sufficient to cover the usual distance between two breaks (4.5 h). PHEVs are only available in the smaller vehicle classes up to 12 t. For vehicles over 12 t the hybrid overhead line truck with diesel is available.

BEV will dominate the stock of trucks smaller than 3.5 t similar to passenger cars in 2050 (Figure 33). For heavy-duty vehicles, hybrid diesel catenary trucks will be the most cost-efficient alternative following the assumption that electric overhead lines will be partly constructed on European highways. In the ALADIN output FCEV play a negligible role (Figure 33) and therefore hydrogen demands are assumed to equal zero in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario.

The consequence of the electrification of trucks and buses is electric energy demands up to 20 Mtoe in EU27+UK till 2050. The remaining operating diesel trucks (hybrid catenary trucks with diesel engines) will be almost CO₂ neutralised by the admixture of synthetic (50% quota in 2050) and biofuels (30% quota in 2050).

Figure 33: Number of trucks <3.5t (left) and > 12t (right) in Germany in thousands, by fuel type in the “NZE EU Policy Standard” scenario

Source: ALADIN model

Rail

Passenger and freight transport performances for railways were extracted from the European transport statistical pocketbook 2019 for the reference year 2018 (European Commission, 2019b). Regarding the EU28 Reference Scenario (European Commission, 2021c) passenger transport performance increases 60% and freight transport performance increases 70% from 2015 to 2050. Therefore, the transport performances were adjusted for each nation. At the same time, efficiency improvement of the train loading by e.g., expanding of tracks and the use of longer trains also augments the load factors by 8% till 2030 and 20% till 2050. This does not completely compensate for the growing demands.

Decarbonisation will be mostly reached by a constant electrification of railway tracks and the use of battery electric trains in remaining rarely frequented areas. The percentage of electrified railway tracks varies between European nations. Therefore, historical values for electrification were used as a basis to calculate the future electrified tracks until 2050. As a big part of transport, performances go through main railway tracks that are electrified or will be electrified in the future, a quick reduction of direct CO₂ emissions from trains is possible. At the same time, the overall electricity demand for EU27+UK will constantly grow to 6 Mtoe until 2050.

Inland shipping

Transport performances for inland shipping were calculated with the numbers from the European transport statistical pocketbook 2019 (European Commission, 2019b). The increase in efficiency is estimated by 30% for inland shipping until 2050 (Timmerberg et al. 2018). Alternative drives for inland shipping were not taken into account. Decarbonisation is mainly reached by the admixture of sustainable fuels.

To reach the climate targets the admixture quotas for sustainable fuels according to the "Fit For 55" targets (6% 2030, 75% 2050) result in a total demand of 3.4 Mtoe synthetic diesel for coastal and inland waterway shipping in EU27+UK. Biofuels will be used to substitute the remaining fossil diesel and contribute to almost zero CO₂ emissions in inland shipping.

Aviation

Transport performances for inland flights and international flights were collected from the International Civil Aviation Organization annual report (ICAO, 2021) and the European transport statistical pocketbook 2019 (European Commission, 2019b). At the same time, the volume of air traffic in Europe is assumed to constantly grow by 0,5 % starting in 2018. It is assumed that transport performance in air traffic is fully recovered after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Energy efficiency improvements through improved propulsion efficiency and increased engine efficiency will be expected in new aircraft, so that energy efficiency improvements of 35% can be achieved by 2050. There will be no relevant alternative drive technologies in aviation till 2035. But starting from 2035 until 2050 the whole national volume of air traffic will have to be handled with aircraft directly powered by hydrogen. Technically short-distance flights can already be powered by the direct use of hydrogen (35 TWh hydrogen in 2050). Due to limited storage capacities of hydrogen long-distance flights can only be sustainably decarbonised by the admixture of synthetic fuels (5% quota in 2030 and 63% quota in 2050). The total demand for synthetic fuels like ammonia and synkerosene will reach 15 Mtoe in EU27+UK until 2050. Biofuels are also used to an extent of up to 7 Mtoe in EU27+UK to move aviation to GHG neutrality without using new propulsion technologies.

All transport modes

Total CO₂ emissions in transport will almost achieve net zero in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario. First, the electrification of passenger cars will reduce the direct CO₂ emissions of transport quickly. Followed by the electrification of heavy-duty vehicles. Rail and inland shipping only play a minor role in total CO₂ emissions. Whereas aviation will prolong CO₂ mitigation until 2050. It can only be fully decarbonized by the use of 100% green hydrogen and its derivatives.

In the *WWH21* scenario, we have a similar pattern as in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario, but with a slower electrification of road transport and lower admixture quotas for synthetic fuels in aviation and shipping. This leads to a remainder of over 150 MtCO₂ in total EU27+UK until 2050 (about 85% reduction compared to 1990).

3.4 Socioeconomic impacts

Our model ensemble includes three macroeconomic models (GEMINI-E3, ICES and NEMESIS), which allow investigating certain socioeconomic aspects of our scenarios. We present below some socioeconomic impacts of the PAC scenarios, focusing on the GDP, employment, and sectoral impacts. As usual, socioeconomic impacts are assessed against a counterfactual scenario. Here, we use the *WWH21* scenario, whilst also naming a reference scenario further below. Thereby, we present the socioeconomic impacts should the EU move from the current climate policy scenario to the deeper decarbonisation scenarios.

Before discussing the results of the three macroeconomic models in detail, we present in Table 10 the recycling scheme used in each model to recycle the carbon revenues from the carbon prices in order to partly explain the differences among model results.

Table 10: Recycling scheme of carbon revenues implemented in each macroeconomic model in the PAC core scenarios

Recycling scheme of carbon revenues	
GEMINI-E3	Carbon revenues are recycled via a lump sum transfer to households after ensuring the balancing of the government account. There is no international transfer.
ICES	Carbon revenues are recycled via a lump sum transfer to households after ensuring the balancing of the government account. There is no international transfer.
NEMESIS	Carbon revenues are recycled to private actors (firms and households) proportionally to the direct cost that the implementation of carbon prices induces for them. An energy-intensive industry will then receive more than a less intensive one. There is no international transfer.

3.4.1 NZE impacts on EU GDP

The results of the three macroeconomic models differ significantly in terms of GDP impacts induced by the NZE scenarios. Although all show a negative impact on EU GDP for stringent European climate objectives, the extent of GDP loss differs. Compared with the *WWH21* scenario, NEMESIS and GEMINI-E3 show European GDP being only marginally impacted, with a GDP loss ranging between 0.46% and 1.53% in GEMINI-E3, and between 0.32% and 0.55% in NEMESIS, from 2020-2050 (Table 11). In ICES, impacts are significantly stronger, with EU GDP losses of between 5.3 and 6% from 2020-2050. This means that in the “*NZE EU Policy Standard*” scenario, GDP loss in ICES reaches -15% by 2050 compared to the *WWH21* scenario. These large losses stem from the limited availability of emission mitigation options – as the model cannot rely completely on technological options to decarbonise the EU economy, it reduces demand. This result warns that, in case of important technology failures or a *lack of* at-scale (commercial) availability (such as for (BE)CCS, hydrogen or VRE in power generation), deep decarbonisation in Europe will not be feasible at a reasonable economic cost. However, in those models with more available mitigation options, the economic burden of shifting the EU from current policies (*WWH21*) to the NZE pathway is greatly diminished. Still, GDP loss reaches -4.15% of EU GDP in 2050 under the “*NZE EU Policy Standard*” scenario in GEMINI-E3, and -1.5% in NEMESIS in the “*NZE Benchmark – Low*” scenario—i.e., the ones with the strongest CO₂ emissions reduction constrain.

Table 11: EU GDP deviation in the NZE scenarios (% w.r.t *WWH21* scenario)

		GDP deviation (% w.r.t the <i>WWH21</i> scenario)								
		2020-2030			2030-2050			2020-2050		
		GEMINI-E3	ICES	NEMESIS	GEMINI-E3	ICES	NEMESIS	GEMINI-E3	ICES	NEMESIS
Scenarios	NZE Bench. Low	-0.24%	--	0.01%	-1.30%	--	-0.75%	-1.02%	--	-0.55%
	NZE Bench. Medium	-0.22%	--	0.01%	-1.20%	--	-0.56%	-0.94%	--	-0.41%
	NZE Bench. High	-0.20%	-0.30%	0.03%	-1.01%	-7.07%	-0.46%	-0.80%	-5.35%	-0.32%
	NZE EU Policy Standard	-0.24%	-0.84%	-0.08%	-1.97%	-7.83%	-0.58%	-1.53%	-5.97%	-0.44%

GEMINI-E3 covers EU27+UK

Figure 34: Contribution to EU GDP deviation in the NZE scenarios (in ppt of GDP, w.r.t. WWH21 scenario)

GEMINI-E3 covers EU27+UK

By analysing the drivers of GDP impacts, Figure 34 shows that models do not portray the same story and that some models' properties affect the results. In NZE scenarios, GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS expect a decline in European exports and private consumption in comparison with the *WWH21* scenario. European exports are penalised by increased relative prices in the EU as a result of deeper mitigation actions in the EU than in the rest of the world (RoW), alongside assumptions of no additional effort in the RoW compared to *WWH21*. This loss of competitiveness reduces the EU GDP by about 1.1 ppt in 2050 in the "NZE Benchmark – Medium" scenario in GEMINI-E3, and 1.4 ppt in NEMESIS. In this scenario, European private consumption is also penalised in comparison to *WWH21*, with -1.1 ppt in GEMINI in 2050 and -1.4 in NEMESIS. Imports also contribute negatively to the EU GDP deviation in the NZE scenario, yet to a lower extent. In the "NZE Benchmark – Medium" scenario, imports reduce EU GDP by 0.1 ppt in 2050 in GEMINI-E3 and by 0.6 ppt in NEMESIS. Similarly to exports, the unilateral implementation of stronger climate ambition in the EU tends to increase internal prices, impacting European competitiveness. It leads to an increase in imports, even if this increase is counterbalanced by lower internal demand, explaining why imports impact EU GDP loss less than exports.

Although both models agree on these observations, they markedly differ on the impact on investments. In NEMESIS, total investment is higher in the NZE scenarios than in *WWH21*, which reinforces European economic growth. In the "NZE Benchmark – Medium" scenario, investment contributes to +2.5 ppt on the EU GDP deviation, counterbalancing the negative contribution of private consumption as well as the trade balance (exports minus imports). In GEMINI-E3, by assumption, total European investment remains similar between the *WWH21* and NZE scenarios. In NEMESIS, the decarbonisation of the European economy implies a huge amount of investments that do not crowd-out non-climate-related investments whereas, in GEMINI-E3, this crowding-out effect is total and does not allow total investment to grow – even though this repartition between sectors can be modified. This

difference between the modelling of capital markets in general equilibrium models and macroeconomic models is a common feature in model intercomparisons (e.g. Capros et al., 2014 or Nikas et al., 2021). Beyond the theoretical debate (Pollit and Mercure, 2018), we can point out the importance of the crowing-out effect on the macroeconomic impact of deep mitigation scenarios and push for policy measures that minimise this potential substitution between climate transition investments and other non-dirty and non-climate-related ones. McKibbin et al. (2020) show, using the macroeconomic model G-Cubed, that monetary policies adapted to climate mitigation action can reduce the economic impacts of mitigation. However, beyond McKibbin et al. (2020), there is a gap in the literature and thus a need for further research on this issue (Keppo et al., 2021; Sanders et al., 2022).

3.4.2 Employment

The diversity within our models allows us to investigate the NZE pathways' impacts on EU employment. Figure 34 shows the sector employment impact in the NZE scenarios for GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS. GEMINI-E3 projects small employment gains in 2050 across all NZE scenarios (between 50,000 and 133,000 jobs created). On the other hand, NEMESIS projects larger employment losses (between 1.14 million and 1.4 million job losses) that represent a maximum loss of 0.6% of total EU employment in 2050 in comparison with the *WWH21* scenario. This difference between the models can be explained by the labour market functioning in each model. In GEMINI-E3, real wages adjust to clear the market – in case of a reduction of labour demand, the real wage decreases, some workers leave the labour market, due to these lower real wages, so that demand matches labour supply. Thus, there is no involuntary unemployment in GEMINI-E3. In NEMESIS, however, the clearing of the labour market takes time, and involuntary unemployment can exist. There is rigidity in wages setting and thus some workers that looking for a job cannot find it because of the shortage in the labour demand from firms.

Figure 35: EU sector employment deviation in NZE scenarios (in thousand w.r.t. *WWH21* scenario)

GEMINI-E3 covers EU27+UK

Looking at sectoral employment, the models also deliver different pictures of the impacts arising from the NZE scenarios. In GEMINI-E3, the European agricultural sector creates approximately 100,000 jobs in 2050 in comparison to the *WWH21* scenario. Employment in the energy supply sector is relatively stable, except in the “*NZE EU Policy Standard*” scenario, in which it declines by ~50,000 jobs. A key result of the GEMINI-E3 model is the immense employment losses in energy-intensive industries (637,000 jobs lost in 2050 in the “*NZE Benchmark – High*” scenario, up to 891,000 in the “*NZE EU Policy Standard*”), and represents a loss of between 12% and 16% of total European employment in energy-intensive sectors in 2050 compared to the *WWH21* scenario. This loss is a result of greater losses in sectoral competitiveness due to the large share of energy in their total production cost, which is not compensated through the recycling scheme that targets households. This negative impact on employment is not visible in the other manufacturing industries, which create around 85,000 jobs in the NZE scenarios. Finally, the services sector counterbalances employment losses in the energy-intensive sectors (708,000-816,000 additional jobs in the NZE scenarios in 2050, in comparison with the *WWH21* scenarios).

In NEMESIS, the evolution of sectoral employment in the EU differs from GEMINI-E3. In comparison with 2050 in the *WWH21* scenario, employment in European agriculture undergoes moderate declines by ~75,000 jobs in the “*NZE Benchmark – High*” and “*NZE EU Policy Standard*” scenarios. However, agricultural employment is almost stable in the “*NZE Benchmark – Medium*” and is positive in the “*NZE Benchmark – Low*” scenario (+161,000 created jobs). The difference between scenarios mainly results from the importance of biomass as an alternative fuel. For instance, biomass use in the “*NZE Benchmark – Low*” is 35% higher than in the “*NZE Benchmark – High*”. Changes in employment are larger in the energy supply sectors, with new jobs created being between 80,000 and 350,000 (depending on the scenario). Although NZE scenarios imply some energy savings, electrification of European economies leads to higher employment in the energy supply sector as the power sector is more labour-intensive than fossil-fuel industries in the EU. The main differences across the scenarios within GEMINI-E3 relate to employment in energy-intensive industries. In NEMESIS, employment in these sectors is higher under the NZE scenarios than in *WWH21*, with an additional +30,000 to +200,000 jobs in 2050. In NEMESIS, total investment grows significantly in the NZE scenarios to achieve the EU’s climate transition. In turn, this increases the internal demand relating to those sectors producing investment goods (e.g., some energy-intensive industries). Furthermore, the recycling scheme in NEMESIS (see Table 10) reduces the negative competitiveness impacts of carbon pricing as carbon revenues are recycled in proportion to each sector’s contribution. Similarly, European employment in other manufacturing sectors, including construction, is positively impacted in the NZE scenarios, with between +600,000 up to +1.5 million additional jobs in 2050 in comparison with *WWH21* (+1.9% and +4.5% respectively). Finally, the services sector faces a reduction in employment in NEMESIS in the NZE scenarios as a direct result of the decline in private consumption that is mainly composed of these services. In comparison with the *WWH21*, in 2050, between 1.9 and 2.4 million jobs are lost in the services sector in the NZE scenarios, representing a decline of -1.1% to -1.4%.

How employment may be impacted by CO₂ emissions mitigation has been studied for several decades (Bossier and Bréchet, 1995) and is concomitant with the “double dividend” economic debate (e.g. Goulder, 1995; Bovenberg and Goulder, 2002; Freire-González, 2018). More recently, using a general equilibrium (CGE) model Chateau and Saint-Martin (2013) show different employment impacts of OECD countries’ CO₂ emissions mitigation scenarios according to the recycling scheme for the carbon revenues, findings that labour market rigidity reinforces negative employment impacts. Fragkos and Fragkiadidakis (2022), also using a CGE, find negative impacts on employment at the global scale of a “2°C scenario” from less than -1% in the EU and more than -2% in Russia and India. They also show relative sector employment impacts are moderate, except for fossil-fuel industries, electricity, and what they called “clean industries”. Specifically focusing on the energy sector Pai et al. (2021) indicate potential global positive impacts of a “2°C scenario”, with +10 million jobs created globally in renewables whereas 8 million could be lost in fossil-fuel industries. Similarly, Mercure et al. (2018), using a macro-econometric model in a “2°C

scenario”, show slight employment gains at the global level. When investigating the EU, Duscha et al. (2016) utilised two different macroeconomic models, with the macroeconometric model showing positive employment impacts in 2030 related to the deployment of renewables in the EU. Fragkos and Paroussos (2018), used a CGE to study employment impacts of EU climate policy (similar to our *WWH21* scenario) and found positive net employment in the EU of approximately 900,000 jobs in 2030, and 1.85 million in 2050. Further, Pollitt et al. (2015), with a macroeconometric model, estimated the potential European employment gains of a “-40% reduction scenario” (as in Fragkos and Paroussos, 2018, and in line with our *WWH21* scenario) of between 0.7 to 1.2 million in 2030. Finally, the European Commission (2018a) using two different types of models (a CGE, and a macroeconometric model), assessed the sector employment impacts of an NZE scenario. Despite finding large ranges in the estimates of employment deviation, the construction (+0.3 to +2.8%), power (+3.6% to 22.3%) and agriculture (-0.7% to +7.9%) sectors were found to benefit – the first via low-carbon investment requirements, and the remaining two via a switch to carbon-free fuels. Fossil-fuel industries are highly affected, with between -2.9% to -62.6% of employment, compared to the reference scenario. For other sectors, it depends on the models themselves and the detailed implementation of the scenarios, with employment impacts on services (-2% to +0.9%), energy-intensive industries (-2.6% to +1.8%) and the other manufacturing industries (-1.4% to +1.1%). These results from the literature highlight key uncertainties surrounding the potential employment impacts in the EU resulting from the implementation of deep decarbonisation scenarios, depending on the scenario design (use of carbon revenues and what happens in non-EU regions) as well as on the theoretical background of the model, and its specific functioning regarding capital and labour markets.

3.5 Results at Member States level

Results for EU Member States (MS) are presented below. In total, five models deliver results at an MS level: the two sector-specific models, ICES (limited to nine individual countries, others are grouped in two aggregated regions), EU-TIMES and NEMESIS covering all MSs individually. We do not focus on the EU as a whole in this section, so the results of sector-specific models are not presented here.

As the PAC core scenarios, emissions caps have been implemented at the EU level, (not at an MS level). Thus, it is interesting to compare the results of the least-cost scenario (“*NZE Benchmark -Medium*”) with the updated National GHG emissions reduction target of the “Fit for 55” proposal (European Commission, 2021e). Figure 36 does this comparison. It displays the GHG emissions reduction¹⁵ in each MS from EU-TIMES and NEMESIS in the sectors covered by the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) in 2030 in the “*NZE Benchmark - Medium*” scenario with the ESR updated national GHG emissions reduction targets. We can group the MS into three cohorts:

- MS where the GHG emissions reduction over-reaches the target, (a reduction higher than 3 ppt compared with the target)
- MS that achieve reductions close to the EU target (less than 3 ppt difference with the target)
- MS where GHG emissions reduction is insufficient to comply with the national target. (a reduction lower than 3 ppt compared with the target)

Surprisingly, both models show important similarities. They project that ten EU MSs (Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Malta, the Netherlands, Portugal, Romania and Spain) will surpass their target in the ESR sector in 2030. Both models also agree that Cyprus and Sweden will be close to their respective targets. Furthermore,

¹⁵ Similar assumptions for non-CO₂ emissions in each MS have been used in both models.

NEMESIS and EU-TIMES expect that six MSs (Austria, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany and Latvia) will not achieve their GHG emissions reduction targets. However, the models' projections diverge for some countries. For instance, in Italy, EU-TIMES shows a reduction in GHG emissions from the ESR sector in 2030 by -39% with respect to 2005, whereas NEMESIS expects greater reductions of 52%. Thus, with a national target fixed at -43.7%, this objective is not reached in EU-TIMES but surpassed in NEMESIS. Inversely, in Poland, EU-TIMES projects a larger GHG emissions reduction than required by the Polish target (of -17.7%) at -34%, whereas NEMESIS shows a reduction that complies with the target at -15% in 2030.

At a global level, we can observe that the MSs in which both models project larger GHG emissions reductions in the ESR sector than required by their respective national targets are generally Eastern or the Mediterranean Member States, whereas those MSs in which they expect lower GHG reduction than their respective targets are more Northern and Western countries. This can be explained by the calculation method of the national ESR targets, with the target being inversely proportional to per capita GDP (European Commission, 2021e; Vielle, 2019). Our results suggest that this 'fairness principle' incorporated into the calculation of national ESR targets tends to digress national burden sharing away from the optimal one calculated by the models in the "*NZE Benchmark – Medium*" scenario.

(a) NEMESIS

(b) EU-TIMES

Figure 36: GHG emissions reduction by Member State in 2030 in the Effort Sharing Regulation sector and in the "NZE Benchmark - Medium" scenario, (a) NEMESIS, (b) EU-TIMES

National distribution of non-CO₂ emissions projections is based on European Commission (2021c), the total for EU-27 fits with Table 4. 2030 national target refers to the European Commission's proposal to revise the ESR directive (European Commission, 2021e).

Figure 37 illustrates the CO₂ emissions reductions in different MSs in comparison with 1990s levels in the "NZE Benchmark" scenario. Without delving into country-level detail, we can observe that all MSs converge towards deep decarbonisation, with at least -70% being achieved in all MSs by 2050. Some Member States have important

negative emissions, as in Finland in EU-TIMES. BECCS deployment in the power generation allows offsetting emissions in other sectors that are more difficult to decarbonise. Furthermore, in EU-TIMES, some Member States have CCS restrictions, such as Germany, that some others compensate. The decarbonisation rates among MSs are more heterogeneous in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS in 2050, which may result from differing mitigation options between the different models, but also key constraints implemented within the models. For instance, EU-TIMES considers current restrictions in MS legislation regarding the storage of carbon in the ground, whereas NEMESIS does not and instead assumes no particular restrictions. This is also the case for national bioenergy constraints, which are implemented in EU-TIMES but not in NEMESIS. In addition, EU-TIMES considers hydrogen as a mitigation option, and NEMESIS does not.

Figure 37: Reduction of CO₂ emissions from energy and processes by Member State in the "NZE Benchmark - Medium" scenario (% w.r.t 1990)

Historical values for 1990 come from EEA (2021a). Luxembourg and Malta have been removed from the figure for EU-TIMES because historical data in EU-TIMES and EEA (2021a) are different, leading to a very large reduction in 2050.

Here, we show the share of renewable energy sources in each MS for the EU-TIMES and NEMESIS models¹⁶. Models' projections differ, however, both show a significant increase in the RES shares across all MSs. Generally, NEMESIS expects a higher RES penetration in national primary energy consumption. For instance, in Belgium and Spain, EU-TIMES shows a RES share of 35% and 67% in 2050, whereas they reach 80% and 86%, respectively, in NEMESIS. In Germany and France, the RES share remains higher in 2050 in NEMESIS than in EU-TIMES, with 81% and 64% (Germany) and 57% and 50% (France), respectively. For Italy, both models converge towards a RES share

¹⁶ The evolution of the fuel mix of the primary energy consumption in each MS is graphed in Figure 47 to Figure 56, in Annex II.

of approximately 73% in 2050. This is also the case for Poland, which sees renewable energy sources accounting for 65% of the total primary energy consumption. Evidently, the differences between the models rely on model specificity but, a priori, as EU-TIMES considers national constraints on bio-energy availability, based on Ruiz et al. (2019), it could be the main reason for the differences.

Figure 38: Share of renewable energy sources in total primary energy by Member State in the "NZE Benchmark - Medium" scenario (%)

The "renewable share" includes biomass, hydro, solar, wind, ocean and geothermal. Nuclear is harmonised among models and accounted as electricity equivalent. ICES is excluded because they do not account for biomass energy. NB: our calculation of the renewable energy sources share (RES share) differs from the official calculation for EU RES shares because our models do not deliver enough details to use Eurostat (2020a) calculation method. Our calculation underestimates the RES share compared with Eurostat (2020a).

This last figure of the results at an MS level illustrates GDP deviation in ICES and NEMESIS under the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario with respect to the WWH21 scenario. As already discussed in Section 3.4, ICES has limited mitigation options and relies on demand reductions to reach the NZE in the EU, leading to huge GDP losses in 2050. This is particularly evident in Greece, Czechia and Poland, which see a GDP loss of over 20% in 2050. In other MSs, ICES generally projects a GDP loss of between 10% and 20%. In NEMESIS, these losses are significantly lower at between -3% and -4.5% (except in Malta in which GDP loss goes up to 8.4% in 2050), and some MSs actually benefit from decarbonisation – such as Cyprus, Slovakia and Spain that experience gains in GDP. The large amount of investment required to realise a climate transition in the EU, that does not crowd-out other non-climate-related investments, significantly limits the loss of GDP expected in NEMESIS's deep decarbonisation scenarios. Moreover, specific national conditions may influence the relative GDP performance of each MS. The national labour market, for example, is a particularly important driver. In NEMESIS (where involuntary unemployment can exist, and there is no labour mobility between MSs) a country with a greater and more available labour force can limit the inflationary pressure of the labour demand arising from investment needs. Therefore, this model will 'win' in

relative competitiveness in comparison with MSs where the labour supply is already scarce. In addition, the specific physical and geographical conditions of some MSs will allow for a less costly transition, such as irradiation levels for solar or prevailing wind conditions.

Figure 39: GDP deviation by Member State in the "NZE EU Policy Standard" scenario (w.r.t WWH21)

Caution: the scale for each model differs. BNL includes Belgium, Netherlands and Luxembourg and RoEU includes Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia.

3.6 Confronting our results with stakeholders

PARIS REINFORCE is a stakeholder-driven modelling project, where the diversity of stakeholders (including policymakers, businesses, NGOs, academia, and broader civil society) lies at the heart of our scientific process. Earlier in the project, the first EU-level modelling analysis of WP5 (as documented in Deliverable D5.3) was driven by stakeholder input (see Deliverable D3.3). In a process of deliberation that was assisted by multiple rounds of polling, stakeholders prioritised their research questions and co-designed the scenario framework. The overall co-creation process is documented in Nikas et al. (2021b).

Due to critical challenges resulting from COVID-19 confinements, as well as the general impacts of the pandemic, our planned stakeholder engagement was delayed. As a consequence, the series of national stakeholder workshops that aimed to feed into the new modelling exercises took place in parallel with the modelling iteration documented in Section 3 of this deliverable. As such, we refrained from basing the scenario design on continuously emerging stakeholder input. Instead, we upgraded our scenario exercise by (a) updating technoeconomic and socioeconomic inputs to follow global developments (including the pandemic and its impacts on economic recovery and emissions trajectories), (b) updating our policy assumptions to reflect the emerging climate pledges, targets, and regulations at all levels, including at the EU and European-national level, and (c) capturing a broader

sectoral focus, aiming to follow up on the questions that stakeholders had prioritised during the first modelling iteration.

However, stakeholder engagement taking place in tandem with this modelling round, provided the opportunity to discuss our protocols/frameworks with stakeholders, as well as to present different bits and pieces along the way, depending on what sections of the analysis in Section 3 were available at the time.

The first national workshop in Europe was carried out in May 2021, in Switzerland¹⁷, where stakeholder discussions focused on the role of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism and the importance of the EU carbon budget for the bloc's long-term strategy (discussed in section 4.3, below). In a polling session (see Annex III), Swiss stakeholders indicated that the power sector will be the easiest sector to decarbonise, that the buildings and industry sectors will pose marginally challenging, and that it will be most difficult to achieve deep emissions cuts in the agricultural and transport sectors. As reflected in Section 3.2.3 and Figure 5, our results on the speed of decarbonisation by sector, model, and scenario largely agreed with stakeholder views. The power sector showed the largest decarbonisation potential, with the supply sector becoming carbon-free as early as between 2035 and 2045 (faster than all other sectors). Industry and buildings followed, although the latter at a slower pace, while projected transport-sector decarbonisation validated stakeholder concerns, by showcasing limited and rather slow CO₂ emissions mitigation. A factor that contradicted stakeholder input was their perceived capacity limitation at reducing emissions in agriculture, however, there is a relatively limited representation of this sector in our models. Swiss stakeholders were also asked about the importance of selected technologies for achieving deep emissions cuts, to which they prioritised renewables and electric mobility, then behavioural change and BECCS/CCS, followed by other technologies (including hydrogen). Our results largely confirm the critical importance of renewable energy sources, not only for electricity decarbonisation, but as part of the broader energy mix. However, despite having a substantial impact, electric mobility is not as profound, with electrification in 2050 in the NZE scenarios reaching 21-56%, depending on scenario variant and model. Although we do not consider behavioural change explicitly in this exercise, we have noted the significance of its role in decarbonisation, the importance of incorporating it into modelling studies for climate action (see Nikas et al., 2020) and have explicitly explored it in the baseline scenario formulation study (see Cassetti et al., under review). Regarding (BE)CCS, unless the EU ramps up its climate ambition, our results show that this technology may not be a valid mitigation option (except maybe in GCAM). However, pursuing climate neutrality by 2050 relies heavily on CCS (coupled with bioenergy or otherwise) across the modelling ensemble. The critical technical and physical constraints are also discussed in Section 3.2.4. Finally, we find the requirement for hydrogen to grow alongside climate ambition and efforts, as well as a moderate switch from grey/blue towards blue/green hydrogen over time. Nevertheless, in line with stakeholders' insights, hydrogen deployment remains negligible in this decade and, in agreement with European Commission projections of hydrogen availability (depending on market-pull measures in place), hydrogen takes off post-2040, and green hydrogen is achieved by mid-century or later.

Similar insights were gained a week later, during a national workshop in France¹⁸, where stakeholders again discussed the prospects of green hydrogen (domestic production vs. imports, investment and infrastructure requirements, cooperation, as well as flexibility and non-conventional storage) and the role of CCS (with a focus on industry). In addition, French stakeholders discussed challenges to the deployment of renewables for

¹⁷ <https://www.paris-reinforce.eu/news-events/project-news-events/european-national-stakeholder-workshop-series-case-switzerland>

¹⁸ <https://www.paris-reinforce.eu/news-events/project-news-events/european-national-stakeholder-workshop-series-case-france>

decarbonisation in the power sector (grid capacity, opposition, etc.). In our modelling study, apart from highlighting the role of RES for electricity in a net-zero Europe (covering about 80% of power generation in 2050), we also discuss technical and societal (with a focus on solar and wind) challenges to such diffusion levels, drawing from the wider literature (see Section 3.2.7). Within this scope, we also validate our model results against similar modelling studies and official EU scenarios, finding that our projections for penetration in the European power sector are in the range of feasibility – beyond which costs could considerably grow and grid stability may be affected (see Section 3.3.1).

In June 2021, a stakeholder workshop in the Netherlands¹⁹ again touched upon issues of hydrogen, although the focus was placed on grey and blue hydrogen, which we also projected will have a prominent role in the next decade, before switching to renewable-powered hydrogen (Section 3.3.2). Another important topic raised by Dutch experts was climate finance, which remains outside the scope of our analysis, as well as the broader economic implications of net-zero. Our modelling exercise highlights that, despite the overall negative impacts on economic growth in the EU (which, however, may be a considerable exaggeration of the actual economic impact, as they do not account for climate change damages), total investments actually increase and counterbalance any other negative shifts (mainly in terms of private consumption and trade)—see Section 3.4.1.

The subsequent national stakeholder workshops in Europe were held in person, in Athens²⁰, Venice²¹, and Berlin²². These workshops were in the context of the wider PARIS REINFORCE project, however, the timing allowed the discussion of the core findings of this study (as presented throughout Section 3). The focus of all three workshops was predominantly on the current energy crisis (as explicitly tackled in project Deliverable D4.4). Nonetheless, similar issues to those identified in the first two workshops emerged. For example, in Greece issues revolved around grid flexibility and RES diffusion capacity, and in Italy they regarded the role of key technologies (including CCS and hydrogen). In both workshops, largely driven by energy-supply challenges in Europe after Russia's invasion of Ukraine, stakeholders thoroughly discussed the evolution of gas in the EU energy mix. Despite designing our scenarios before this conflict arose (and therefore without considering the Russia-Ukraine conflict, the EU's response to it (REPowerEU), or the possibility of Russia cutting off gas supply (see discussion in Box 2), our model results showed bold reductions, with natural gas shares plummeting towards the middle of the century in most models (Section 3.2.7 and Table 8). Finally, in Germany, stakeholders reconfirmed the difficulties in decarbonising agriculture (as also pinpointed by Swiss stakeholders, see section 4.2 that discusses Member States' strategies for mitigating emissions in the agriculture and LULUCF sector, and Annex III for the poll results), although in this case significant emphasis was placed on challenges to industrial decarbonisation, as well as the perception of hydrogen and carbon-free electricity. Notably, however, German participants were experts in industrial decarbonisation. German stakeholders also highlighted the importance of hydrogen for decarbonising all energy-intensive sectors (especially iron and steel, and chemicals), which is in line with our model findings (see Section 3.3.3.2).

¹⁹ <https://www.paris-reinforce.eu/news-events/project-news-events/european-national-stakeholder-workshop-series-case-netherlands>

²⁰ <https://www.paris-reinforce.eu/news-events/project-news-events/pathways-climate-neutrality-europe-spotlight-greece-stakeholder>

²¹ <https://www.paris-reinforce.eu/news-events/project-news-events/challenges-and-progress-towards-sdg7-italy-light-todays-energy>

²² <https://www.paris-reinforce.eu/news-events/project-news-events/bottlenecks-decarbonising-german-energy-intensive-industries>

4 A deep dive into niche areas of modelling

This section complements the previous Section 3 and fills some gaps of the previous modelling exercises, it compiles three different works that address important points of the EU climate policy:

- The first is the implementation of the “Fit for 55” proposal (European Commission, 2021a) in the models, not limited to EU emissions caps as done in Section 3, but trying to consider the set of EU climate policy
- The second analyses the Member States Long-term Strategy for the agriculture, forestry and land use (AFOLU) sector to support the NZE EU objective
- The last assesses, with the GEMINI-E3 model, the impact of different implementations of an EU carbon border adjustment mechanism, following the EU proposals (European Commission, 2021h)

4.1 The WWH21+ scenario

4.1.1 Methodology

We updated the *WWH* scenarios for the EU (Nikas et al., 2021a) with the new set of policy options proposed by the European Commission (2021a), in its “Fit for 55” proposal that aims to deliver a -55% GHG emissions reduction by 2030 with respect to 1990. We call this scenario “*WWH21+*” thereafter. The scenario framework follows the “*Where are We Heading*” scenario protocol developed by Sognaes et al. (2021) and applied at an EU by Nikas et al. (2021a). It consists of (i) implementing climate policy, the “Fit for 55” proposals in our case, up to 2030 and (ii) maintaining consummate levels of effort after 2030. To project the post-2030 mitigation effort, it extends emissions caps based on past emissions intensity improvements (see Box 3 for details).

The scenario is designed to reflect current levels of mitigation efforts in the EU, referred to as current policies (CP). To extend the GHG mitigation efforts after 2030, we apply a method keeping the rate of change in emissions intensity after 2030 as it is up to 2030 in each region. This method is used by Fawcett *et al.* (2015) and Vandyck *et al.* (2016) to assess the long-term implications of INDCs. Cai *et al.* (2017) explains how emissions intensity targets can be implemented in models with endogenous GDP based on an iterative method. The emissions cap at time t and in region r is then calculated as follows:

$$EmCap_t^r = (Effect_{ref}^r)^{(t-2030)} * \left(\frac{Em_{2030}^r}{GDP_{2030}^r} \right) * GDP_t^r$$

$$Effect_{ref}^r = \left[\frac{Em_{2030}^r / GDP_{2030}^r}{Em_{ref}^r / GDP_{ref}^r} \right]^{1/(2030-ref)}$$

With Em_t^r : GHG (or CO₂) emissions at time t and in region r , GDP_t^r : the real GDP in region r at time t and $Effect_{ref}^r$ the average annual emissions efficiency factor between time ref to 2030. Please use ref=2020 when feasible.

Box 3: Scenario protocol for the WWH21+ scenario

The socio-economic parameters are the same as those in the *WWH21* scenario, *i.e.* the original set of parameters from Giarola et al. (2021), but with updated GDP projections for EU countries and updated fossil fuel prices to account for the COVID-19 pandemic, these updated GDP and fossil fuel prices are also used for the *WWH21* scenario (see section 3.1.1). For the models that do not cover LULUCF and/or non-CO₂ emissions, we utilised the assumptions proposed in Table 12. EU-27 values are similar to the ones used for the medium case of the PAC Core

scenarios (see section 3.1), except for those models that do not distinguish the UK from the rest of the EU. As the UK is no longer affected by EU policy, it will not be included in the results. The UK climate action implemented in the *WWH21* scenario in Section 3 must be the same for this *WWH21+* scenario.

European Commission (2021a), with the “*Fit for 55*” plan, proposed several amendments to the current European legislation regarding climate action. It has asked each model to implement them in the models when feasible. We summarise these updates in Table 13 below, and further details can be found in Annex VI.

Table 12: Assumptions on LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions for the WWH21+ scenario

	LULUCF emissions in 2030 MtCO ₂ eq/y.	Non-CO ₂ emissions (without LULUCF) in 2030 MtCO ₂ eq/y.
Belgium	-1.17	12.57
Bulgaria	-8.39	10.39
Czechia	-1.06	14.42
Denmark	4.61	10.90
Germany	-26.61	74.63
Estonia	-2.20	1.83
Ireland	3.22	20.92
Greece	-3.77	13.42
Spain	-37.65	48.68
France	-29.38	85.35
Croatia	-4.77	4.35
Italy	-30.86	54.97
Cyprus	-0.30	1.07
Latvia	-0.56	3.22
Lithuania	-4.00	5.40
Luxembourg	-0.35	0.78
Hungary	-4.94	10.35
Malta	0.00	0.46
Netherlands	3.90	24.04
Austria	-4.88	8.89
Poland	-32.87	60.02
Portugal	-1.17	11.27
Romania	-22.15	35.07
Slovenia	-0.13	2.81
Slovakia	-5.89	4.67
Finland	-15.32	7.39
Sweden	-40.83	7.76
EU-27	-267.5	535.5

Calculation: EU LULUCF emissions are based on the average value between the current LULUCF regulation target: -225 MtCO₂eq. (European Commission, 2018b) and the new EU target of the Fit for 55 proposals: 310 MtCO₂eq (European Commission, 2021b) and the EU value is split to calculate the national emissions using the national share of the revised LULUCF Regulation proposal (European Commission, 2021b). The EU non-CO₂ emissions are based on the average value of the European Commission scenarios (scenarios MIX-50 and ALLBNK, European Commission, 2020a) and national values are derived from the national share of the EC reference scenario 2020 (European Commission, 2021c).

Table 13: Summary of “Fit for 55” proposal

EU-ETS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extension of the EU ETS to maritime transport • EU ETS emissions reduction of 61 % by 2030 compared to 2005 • Implementation of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) • Introduction of emissions trading for buildings and road transport
ESR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESR emissions reduction of 40% by 2030 compared to 2005 • Updated National emissions reduction targets for 2030
Energy Efficiency Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New target for primary energy consumption for EU-27 in 2030: 1023 Mtoe or 787 Mtoe of final energy consumption
Renewable Energy Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least a 40% share of energy from renewable sources in the Union’s gross final consumption of energy in 2030
LULUCF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitments for 2021 – 2025 • Member States targets for 2026 – 2030 • Commitments to climate neutrality in 2035
Update Regulation of fuels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update of the “CO₂ emissions performance standards for new passenger cars and new light commercial vehicles” Regulation • Update of the “Alternative fuel Infrastructure” Regulation • Update of the “ReFuelEU Aviation” Regulation • Update of the “FuelEU Maritime” Regulation

4.1.2 Results

We present below the results for seven different models: four global models (GCAM: partial equilibrium; GEMINI-E3: general equilibrium; MUSE: energy-system model and TIAM: partial equilibrium²³), two European models (EU-TIMES: energy-system model and NEMESIS: macroeconometric model) and one European sector-specific model (FORECAST for industry and buildings)²⁴.

We start with the EU GHG and CO₂ emissions pathways up to 2050 (Figure 40). Almost all models (except MUSE) show important emissions reduction in 2030. GCAM and GEMINI-E3, covering all GHGs, project a reduction of 50% and 54% respectively compared to 1990. For CO₂ emissions, all models (except MUSE) show more than a 50% reduction compared to 1990. Using the LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions projections for EU, as calculated in the NZE scenarios in Section 3.1 (i.e. -270 MtCO₂eq. for LULUCF and 540 for non-CO₂, EU27 perimeter), the emissions projected for 2030 are closed of the -55% GHG emissions reduction of the updated European climate ambition, with some models a bit below: -53% in GCAM and -54% in TIAM. MUSE projection for 2030 differs a lot and the model does not show significant CO₂ emissions reduction, with only -45%.

In 2050, the models (except MUSE) converge towards a narrow range including between 600 and 700 Mt for EU

²³ The geographical coverage of TIAM do not allow to perfectly fit with the definition of EU27 or EU27+UK countries. In the numbers delivered in this section, TIAM covers EU27+UK, plus Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Iceland, Macedonia, Montenegro, Norway, Serbia, and Switzerland and excludes Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania.

²⁴ A detailed presentation of these models can be found on the I²AM Paris Platform : https://i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc

CO₂ emissions, as the results of the extrapolation method for post-2030. It represents a reduction between 82% and 87% compared to 1990. By including LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions, either with own models' projections or with proposed assumptions, the GHG emissions reductions range between 82% to 90% and do not lead to the EU's objective of a carbon-neutral economy in 2050, more ambition reductions should then be engaged to achieve NZE. In MUSE, the CO₂ emissions reduction reaches 56% in 2050.

Figure 40: GHG and CO₂ emissions in EU in the WWH21+ scenario (GtCO₂/y.)

GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE consider EU27+UK and TIAM geographical coverage includes EU27+UK+EFTA+Balkans but excludes Baltic states. GHG emissions do not cover LULUCF and international aviation. CO₂ emissions are emissions from energy and industrial processes. Historical values come from EEA (2022)

The projections of the CO₂ emissions by sector show also important similarities (see Figure 41). All models agree that the decarbonisation of the supply sector will be the fastest, between -55% and -78% from 2030 compared to 1990 and emissions become negative in 2050 (except in MUSE), slightly in NEMESIS with -33Mt and largely in GCAM with -680Mt. Similarly, EU CO₂ emissions from the industry and the industrial processes decline importantly, between 50 and 75% in 2050 and 70% and 83% in 2050 compared to 1990. However, in 2020, one-third of these reductions is already achieved. In 2050, it remains between 350 and 190Mt of CO₂ in the European industrial sectors. Models also converge (except MUSE) towards a large CO₂ emissions decline in the buildings sector in 2030 between 40% to 60% compared to 1990. The range is even more narrow for 2050, with between 65% and 80%, i.e. from 200 to 135Mt. For the European transport sector, models deliver different pictures. On the one hand, in 2030, GEMINI-E3, GCAM and MUSE project higher CO₂ emissions than in 1990, +24%, +8% and +1% respectively. On the other hand, EU-TIMES, NEMESIS and particularly TIAM show emissions reduction, with respectively -17%, -18% and -31% in 2030 compared to 1990. The projections for 2050 remain varied between models: GCAM shows almost no reduction (3% compared to 1990), the decline is weak in GEMINI-E3 and MUSE (14% and 32%), and more important in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS (55% and 67%) and large in TIAM (90%).

GCAM and GEMINI-E3, that model non-CO₂ emissions, project a moderated decrease of about 40% (740 and 670 MtCO₂eq. respectively) in 2030 compared to 1990 which is lower than the assumptions used in Section 3.1, of 600

MtCO₂eq. for EU27+UK. In 2050, the non-CO₂ emissions reduction do not accelerate: GCAM projects almost the same level with 700 MtCO₂eq. and GEMINI-E3 a more marked reduction with 515 MtCO₂eq. This is again above the 300 MtCO₂eq used for NZE scenarios.

The LULUCF emissions projected only by GCAM are -110 in 2030 and -60 MtCO₂ in 2050, well below our assumptions for the NZE scenarios, which were -270 and -310MtCO₂.

Figure 41: EU emissions by sector in the WWH21+ scenario (MtCO₂eq./y.)

GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE consider EU27+UK and TIAM geographical coverage includes EU27+UK+EFTA +Balkans but excludes Baltic states. Only GCAM covers LULUCF emissions and GCAM and GEMINI-E3 non-CO₂ emissions. CO₂ emissions are emissions from energy and industrial processes.

These CO₂ emissions reductions are supported by a decline in the total energy consumed in three models on the six: GEMINI-E3, MUSE and NEMESIS (Figure 42). The three others show either relative stability in comparison to 2020 (EU-TIMES or TIAM) or an increase as in GCAM. In 2030, only GEMINI-E3, with 1,164 Mtoe, reaches the updated primary energy consumption target of the "Fit for 55" proposal (European Commission, 2021f) of 1,023 Mtoe in 2030 for the EU (corrected to 1,160 for EU27+UK, own calculation). NEMESIS is slightly above the target with 1,111 Mtoe, EU-TIMES, MUSE and GCAM are further: 1,306, 1,555 and 1,603 Mtoe respectively. This is more difficult to compare for TIAM because of the diverge in the countries' coverage. In 2050, the level of primary energy consumption does not differ significantly from 2030, except in GEMINI-E3 and MUSE, in which the energy saving continues and in GCAM which projects higher energy consumption.

In 2030, the share of fossil fuel is declining in all models, except in GEMINI-E3 which relies more on energy saving to reduce emissions. In 2050, fossil energy represents between 31% to 75% according to models. GEMINI-E3 shows the highest share (75%), whereas EU-TIMES, GCAM and TIAM project a share below 50% and even below one-third for NEMESIS (31%). Obviously, the importance of renewable energy sources (RES) grows in all models, in share in the energy mix as well as in absolute value (except for some specific renewable energy technologies).

Even if because of different calculations, the comparison is difficult, we can say the 40% target for the EU RES share in 2030 (European Commission, 2021e) seems out of reach for GEMINI-E3, EU-TIMES and MUSE and achievable for NEMESIS, TIAM and GCAM. In 2050, the RES share reaches more than 50% in NEMESIS and TIAM (58% and 55%), a bit less in GCAM and EU-TIMES, (47% and 43%) and significantly less in MUSE and GEMINI-E3 (29% and 18%). The renewable energy sources mobilised by the model are not necessarily the same. EU-TIMES, NEMESIS, TIAM and particularly GCAM rely significantly on bioenergy to reduce emissions. These four models also push massively solar energy into the energy mix. It is similar to wind energy and particularly in TIAM, with wind representing 20% of the EU's primary energy in 2050.

Figure 42: EU primary energy consumption by fuel in the WWH21+ scenario (Mtoe/y.)

GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE consider EU27+UK and TIAM geographical coverage includes EU27+UK+EFTA +Balkans but excludes Baltic states. Nuclear is harmonised among models and accounted as nuclear heat like in Eurostat, with an efficiency factor of 33%.

The EU final energy consumption (Figure 43) declines all along the period for four of the seven models: FORECAST, GEMINI-E3, MUSE and NEMESIS. It reduces between 2020 and 2030 and stays thereafter stable in GCAM whereas it goes up the last decade in TIAM. In EU-TIMES, the European final energy consumption remains relatively stable between 2020 and 2050. The comparison of our models' projections with the EU energy efficiency objective (787 Mtoe of final energy consumption in 2030 in EU27, and around 870 for EU27+UK, own calculation), does not change the findings observed with the primary energy consumption. GEMINI-E3 is close to the EU target, with 900 Mtoe for EU27+UK²⁵. It is also the case for NEMESIS with 800 Mtoe in 2030 for EU27. The others are well above

²⁵ The numbers excluded the non-energy use consumption.

the target with 870 in EU-TIMES, 900 in GCAM and 1,030 Mtoe in MUSE.

Between 2020 and 2030, there is almost no difference in the final energy consumed by the different sectors in EU-TIMES, except in the residential sector, with -12%. It is a bit similar In FORECAST, in which the final energy in the industry, commercial and residential sectors slightly declines (between 4% and 7%). MUSE does not show important evolutions, with no change for transport, almost stable final energy consumption in the residential and tertiary sector (+3% and -2% respectively) and a slight decrease for the industry (6%). NEMESIS, GEMINI-E3 and TIAM show larger reductions in the industry (10%, 19% and 25% respectively) and in the transport sector for the two latter (with 10% and 25%) and more market for the transport of passengers and the freight in TIAM (35% against 19%). It is observable in GCAM with -19% for passengers against no change for freight.

In 2050, only -GEMINI-E3 and FORECAST project significant final energy savings in the buildings sector, the others expecting relative stability of the energy consumed. In all models, except in EU-TIMES, the energy consumption of the European transport sector declines, by more than 30% for TIAM and GEMINI-E3, more than 20% in NEMESIS and MUSE and more than 10% in GCAM. For the European industry, four models, GEMINI-E3, FORECAST, MUSE and NEMESIS project a reduction of its final energy consumption (from 40% to 20% compared to 2020). This reduction is weaker in EU-TIMES with 5% and null in GCAM and TIAM.

Figure 43: EU final energy by sector in the WWH21+ scenario (Mtoe/y.)

GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE consider EU27+UK and TIAM geographical coverage includes EU27+UK+EFTA +Balkans but excludes Baltic states. GEMINI-E3 does not deliver output on "non-energy use". For models allowing the split between Commercial and Residential and between Transports for freight and passenger, their sum equals the respective aggregate (Buildings and Transports respectively).

The reduction of the CO₂ emissions in the WWH21+ scenario takes also place through the electrification of the final energy uses (Table 14), allowed by the decarbonisation of the power sector (Figure 41). The share of electricity in the EU final energy consumption grows in all models between 2020 and 2030, weakly in GEMINI-E3 and MUSE

(+0.7 and +1.5 ppt respectively), moderately in EU-TIMES (+2.8 ppt), significantly in NEMESIS and TIAM (+5.4 and +7.1 ppt) and strongly in GCAM (+19.4 ppt). The penetration of electricity in the final energy mix continues up to 2050 in all models even if generally at a lower rate than in the first decade. The share of electricity reaches more than 50% in TIMES, more than 40% in GCAM and NEMESIS and around 30% in EU-TIMES, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE.

Table 14: Share of electricity in the total EU final energy consumption in the WWH21+ scenario

Share of electricity in the European final energy consumption					
	2015*	2020	2030	2040	2050
EU-TIMES	23%	22.4%	25.2%	28.0%	32.6%
GCAM		21.1%	40.5%	46.6%	45.8%
GEMINI-E3		25.2%	25.8%	28.2%	32.0%
MUSE		20.1%	21.7%	28.1%	28.1%
NEMESIS		26.4%	31.8%	38.4%	44.1%
TIAM		27.6%	34.7%	49.5%	58.1%

*: source Eurostat (2022a), similar values for EU27 and EU27+UK. GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE consider EU27+UK and TIAM geographical coverage includes EU27+UK+EFTA +Balkans but excludes Baltic states.

The decarbonisation of the European power generation sector is fully achieved by all models (except MUSE) in 2050 and even from 2040 in GCAM (Figure 44). It takes place by the decline of fossil fuels consumption not coupled with carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies and of which the remaining uses are over-balanced by bio-energy CCS (BECCS) between 2040 and 2050. The phasing out of coal (without CCS), measured as less than 2% in the total electricity mix, is achieved from 2040 in EU-TIMES and GEMINI-E3 and 2050 for all others, except for MUSE. Differently, natural gas remains in the European electricity mix up to 2050, except in TIAM and MUSE in which it phases out between 2040 and 2050

Figure 44: EU power generation by source in the WWH21+ scenario (Mtoe/y)

GCAM, GEMINI-E3 and MUSE consider EU27+UK and TIAM geographical coverage includes EU27+UK+EFTA +Balkans but excludes Baltic states

In 2030, GCAM and NEMESIS project that bio-energy uses in power generation will progress importantly. It is even more largely shared among models for solar and wind energy (except in MUSE). Electricity from solar energy is multiplied by more than four in GCAM and NEMESIS, more than three in EU-TIMES and by two in TIAM. Electricity from wind triples in GCAM and doubles in NEMESIS and TIAM. Hydro-electricity production is also expected to grow in all models, but at a lower rate, up to +25% in MUSE (compared to 2020). Finally, nuclear energy is mobilised moderately in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS to decarbonise the European sector, more importantly in TIAM and GCAM and not in MUSE and GEMINI-E3.

In 2050, the dynamics of the electricity sources remains relatively the same as the ones observed for 2030. Biomass, mainly coupled with CCS, is more largely mobilised by the different models. Wind energy is the largest electricity source in TIAM, EU-TIMES, GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS, with more than 50% of the electricity mix in TIAM, almost 40% in EU-TIMES and a bit more than one quarter for the two later. Solar also has a great place in the EU electricity mix in 2050, with 20% or more in NEMESIS, GCAM and TIAM and more than 15% in EU-TIMES and MUSE. Finally, hydro has a major role in MUSE (36%) whereas GCAM relies more on nuclear energy (31%).

Figure 45: GDP and components deviation by Member State in the WWH21+ scenario (in ppt of GDP, w.r.t WWH21)

Caution: scales differ between sub-figures. Source: NEMESIS model. Results are presented in difference compared to the WWH21 scenario presented in Section 3.1.1.

Figure 45 presents the deviation of the Member States' GDP and components deviations in the WWH21+ scenario in comparison to the WWH21 one. At an EU level, the NEMESIS model shows the weak impact of the scenario on the EU GDP²⁶. For 2030, the implementation of the "Fit for 55" proposal in NEMESIS leads to a slight GDP gain for the EU, with +0.33% in comparison to WWH21, but this gain vanishes progressively and is null 2040 and even slightly negative in 2050 with -0.1%. The EU GDP is positively impacted by the rise of investment, but, because climate policy is unilaterally implemented in the NEMESIS model, the European competitiveness is reduced, and relative prices go up, leading to lower exports and a decline in internal demand; mainly the private consumption as imports are favoured by the increase of the EU internal prices. This raises concerns about the implementation of an EU Carbon Border Adjustment mechanism (CBAM) compared to the rest of the World (see Section 4.3 for a modelling exercise on CBAM).

At a Member State level, the impact on GDP differs, some are positively impacted, especially up to 2030. It is the case for instance in Belgium, Spain or Romania. While others face a negative impact on GDP from 2030, as in Ireland or Poland, very modestly in 2030 with -0.1% and -0.2% respectively and more marked in 2050, with -0.8% and -1.2%.

²⁶ It is important to note that, in NEMESIS, carbon revenues are recycled to private actors (firms and households) proportionally to the direct cost that the implementation of carbon prices induces for them (without international transfers). This may differ from EU existing policies, as for the auctioning of the permits in EU-ETS (European Commission, 2020c).

The impact of GDP in the *WWH21+* scenarios depends mainly on the relative impact of the climate policies on the Member States' competitiveness. It is typically the case in Ireland where, in 2050, exports' reduction in comparison to *WWH21* contributes to -1.1 ppt of GDP. The impact of GDP is also driven by the change in the internal demand which, in almost all countries, pushes GDP up but that is a long-term impact on firms' production cost and their prices, leading to lower household consumption and relatively higher imports.

4.1.3 Summary

In summary, we mobilised seven different models to update the "Current Policy" or "Where are We Heading" scenario for the EU considering the recent reinforcement of the EU climate ambition for 2030, the "Fit for 55" proposal, (European Commission, 2021a). The results of this scenario, called *WWH21+*, show that our models, except MUSE, project that the update of EU policies will allow the achievement of the -55% emissions reduction in 2050 by accelerating the decarbonisation in almost all sectors but particularly in the energy supply sector, that is, the power generation sector, part of the EU-ETS. Nevertheless, maintaining this emissions mitigation effort thereafter will lead to around 650 Mt of CO₂ emissions that will probably be too high to reach the 2050 NZE target, regarding the potential for non-CO₂ and LULUCF emissions and additional effort will then be required.

Nevertheless, the 2030 objectives will engage the EU towards a strong transition of its energy system that will rely more on electricity and significantly less on fossil fuel energy. To achieve this energy transition, our models mobilise some common levers such as the large deployment of wind and solar energy and, in a longer term, of BECCS, but to a different extent. Hydro and nuclear energy are also expected to play a role, even if their growth will be limited. Finally, energy efficiency, not mobilised by all models, will be crucial for some to alleviate the expansion requirement in renewable energy sources.

Besides individual cases, the impact on GDP of the energy transition to mitigate climate change will require supporting some regions in which the transition could be more costly that is the aim of the Just Transition Mechanisms of the European Commission supporting "*regions, industries and workers who will face the greatest challenges*". Nevertheless, JTM has some limitations (Moesker and Pesch, 2022) and should also be complemented by appropriated national (Berghmans, 2021) and/or sectoral support policies (Galgóczy, 2020; Pianta and Lucchese, 2020).

4.2 The EU countries' long-term strategies for AFOLU

4.2.1 Background

All Parties that undersigned the Paris Agreement had to communicate Long-Term Strategies (LTSs) (sometimes called Long-Term low GHG emission development Strategies or Mid-Century Strategies) by 2020, as determined by Art. 4.19 of the Agreement and Decision 1/CP.21 (UNFCCC, 2015). Commonly, LTSs deal with mitigation however Parties can add any other aspect, such as adaptation and sustainable development goals (SDGs). The EU submitted its LTS to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in March 2020 (European Union, 2020a). EU MSs are also required to develop national LTSs, which have to describe how they plan to meet the long-term goal of the Paris Agreement and the EU objectives. No specific prescriptions are imposed on the Parties on the methods to develop and submit the LTSs. There are neither guidance nor reporting requirements to develop LTSs, nor do they undergo third-party technical review; however, at an EU level, the process for MSs to prepare the strategies is defined in the Regulation on the governance of the energy union and

climate action (EU/2018/1999)²⁷. It invites MSs to build their strategies transparently and, preferably, whilst engaging the public in the process. Furthermore, it highlights the importance for the LTSs to be consistent with MSs' integrated national energy and climate plans for the period 2021-2030, and to cover, with a perspective of at least 30 years²⁸, the following aspects:

- total greenhouse gas emission reductions and enhancements of removals by sinks for all relevant sectors, such as electricity, industry, transport, the heating and cooling and buildings sector (residential and tertiary), agriculture, waste and land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF);
- how to deliver the low GHG transition whilst maintaining a globally competitive and innovative industry;
- how a just and socially fair transition will be ensured, explaining to the extent feasible the expected socio-economic effect of decarbonisation measures, including economic as well as health risks and benefits and environmental protection;
- links to other national long-term objectives, planning and other policies and measures, and investment.

In order to have a coherent framework among the EU objectives and targets as well as the single state's pledges, the European Commission provides technical and scientific support to MSs before integrating the strategies with additional information. Finally, the European Commission assesses the national LTSs, framing them in the broader context of EU objectives and targets, and provides information on any remaining collective gaps.

The LTS represents a useful tool (i) to provide direction to future Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), (ii) to enlarge the vision summarised in them and (iii) to envision where a country wants to be in terms of sustainable development up to mid-century. Designing such a strategy requires ambition and a comprehensive understanding of all the interconnected socio-economic and environmental processes that will contribute to global climate change solutions. Credible and stable LTSs support the successful achievement of the socio-economic transformation aimed by the Paris Agreement. Furthermore, LTSs constitute an important tool as they allow the comparison between individual countries' policy approaches, decarbonisation trajectories and practical measures with both their own pledged emissions reduction and EU climate-neutrality goal. Through LTS reports, each country indicates the role of the land sector (including agriculture) in the achievement of carbon neutrality by 2050.

This analysis aims to assess the AFOLU-based measures foreseen by EU MSs in their LTSs for achieving climate neutrality by 2050, evaluate the role attributed to the AFOLU sector in the reduction of emissions and enhancement of the carbon removals and assess whether the mitigation potential, as reported by literature, is fully exploited.

4.2.2 Methodology

We analysed all the available LTS reports submitted by EU MSs and compiled the AFOLU-based Policies and Measures (PaMs) for climate change mitigation and adaptation. Totally, we collected the twenty-one LTSs from the European Commission²⁹ and UNFCCC³⁰ websites. We considered the following definition of measures given

²⁷ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2018.328.01.0001.01.ENG

²⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/energy-climate-change-environment/implementation-eu-countries/energy-and-climate-governance-and-reporting/national-long-term-strategies_en

²⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/energy-climate-change-environment/implementation-eu-countries/energy-and-climate-governance-and-reporting/national-long-term-strategies_en

³⁰ <https://unfccc.int/documents/210328>

in Regulation (EU) No 525/2013: “all instruments which aim to implement commitments under Article 4(2)(a) and (b) of the UNFCCC, which may include those that do not have the limitation and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions as a primary objective” (European Union, 2013). We only collected PaMs from countries that explained either how they could be implemented or their potential expected benefit through specific actions or objectives. We analysed the LTSs and searched for all the land-based PaMs for climate change mitigation and adaptation, as long as the country presented at least an overall concept of the expected benefits and the needed actions to achieve them, possibly through a stepwise approach. Therefore, we excluded statements of general objectives, for example, ‘promote sustainable agriculture’. LTS reports often vary considerably from one country to another, both in contents and format, for example, not all provide details on the contribution of each sector in the achievement of their national long-term target.

We aimed to assess the role played by AFOLU in the EU low carbon emission strategy; however, the LTSs do not include quantitative estimates of the potential carbon emissions and removals for each PaM. Thus, the PaMs collected in the LTSs were compared and associated with the land-based measures defined in the study by Roe et al. (2021), which provides a quantitative estimate (in tCO₂eq) for a set of twenty measures for all the EU countries from 2020 to 2050 (Table 15). It must be highlighted that the estimations from individual mitigation measures cannot be directly summarised due to potential interactions between measures and multiple carbon pools and fluxes may be affected simultaneously, or some measures may be in competition over the same land use. Roe et al. (2021) estimated two types of mitigation potential: the “technical” potential (possible with available technology, regardless of the cost) and the “cost-effective” economic potential (possible up to \$100/tCO₂eq). A limitation of the “technical” potentials is that under certain circumstances they may not be plausible or desirable due to economic, social, political, or environmental constraints and trade-offs. Nevertheless, we utilised this “technical” potential as a metric for the definition of a qualitative index (*i.e.* categorical and ordinal index) of potential carbon benefits deriving from the implementation of the pledges included in the LTSs. We classified all the collected PaMs by sector as done in Roe et al. (2021) excluding seven that were not represented in any LTS (reduce deforestation, reduce mangrove loss, grassland fire management, mangrove restoration, rice cultivation, increase clean cookstoves, BECCS). Then, we converted the quantitative estimates provided by them into a 5-level category classification system, where one [+] indicates negligible or null, [++] low, [+++] moderate, [++++] high and [+++++] very high mitigation potential. The conversion was done by assigning the highest score to the PaM with the highest value of mitigation potential and accordingly, we calculated all the other scores proportionally. In this way, each PaM has an index, which reflects the relative mitigation potential for a specific country. In our results, we report the emissions and removals values of both the PaMs envisaged in the LTS and those that were not even mentioned. In this way, we can highlight whether the LTSs miss measures with remarkable relevance in terms of climate change mitigation.

Table 15: Estimation of the mitigation potential of land-based measures from 2020 to 2050 (in MtCO₂/yr.)

Category	Forests and other ecosystems				Agriculture							Demand side		Total
	Restoration		Managem ent	Protection	Emissions reduction			Carbon sequestration				Demand side		
	Afforestat ion and reforestati on	Peatland restoratio n	Forest Mngt	Reduce peatland degradati on and conversio n	Enteric fermentati on	Manure Mngt	Nutrient Mngt	Soil carbon croplands	Soil carbon grasslands	Agrofores try	Biochar	Food waste	Healthy diets	
Austria	1.7	0.0	4.7	0.0	0.5	0.3	0.2	1.2	2.0	2.7	1.9	1.6	4.2	22.7
Belgium	0.4	0.0	1.6	0.0	0.6	0.8	0.4	1.5	1.1	1.4	0.7	2.1	5.6	16.4
Croatia	1.1	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.4	1.8	0.9	4.2	1.7	0.6	1.5	22.3
Czechia	2.4	0.0	2.7	0.0	0.5	0.2	0.3	1.8	1.7	6.2	2.4	0.6	1.6	22.4
Denmark	0.6	5.5	8.1	0.0	0.5	1.4	0.2	3.2	0.2	4.4	1.8	1.3	3.5	30.7
Estonia	0.8	12.6	2.5	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.2	2.0	0.4	0.2	0.5	23.9
Finland	3.5	44.7	25.6	0.0	0.3	0.2	0.4	4.0	0.2	1.3	0.6	1.2	3.3	86.3
France	13.4	4.0	11.1	0.4	4.4	1.9	3.2	10.7	7.6	0.7	20.8	14.9	39.1	158.9
Germany	5.4	36.7	17.0	2.2	3.2	3.7	3.4	9.8	6.7	22.0	10.2	11.9	31.4	167.2
Greece	2.5	0.0	2.3	0.0	0.5	0.4	0.3	1.3	1.4	7.4	2.2	1.7	4.5	24.5
Hungary	1.1	1.3	1.5	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	1.4	0.6	10.3	8.0	0.9	2.5	31.9
Italy	6.4	0.0	2.9	0.0	1.8	1.8	2.1	5.9	3.1	28.0	8.2	11.3	29.7	106.6
Latvia	1.5	11.2	4.2	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.5	1.8	3.0	0.9	0.2	0.6	28.5
Lithuania	1.1	7.7	1.9	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.2	0.9	5.0	1.6	0.4	1.0	25.4
Malta	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3
Netherlan ds	0.2	9.1	0.5	0.1	1.2	2.9	1.2	1.2	1.1	2.1	0.5	3.4	9.1	32.5
Portugal	1.6	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.1	10.6	0.6	2.0	5.3	33.6
Slovak Republic	1.0	0.0	3.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.0	0.6	3.4	1.9	0.4	1.1	14.1
Slovenia	0.6	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.2	1.3	0.2	0.3	0.8	7.1
Spain	10.4	0.2	11.2	0.0	2.0	4.5	3.3	5.9	4.4	78.2	7.6	6.5	17.2	163.0
Sweden	5.2	8.8	28.3	0.0	0.4	0.1	0.4	4.4	1.8	4.1	1.1	1.9	5.0	62.7
Total	60.9	141.8	136.8	5.8	16.6	19.1	17.0	64.3	36.5	198.1	73.4	63.7	167.6	1003

Source: Roe et al. (2021). Mmgt = Management.

4.2.3 Results

Some countries have not submitted any LTS yet (updated May 2022), even if the governance regulation required submitting it to the European Commission by the 1st of January 2020 (Table 16). The majority of MSs submitted their LTSs in English, while 25% used their national language and provided an English summary. To organise the data in a systematic and comparable way, the next three sections present the PaMs divided into three mitigation categories, as done in Roe et al. (2021): forests and other ecosystems, agriculture and demand side.

Table 16: Summary data on the LTS submitted by the Member States

LTS analysed	Available in full English version	Available in national language (summary available in English)
Austria	✓	
Belgium		✓
Croatia		✓
Czechia		✓
Denmark	✓	
Estonia	✓	
Finland	✓	
France	✓	
Germany	✓	
Greece		✓
Hungary	✓	
Italy		✓
Latvia	✓	
Lithuania	✓	
Malta	✓	
Netherlands	✓	
Portugal	✓	
Slovak Republic	✓	
Slovenia	✓	
Spain	✓	
Sweden	✓	

4.2.4 Forests and other ecosystems

The mitigation category ‘Forests and other ecosystems’ includes three classes: restoration, management and protection (Table 17). Results show that the mitigation potential of forest management PaMs (management class) is substantial, and over 70% of the countries intend to exploit forests as an emissions reduction mechanism. Austria, Slovakia and Sweden, which can count on a very high contribution from forests [+++++], have considered forest management in their Long-Term Strategies (LTSs). Denmark did not mention forest management in the LTS and did not clearly define the role of LULUCF in relation to the 2030 and 2050 targets in its LTS. However, we cannot exclude the potential for forest management to become prominent, considering the very high mitigation potential for the country. Italy, Malta and Netherlands, which are the only three countries where forest management would provide a negligible or null contribution, did not include such measures in their LTSs. Afforestation and reforestation (restoration class) are carbon dioxide removal methods that 15 out of 21 countries consider in their LTSs. These methods have a low mitigation potential in over half of the countries, and for the remaining ones, the potential is negligible or null, excluding Czechia, where there it is moderate.

‘Peatland restoration’ (*restoration class*) and ‘Reduce peatland degradation and conversion’ (*protection class*) are

included in 28% and 42% of the analysed LTS reports, respectively. These measures concern very specific geographical areas and ecosystems mainly located in Northern Europe. In particular, 'Reduce peatland degradation and conversion' have negligible or null potential with respect to other land measures. 'Peatland restoration' potential varies considerably across countries and only two north European countries, Estonia and Lithuania, plan to implement measures to restore the original form and function of peatland habitats. Five countries did not present peatland as a possibility to reduce CO₂ emissions, even though the contribution would be high or very high: Denmark, Finland, Germany, Latvia and Netherlands.

Table 17: Mitigation Policies and Measures (PaMs) envisaged in the LTS under the category related to forests and other ecosystems

Mitigation classification	Restoration		Management		Protection
	Afforestation and reforestation	Peatland restoration	Forest management	Reduce peatland degradation and conversion	
Austria	++	+	[+++++]		+
Belgium	+	+	[++]		[+]
Croatia	[++]	+	[++]		+
Czechia	[+++]	[+]	[+++]		+
Denmark	[+]	++++	+++++		[+]
Estonia	+	[+++++]	[++]		[+]
Finland	[+]	+++++	+++		[+]
France	[++]	[+]	[++]		[+]
Germany	[++]	+++++	[+++]		[+]
Greece	++	+	++		+
Hungary	[+]	+	[++]		+
Italy	[++]	+	+		+
Latvia	[++]	+++++	[+++]		+
Lithuania	[++]	[+++++]	[++]		[+]
Malta	[+]	+	+		+
Netherlands	[+]	+++++	+		+
Portugal	[++]	+	[+++]		+
Slovakia	[++]	[+]	[+++++]		[+]
Slovenia	++	+	[+++]		+
Spain	[++]	+	[++]		+
Sweden	++	[++]	[+++++]		[+]

The green-coloured sign in brackets indicates that the PaM is reported in the country's LTS, while the grey colour without brackets indicates that the PaM is missing. The mitigation potential is expressed as follows: one [+] negligible or null, [++] low, [+++] moderate, [++++] high and [+++++] very high.

4.2.5 Agriculture

The mitigation category 'agriculture' includes two classes: emissions reduction and carbon sequestration (Table 18). The analysed LTS reports contain three measures belonging to the emission reduction class: enteric fermentation, manure management and nutrient management. These measures do not show remarkable differences in their mitigation potential among countries. Overall, the potential to reduce emissions in agriculture through enteric fermentation, manure management and nutrient management is relatively modest, mainly including measures with negligible, low or modest mitigation potential, *i.e.*, from one [+] to three [+++]. Although the mitigation potential of such measures is relatively low in Europe with respect to the whole land sector, almost all countries aim to reduce emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management up to 2050. Denmark and Greece are exceptions, since the AFOLU role in relation to the 2030 and 2050 targets is mostly undefined in their LTSs. The last measures to reduce emissions in agriculture relate to the management of nutrients, including optimised fertiliser application rate, fertiliser type (organic manures, compost and mineral), timing, precision application, and nitrification inhibitors. Their mitigation potential is null or negligible and only Croatia, Finland and Lithuania considered these measures in their LTSs.

Carbon sequestration measures (such as biochar and biogas) have the largest mitigation potential, with substantial differences among countries. Agroforestry (another method to increase carbon sequestration) has the largest potential to reduce emissions, whilst simultaneously increasing removals among the other agricultural measures in all countries. Unfortunately, only five included it in their LTSs, and seven countries that hold high and very high mitigation potential from agroforestry did not consider it. At the same time, agroforestry is also the approach that has the most diverse impact on carbon dynamics according to the place of implementation: the effectiveness in many north European countries is low or null/negligible, yet very high in Mediterranean countries. Finally, an increase of soil carbon in cropland and grassland may provide a low or moderate contribution to carbon sequestration, and eleven out of twenty-one countries considered this measure in their LTSs.

Table 18: Mitigation Policies and Measures envisaged in the LTS under the category related to agriculture

Mitigation classification	Emissions reduction			Carbon sequestration			
	Enteric fermentation	Manure management	Nutrient management	Soil carbon croplands	Soil carbon grasslands	Agroforestry	Biochar and biogas
Austria	[+]	[+]	+	[++]	[+++]	+++	[+++]
Belgium	[+]	[++]	+	[++]	[++]	[++]	[++]
Croatia	[+]	[+]	[+]	[++]	[+]	[+++]	[++]
Czechia	[+]	[+]	+	[++]	[++]	+++++	[+++]
Denmark	+	++	+	+++	+	+++	++
Estonia	+	[+]	+	+	+	++	[+]
Finland	+	[+]	[+]	+	+	+	[+]
France	[+]	[+]	+	++	++	[+]	[+++]
Germany	[+]	[+]	+	++	++	+++	[++]
Greece	+	+	+	++	++	+++++	[++]
Hungary	[+]	[+]	+	[++]	[+]	+++++	[++++]
Italy	[+]	[+]	+	[++]	[+]	+++++	[++]
Latvia	[+]	[+]	+	++	++	++	[+]
Lithuania	[+]	[+]	[+]	[+++]	[+]	++++	[++]
Malta	[+]	[+]	+	+	+	++	+
Netherlands	[++]	[++]	++	[++]	[+]	++	+
Portugal	[+]	[+]	+	+	+	+++++	[+]
Slovak Republic	[+]	[+]	+	[++]	[++]	[+++++]	[+++]
Slovenia	[+]	[+]	+	[++]	[+]	++++	[++]
Spain	[+]	[+]	+	[+]	[+]	[+++++]	[+]
Sweden	[+]	[+]	+	++	+	++	[+]

The green-coloured sign in brackets indicates that the PaM is reported in the country's LTS, while the grey colour without brackets indicates that the PaM is missing. The mitigation potential is expressed as follows: one [+] negligible or null, [++] low, [+++] moderate, [++++] high and [+++++] very high.

4.2.6 Demand side

The mitigation category 'demand side' includes only the class demand side (Table 19) and two PaMs: food waste and healthy diets. The demand-side class covers PaMs for influencing the demand for goods and/or services. In the land sector, demand-side management aims at reducing the demand for products with a large carbon footprint and environmental impact. The collected demand-side policies present relatively high mitigation potential among the land-based PaMs. This fact is acknowledged by the great majority of countries, who present and describe these methods in their LTSs. Promoting healthy diets is the most impactful policy in this class, and all countries mention it as necessary to reach carbon emission targets in 2030 and 2050, despite its contribution differing substantially among countries. The promotion of healthy diets represents a range of dietary changes to improve human diets, making them healthier in terms of the nutrition delivered, and also sustainable from an economic, social and environmental perspective. The carbon benefits resulting from a reduction of food waste vary substantially among the reporting countries, and two-thirds of them present this measure in their LTSs. Besides the actual potential of this strategy to mitigate climate change, tackling food waste is a key Sustainable Development Goal and the EU (alongside all EU countries) should be committed to meeting Target 12.3 of the Sustainable Development Goals, "by 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses".

Table 19: Mitigation Policies and Measures envisaged in the LTS under the category related to demand-side

Mitigation classification	Demand-side	
	Food waste	Healthy diets
Austria	[++]	[+++++]
Belgium	[+++]	[+++++]
Croatia	[+]	[++]
Czechia	[+]	[++]
Denmark	[++]	[+++]
Estonia	+	[+]
Finland	+	[+]
France	[+++]	[+++++]
Germany	[++]	[+++++]
Greece	++	[+++]
Hungary	[+]	[++]
Italy	+++	[+++++]
Latvia	+	[+]
Lithuania	[+]	[++]
Malta	[+++]	[+++++]
Netherlands	[+++]	[+++++]
Portugal	[++]	[+++]
Slovak Republic	[+]	[++]
Slovenia	++	[+++]
Spain	[+]	[++]
Sweden	+	[++]

The green-coloured sign in brackets indicates that the PaM is reported in the country's LTS, while the grey colour without brackets indicates that the PaM is missing. The mitigation potential is expressed as follows: one [+] negligible or null, [++] low, [+++] moderate, [++++] high and [+++++] very high.

4.2.7 Summary and discussion

The expectations and requirements surrounding the role of Agricultural Forestry and Other Land Uses (AFOLU) in climate change mitigation are high (European Commission, 2021c; Grassi et al., 2013). In fact, besides Carbon Capture and Storage, the only other way to compensate for residual emissions (*i.e.* those hard-to-abate emissions that will be still emitted even after all reasonable efforts have been made to reduce them) is through AFOLU-based solutions. It gives the AFOLU sector a crucial responsibility, since addressing residual emissions is a necessary requirement to reach the 1.5 °C goal (Luderer, et al., 2018). As such, the EU relies heavily on the LULUCF sector to absorb (and compensate for) residual emissions, and the EU is required to nearly double the sector's sink capacity to achieve net removals of 425 MtCO₂e by 2050 (European Union, 2020).

The EU MS incorporate a wide range of AFOLU-based measures in their LTSs for achieving climate neutrality by 2050. This indicates that MSs have evaluated the role of AFOLU, relying on it to reduce GHG emissions, even though the LTSs do not transparently or accurately describe how each MS plans to achieve the mid-century climate target. In fact, most LTSs present general intentions, measures and objectives, rather than absolute aims, and 40% of the EU's LTSs lack quantitative data on future LULUCF emissions and removals.

In the mitigation category 'Forests and other ecosystems', forest management plays a key role throughout the EU, and the vast majority of MSs consider forest management essential to reach their climate targets. While in the mitigation categories 'agriculture' and 'demand side', the most important policies and measures are agroforestry and promoting healthy diets, respectively. All countries committed to promoting healthy diets over the next 30 years, demonstrating to be involved in such an important action. Agroforestry, despite having a very high mitigation potential, is not prioritised by the majority of countries, which conversely aim to reduce emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management, although the mitigation potential of such measures is relatively low with respect to other land-based measures. The mitigation potential of AFOLU-based PaMs, as well as their benefits and trade-offs, can vary substantially across countries depending on the place and time of their implementation. For example, agroforestry is very effective, and applicable, in Mediterranean countries, whereas peatland restoration is most effective in Northern countries.

4.3 EU carbon border adjustment mechanisms

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4.3.1 EU CBAM under EU Fit for 55 packages

As part of the new policy initiative of the European Green Deal, the European Union (EU) Commission has initiated the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) to reduce the risk of carbon leakage and to ensure competitive prices in the European market (European Commission, 2019a). A more stringent abatement target could potentially trigger a reallocation of production to other countries that are more lenient leading to carbon leakage and increasing their GHG emissions. CBAM is proposed, amongst various other policy measures, to support a newly defined emissions reduction target of 55% from the 1990 level by 2030 and reach carbon neutrality by 2050. Achieving this new climate ambition needs a substantial and rapid reduction in the current emissions quota, and CBAM supports the transition to stop free allowances under the EU-ETS (Munro, 2018). At the initial stage, CBAM as a carbon-based import tariff will be applied to power sectors and Energy Intensive Industries (EII) – the hardest sectors to decarbonise that are constantly receiving free allowances to keep competitive.

CBAM is a climate policy instrument that is increasingly being considered as an attempt to create an equal playing field *in the global carbon market* through carbon-based import tariffs on certain goods in the EU. Without CBAM, however, the EU would experience substantial carbon leakage and export declines (Marcu et al., 2020; Vögele et al., 2020). Whilst there are conflicting results regarding the exact significance and magnitude, most studies focussing on the EU confirm that a CBAM reduces leakage (Elliott et al., 2010; Böhringer et al., 2012a; Bednar-Friedl et al., 2012). A recent study by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2021), for example, suggests that the CBAM can be an effective instrument to substantially reduce carbon leakage, with a 44 US\$ per tonne carbon tax reducing leakage by over half (from 13.3 to 5.2%).

The implementation of a CBAM will likely be highly complex as it must be compatible with both the World Trade Organisation (WTO) rules and the EU Free Trade Agreement. This mechanism needs to be transparent and impartial, without disguised restrictions and constitutions on international trade (European Commission, 2021g). From a legal perspective, the EU's CBAM can only be applied to sectors that are also subject to an internal EU carbon price in order to be compatible with the EU's WTO commitments (Cendra, 2006; Evans et al., 2021). At the initial stage, the domestic carbon price will likely be determined by the purchasing permit cost of domestic producers in the EU ETS (Lowe, 2021). This constraint limits the CBAM's scope in sectors currently covered by the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), mostly energy-intensive industries such as cement, steel, aluminium, and fertiliser production. The latest EU legislative proposal targets the power sector and EII sectors to be included in this mechanism (European Commission, 2021h).

While the EU import share of the power sector is relatively insignificant, particular attention needs to be paid to EIs. EIs represent the foundations of critical and strategic value chains for the EU, including pulp and paper, basic chemicals, refining, iron and steel, nonferrous metals (primarily aluminium), and non-metallic minerals (primarily cement) (EIA definition of EI cited from Bassi et al., 2009). EIs represent 15% of industrial EU CO₂ emissions and are often classified as one of the most difficult for full decarbonisation, thus continue to receive a substantial free allocation in the EU ETS market (European Commission, 2021g). CBAM intends to stop free permit allowances, which will lead to stringent carbon tariffs levied on EI imports.

In general, studies investigating CBAM (Babiker and Rutherford, 2005; Mattoo et al., 2009; Böhringer et al., 2010; Winchester et al., 2011), including the EU as a unilateral region (Elliott et al., 2010; Böhringer et al., 2012b; Bednar-Friedl et al., 2012) focus on the implication of carbon leakage and competitiveness issue due to changes in production output. Three aspects emerge from these prior analyses. First, the CBAM reduces leakage and provides gains in global cost-effectiveness when unilateral action is taken. Second, CBAM attenuates adverse output effects for EIs in unilaterally regulated countries, thus increasing competitiveness. And third, the question of welfare and whether it enhances negative terms-of-trade that cause spill-over effects to countries without emission regulation and vice versa.

The vast majority of research around CBAM is built on the Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, where carbon leakage and distributive allocation between sectors can adequately be assessed. The initial assessment of the EU CBAM for this deliverable follows the early work of Perdana and Vielle (2022) using GEMINI-E3, where the impacts of a climate policies scenario incorporating an EU CBAM are evaluated in the context of the EU's latest climate target (Fit for 55), and measured relative to a reference scenario based on the current policies in each region. The scenario design follows the CD-Links policies database, documented in McCollum et al. (2018) and Roelfsema et al. (2020), along with the International Energy Agency (2020b) to ensure a more updated complementary climate development policy until the year 2030. The assumptions on demography, GDP, energy prices and technology costs follow our previous work on the H2020 PARIS REINFORCE project, detailed in Giarola et al. (2021) and Sognaes et al. (2021).

For robustness, simulations are conducted until the year 2040 to fit the undefined climate policies post-2030, and the feasibility of policy implementation due to technological and sectoral granularity in the model. The EU climate target in 2030 follows the Climate and Energy Framework of a -43% emissions decrease with respect to 2005 for ETS and -30% for non-ETS emissions. These two carbon prices are then assumed to grow in line with per capita GDP rates until 2040. In the EU ETS market, we assume that all the permit allowances are auctioned, and there are no more free allowances. A further scenario design integrates the “Fit for 55” package and incorporates carbon-neutral targets in 2050-2060 by adjusting the abatement target in precedent years.

4.3.2 EU Fit for 55: impacts on leakage, carbon price and energy-intensive goods

This EU new stringent policy results in a higher EU ETS price, growing from approximately 80 € (or 77 US\$) per ton of CO₂ in 2040 (European Commission, 2021c) to 132 US\$ in 2040 (Table 20). The CO₂ price applied in the EU ESR sectors reach 3,312 US\$ in 2040, showing the stringency of the emissions reduction in these sectors, especially relating to the transportation and non-CO₂ GHG emissions. The Fit for 55 packages negatively impacts European GDP, which is estimated to fall by 3.6% by 2040 (Table 21). The impacts on other countries in terms of GDP changes are rather limited. The European EII production falls by 13.8% by 2040. Other regions experience a production increase in EII goods, especially those that have a strong specialisation in these products, such as Russia and the Middle East. Production in India and China remain unchanged, with only a slight tendency to decrease by around -0.2% and -0.1%, respectively.

Table 20: EU Carbon Prices US\$2014

	2025	2030	2040
EU ETS Price	48	75	132
EU ESR (Non ETS) Price	146	764	3,312

Source: GEMINI-E3 model

Compared to the impact assessment done by the European Commission (European Commission, 2021b) using the JRC GEM-E3 model, this prediction is closest to the scenario “MIX with full auctioning for ETS” with 4% output losses and 9.9% EII imports increase by 2030. With our GEMINI-E3 model, output decreases by 5.5% and imports increases by 13.9% by 2030. For the same year, Mörsdorf (2021) predicts that output will be reduced by 5.8% in the metal industry, 3.3% in the minerals sector and by 2.6% in the chemical sector. Comparable to GEMINI-E3, this study uses a multi-sectoral, multi-regional CGE model of the GTAP-E model as documented in McDougall and Golub (2007).

Our results show that the leakage experienced by the EU is significant and equal to 17% for CO₂ and 12.1% for all GHG emissions. This rate is statistically comparable with Branger and Quirion (2014) of 14% (5% to 25% leakage range) and a recent study by Mörsdorf (2021) of 22.2%, yet higher compared to an earlier study by Burniaux *et al.* (2013) of 8%. This relatively lower leakage rate is due to the assumption that the EU only cut their emissions by 30% in 2030 relative to 2005 levels.

Table 21: Results from “EU Fit for 55” (changes w.r.t current policies scenario) - Year 2040

	Welfare change in % of household consumption	GDP change in %	EII production change in %	CO ₂ emissions* change in Mt CO ₂	GHG emissions† change in Mt CO ₂ -eq
EUR	-4.5%	-3.6%	-13.8%	-1,564	-1,849
USA	-0.4%	0.1%	2.5%	62	56

CHI	-0.8%	-0.1%	-0.1%	-21	-24
BRA	-0.9%	0.0%	1.7%	3	-2
RUS	-2.4%	0.7%	15.6%	75	64
MID	-1.6%	0.5%	6.4%	68	67
ROW	-1.5%	0.1%	4.0%	40	34
IND	-0.5%	-0.1%	-0.2%	-45	-48
CSA	-0.8%	0.0%	2.5%	24	29
ASI	-0.6%	0.0%	0.2%	18	20
AFR	-1.3%	0.0%	1.5%	43	29
World	-1.4%	-0.6%	-0.4%	-1,298	-1,625

Source: GEMINI-E3 model

For India and China, a fall in international fossil fuel prices would reduce CO₂ emissions even further. As EU consumption of coal is relatively modest, the impact is stronger for gas and oil energy markets. This fall in international gas prices triggers substitution from domestic coal to gas in electricity generation in China and India, leading to a decline in their emissions. In regards to welfare change, the EU would be detrimentally impacted due to the imposed GHG taxation. Energy-exporting countries such as Russia, the Middle East, Africa and the Rest of the World (ROW) would experience revenue loss from energy exports.

4.3.3 Implementing EU CBAM under Fit for 55: implications on carbon leakage, energy-intensive goods and welfare

Following the existing EU regulation (European Commission, 2021c), CBAM is applied to EIs and electricity generation, based on the CO₂ content that includes only direct emissions (scope 1). Here we follow the European Commission for the use of scope 1 as the basis for CBAM for its simplicity to be applied at an initial stage. Calculating emissions by taking into account direct emissions and electricity used (scope 2) or direct and indirect emissions (scope 3), are more complicated and less likely to be applied at the initial stages of CBAM implementation.

Introducing CBAM would decrease CO₂ leakage by approximately one-third, from 17% to 12.6%. And as shown in Table 22, the decrease in European EI production is only reduced by 15% (from -13.8% to -11.6%). The reduction in leakage after the introduction of CBAM is within the range stated by Mörsdorf (2021) of 22.2% to 14.8%. The carbon tariffs shift the economic burden on non-European countries, and especially on the developing world. The regions of Africa, India, Russia and ROW are negatively impacted by the implementation of CBAM. Declines in the production of energy-intensive goods lead to a welfare loss. It is interesting to note that the US and China are slightly affected by the introduction of CBAM. The European welfare gain from CBAM is estimated at 47 billion US\$. The production loss of EI in 2030 reduced slightly from 5.5% to 4.7%.

Table 22: Results from EU Fit for 55 with CBAM - scope 1 (changes w.r.t current policies scenario) - Year 2040

	Welfare change in % of household consumption	GDP change in %	EI production change in %	CO ₂ emissions* change in Mt CO ₂	GHG emissions† change in Mt CO ₂ -eq
EUR	-4.2%	-3.5%	-11.6%	-1,564	-1,849
USA	-0.3%	0.1%	2.4%	64	58
CHI	-0.8%	-0.1%	-0.2%	-27	-30
BRA	-0.9%	0.0%	1.7%	3	-2
RUS	-2.7%	0.6%	14.6%	67	55

MID	-1.8%	0.5%	5.9%	62	60
ROW	-1.7%	0.1%	4.1%	36	30
IND	-0.9%	-0.2%	-1.1%	-87	-93
CSA	-0.8%	0.0%	2.5%	24	29
ASI	-0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	19	22
AFR	-1.6%	-0.1%	1.0%	36	20
World	-1.5%	-0.6%	-0.4%	-1,366	-1,701

Source: GEMINI-E3 model

Table 23: Results from EU Fit for 55 with CBAM - scope 2 (changes w.r.t current policies scenario) - Year 2040

	Welfare change in % of household consumption	GDP change in %	EII production change in %	CO ₂ emissions* change in Mt CO ₂	GHG emissions† change in Mt CO ₂ -eq
EUR	-4.0%	-3.5%	-9.7%	-1,563	-1,849
USA	-0.3%	0.1%	2.3%	66	59
CHI	-0.9%	-0.1%	-0.3%	-37	-41
BRA	-0.9%	0.1%	1.8%	3	-2
RUS	-3.1%	0.4%	11.9%	50	36
MID	-2.0%	0.5%	5.9%	62	60
ROW	-1.9%	0.1%	3.9%	34	27
IND	-1.0%	-0.3%	-1.4%	-100	-108
CSA	-0.9%	0.0%	2.5%	24	29
ASI	-0.7%	0.0%	-0.1%	18	21
AFR	-1.7%	-0.2%	0.5%	29	12
World	-1.5%	-0.6%	-0.4%	-1,413	-1,756

Source: GEMINI-E3 model

Table 23 shows the scenario when CBAM is implemented by taking into account direct and indirect emissions from electricity generation (scope 2). Results are consistent with that performed using the JRC GEM-E3 model titled "MIX-full auctioning option 3" (European Commission, 2021b).

Table 24 shows the scenario outcomes of CBAM implementation with direct emissions and any indirect production-related emissions including all the intermediate CO₂ consumption by sector (scope 3).

Table 24: Results from EU Fit for 55 with CBAM - scope 3 (changes w.r.t current policies scenario) - Year 2040

	Welfare change in % of household consumption	GDP change in %	EII production change in %	CO ₂ emissions* change in Mt CO ₂	GHG emissions† change in Mt CO ₂ -eq
EUR	-3.9%	-3.4%	-8.7%	-1,563	-1,849
USA	-0.3%	0.1%	2.2%	65	58
CHI	-1.0%	-0.2%	-0.5%	-50	-56
BRA	-1.0%	0.0%	1.7%	3	-2
RUS	-3.0%	0.5%	13.5%	60	47
MID	-2.0%	0.5%	5.8%	61	59
ROW	-2.0%	0.1%	3.9%	33	26

IND	-1.1%	-0.3%	-1.6%	-107	-115
CSA	-0.9%	0.0%	2.4%	24	29
ASI	-0.7%	0.0%	-0.4%	12	14
AFR	-1.7%	-0.2%	0.4%	28	11
World	-1.5%	-0.6%	-0.4%	-1,435	-1,779

Source: GEMINI-E3 model

4.3.4 EU CBAM complementary designs: revenue recycle

The introduction of the EU CBAM will come with a high cost, especially for countries with a substantial share of export to the EU. Implementation of EU CBAM will reduce their export, and without any effective mitigation and environmental sustainability objectives in their national development strategies, the economic impacts may be substantial (Mealy and Teytelboym, 2020; Ameli et al., 2021). Many of the EU's trading partners exporting carbon-intensive goods, especially developing countries, have raised concerns that the EU CBAM would substantially curtail their exports and competitiveness. Eicke et al. (2021) assess that relative risks from the EU CBAM vary among exporting countries, and suggest that future EU CBAM design should be equipped with complementary policies based on countries' exposure to exporting to the EU. Here, the focus lies on the Least Developed Economies (LDCs). Despite holding a smaller share of the EU's imports of energy, in theory, EU CBAM could negatively impact these poorer countries and reduce opportunities for export-led development due to high exposure of their exports to the EU.

Further analysis in designing CBAM³¹, focuses on complementary measures that can alleviate or limit the impact on LDCs. Here the definitions of LDCs are recognised under the UNDP Human Development Index (HDI), as being below 0.8 in 2020 (Majerova, 2012). This classification includes India and countries in our aggregated regions of Africa, the rest of Asia, and Central and South America. Among many scenarios developed as CBAM complementary measures, three scenarios are selected for this deliverable which redistribute a part of revenue gained from CBAM to LDCs. The first scenario involves no target, while the other two are linked to such development programs improving the ability of countries to adapt, such as shifting trade flows and decarbonising or verifying carbon. Partly of CBAM revenue will be redistributed to LDCs as lump-sum transfers based on their export contributions. This scheme is likely more realistic, as it aligns with the proposal of "*most revenues generated by CBAM will go towards the EU budget*" (European Commission, 2021g). Results are being compared to CBAM implementation without the complementary measure on four components i.e: leakages, welfare changes for both EU and LDC as well as changes in EU EII production. Figure 46 summarises the impacts of these distributive measures by 2040.

³¹ This section is based on Perdana and Vielle (2022).

Figure 46: Impacts of different redistributive measures on key figures by 2040 (changes w.r.t to EU fit 55 with CBAM)

Source: GEMINI-E3 model

4.3.4.1 Revenue Transfer to LDCs – No Target

The first complementary scenario assumes all the revenue collected from the CBAM (including that perceived from non-LDCs) is redistributed to our four developing regions on their export contribution with no specific target. The amount of transfer is around 13 billion US\$, and results in slightly lower leakage compared to implementing CBAM without this complementary revenue return scenario. The effects are moderate, and the welfare of LDCs is positively improved under certain welfare costs for the EU. European EII production increased by 10 billion US\$.

4.3.4.2 Revenue Transfer to LDCs - Promoting Renewable Electricity Target

Following the objectives of global adaptation funds, the next scenario uses CBAM funds to promote climate-friendly transformations in developing countries (Brandt, 2021). The revenue will be used to subsidise electricity renewables (*i.e.* solar and wind) in LDCs. Impacts on welfare and EII production are almost the same magnitude as in what you get is what you contribute, but this scenario results in a very positive effect on leakage reduction. The global emissions are reduced by 79 MtCO₂, with the leakage rate reduced by 7.6%. The increase in renewable electricity reduces CO₂ emissions from coal and gas power plants. The electricity from solar and photovoltaic increases by 168 TWh by 2040, and from wind by 107 TWh. Significant increases in renewable electricity happen mostly in India (+121 TWh) and Africa (+107 TWh).

4.3.4.3 Revenue Transfer to LDCs - Promoting Efficiency Measures in Residential Energy Consumption

The last scenario assumes that the revenue will be assigned to LDCs' households to reduce fuel poverty. Under this scheme, households could buy efficient appliances and reduce their electricity bills. To simulate this, we use technological cost assumptions of the TIAM Model (Loulou and Labriet, 2008) for electric appliances (such as refrigerators, dishwashers, washing machines, etc.), their purchasing costs and efficiency levels. The efficiency gain

is calculated, followed by an investment cost estimation to transition the standard appliance to the most efficient one. Using Africa as a reference (as the costs are quite close among LDCs), the cost of a 1% efficiency improvement ranges from 1\$ to 4\$ per appliance.

As an illustrative example, we use a conservative value of 1% efficiency improvement costs of 3 US\$ and consider the aid will be used to replace standard refrigerators with efficient ones. Revenue returned from EU CBAM is used to cover purchasing cost differences of 100 US\$ per 300-litre refrigerator. The new refrigerator decreases electricity consumption by one-third. Assuming that the annual average electricity consumption of a refrigerator is equal to 400 KWh (Cardoso et al., 2010; Gürel et al., 2020), 100 US\$ aid per refrigerator allows for reducing electricity consumption annually by 133 KWh. The number of households that can benefit from this aid and the electricity saving is calculated based on the CBAM revenue collected. Table 25 provides the estimation by 2040.

Table 25: Gains in Household Electricity Consumption from EU Financial Aid - Year 2040

	India	Central & South America	Rest of Asia	Africa
Financial aid by region in millions US\$ [†]	4,100	700	2,100	3,800
Number of refrigerators replaced in millions	41	7	21	38
Electricity consumption saving in TWh	11	2	6	10
Electricity consumption by household in TWh [†]	1,009	475	1,472	803
Decrease of electricity consumption in %	-1.1%	-0.4%	-0.4%	-1.3%

[†] Estimated by GEMINI-E3 model; Source: GEMINI-E3

By 2040, this scenario would benefit up to 107 million homes and save 26 TWh of electricity (around -0.8% of electricity consumed by households). This has strong implications for the welfare of LDCs by generating an increase of 36 billion US\$, and by reducing their CO₂ emissions by 90 million tonnes. The cumulative impacts of replacing equipment between 2020 to 2040 result in improving final energy efficiency. The leakage rate is reduced to 4.9% and electricity used in LDCs decreases by 209 TWh in 2040.

Following these results, complementary measures should be seen as an integrated part of EU CBAM implementation. While revenue return with no specific target induces more reduction in leakage, specialising those complementary policies to promote clean energy or improve energy efficiency substantially reduces leakage with relatively the same costs for the EU. Promoting efficiency measures in residential energy consumption significantly improves LDCs' welfare with an equal rate of leakage reduction as the complimentary scenario promoting renewable electricity.

5 Summary and conclusion

In the context of up-scaling the European Union's ambition to fight climate change by updating its GHG emissions targets for 2030, from -40% to -55% and by targeting net zero emissions by 2050, this deliverable presents a set of multi-model exercises and scenarios of deep decarbonisation in EU to be in line with the Paris Agreement.

First, we focus on global scenarios that aim at limiting temperature increase to 1.5, 1.75 or 2°C. The CO₂ emissions pathways for the EU, obtained by a set of six global IAMs, show that only one model achieves NZE in 2050 to comply with the stringent temperature rise scenario (1.5°C). Thus, EU commitments, and especially the 2050 NZE target, on climate are beyond the optimal mitigation burden found by the models. It shows that EU climate ambition takes a part of its historical responsibility (Rocha et al., 2015; Leimbach and Giannousakis, 2019), engages in a fairer climate transition (Raupach et al., 2014; Robiou du Pont et al., 2017) and assumes a leading role (Oberthür and Dupont, 2021; Schreyer et al., 2018).

We thereafter develop a set of scenarios specifically for the EU, that have been implemented in eight different models: three global models (the partial equilibrium model: GCAM and two general equilibrium models: GEMINI-E3 and ICES), two system-wide European models (the energy system model: EU-TIMES and NEMESIS a macro-econometric model) and two sector-specific models (FORECAST for the industry and the buildings sectors and ALADIN for the transport). The set of scenarios was defined as follows:

- (i) the *WWH21*, a post-COVID 19 update of the "Where are We Headed" scenario (Sognnaes et al., 2021) that considers EU climate policy before the European Green Deal (Cassetti et al., under review);
- (ii) two net zero emission scenarios for the EU, both passing by -55% of GHG emissions in 2050 compared to 1990; the first is a cost-optimal scenario ("*NZE Benchmark*") whereas the second imposes emissions caps for the EU-ETS and the ESR sectors ("*NZE EU Policy Standard*").

The analysis of the GHG emissions pathways in both models dealing with non-CO₂ emissions (GCAM and GEMINI-E3) shows an abatement between 45% and 75% (compared to 1990) for CH₄ and 40% and 60% in N₂O whereas for the LULUCF emissions GCAM projects a sink of -155 MtCO₂ at maximum. These projections are relatively in line with the ones found in the literature (see Section 3.1 in deliverable D.5.3) except for LULUCF for which they are more pessimistic, as the deployment of biomass energy in GCAM is used as a main mitigation option in NZE scenarios.

The models in the least-cost NZE scenario show a burden sharing relatively close to the European Commission proposal for 2030 in its Fit for 55 packages, *i.e.*, -61% for the EU-ETS (in comparison with 2005) and -40% for the ESR sector. In 2050, the GHG emissions reduction in the ESR sector are between 70% and 80% with respect to 2005, depending on the extent of the use of negative emissions technologies in the EU-ETS sector. Furthermore, all models agree that the decarbonisation of the European economy takes place rapidly in the energy supply sector that becomes carbon-free between 2035 and 2045. In the other sectors, the decarbonisation rates are more heterogeneous, the CO₂ emissions in the transport sector reduce generally slower than in other sectors, and are offset by NETs in the power generation sector.

All models, except ICES for which the option is not available, rely on CCS or/and BECCS to reach NZE emissions in 2050; (BE)CCS is massively deployed in the power generation but at a different scale according to models and more marginally in the industry sector. Total annual CO₂ stored in 2050 reaches up to 1.8 Gt/y in GCAM, 1 Gt/y in GEMINI-E3 and between 450 and 350 Mt in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS. As regularly pointed out in the literature and highlighted in D6.5, such large deployment of CCS questions the realism of IAMs' deep decarbonisation pathways (Anderson and Peters, 2018). However, despite important technical and societal uncertainties (Geden et al., 2018), the low range of our models' projections complies with the current assessment of the European storage capacity

(Fuss et al., 2018).

In addition to NETs, some models mobilise important energy savings to alleviate the CO₂ mitigation burden, which is particularly the case for GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS that (almost) achieve the EU energy efficiency target of about 39% in 2030. In other models, the energy efficiency is more limited. In the stringent scenarios, some models even project a rebound of primary energy consumption in the last decade (like in EU-TIMES and NEMESIS), as the result of a high-level penetration of carbon-free electricity. In comparison with energy savings, fuel shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources is a common result between models.

Fossil fuels' share in the European primary energy consumption declines from three quarters in 2020 to 13-28% in 2050 (excluding GEMINI-E3). Consequently, the RES share is increasing rapidly in all models, from around one-fifth in 2020 to around two-thirds in 2050, Nuclear only moderately energy grows. Despite that, our modelling exercise did not consider the REPowerEU plan (European Commission, 2022a) framed as a consequence of the Russian-Ukrainian military conflict, the European climate policy can reduce gas demand by 90bm³/y. in 2025 and 135 in 2030 (in comparison with 2019, average values), representing respectively more than half and almost 80% of 2019 natural gas imports from Russia.

Among RES, biomass energy plays a key role in the decarbonisation of the European energy system. NEMESIS and EU-TIMES bioenergy requirements, between 270 and 310 Mtoe/y at the middle of the century, are below the upper bound of biomass potential for EU (Ruiz *et al.*, 2019), except from GCAM, overshooting it with 800 Mtoe/y. Solar and wind are also massively deployed in all NZE scenarios. Our projections remain well-below respective potentials (Ruiz *et al.*, 2019), but reaching such level of deployment in the EU should overcome existing current barriers (Doukas *et al.*, 2022) to.

Electrification appears in all models as an essential lever to decarbonise the final uses of energy, with electricity reaching more than 50% of secondary energy in almost all models, and electricity production more than doubling between 2020 and 2050. In these NZE scenarios, the European power generation becomes carbon neutral between 2035 and 2045 (except in ICES) with coal without CCS disappearing up to 2030 as in EU-TIMES. The share of renewable energy sources in the European power generation grows from around 33% in 2020, 52% in 2030 and 80% in 2050 (average values), with a share of variable renewable energies of 70-80% in EU-TIMES and around 50% in GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS. This share gets close to (and even reaches) a level for which their management may push significantly their cost (Heptonstall and Gross, 2020; Reichenberg *et al.*, 2018).

Besides electricity, hydrogen is also viewed as a growing alternative energy vector in the coming decades and particularly in some hard-to-decarbonise sectors. From the supply side, our models expect that the deployment of H₂ production will be negligible in 2030, which suggests that, without specific market-pull measures, deployment of hydrogen production will not happen in 2030 and the 40 GW electrolysers installed in the EU of the Hydrogen Strategy will be out of reach (European Commission, 2020b). A complete (or almost) transition to green hydrogen is achieved in 2050 with produced quantities increasing sharply in scenarios with deeper CO₂ emissions mitigation targets, the total installed capacity reaching up to 650 GW/y. On the demand side, no hydrogen use is expected in the building sector; in the transport sector ALADIN assumes a minor role, while EU-TIMES a higher penetration and all models agree on its usefulness to decarbonise the European industry but to a different extent.

A deeper analysis of the energy demand by the final sectors has shown that our models diverge in their choice to decarbonise the industry sector. Some, like GEMINI-E3, NEMESIS and FORECAST, envisage significant energy efficiency gains coupled with a strong electrification of the sector, especially for the two later ones. This electrification also operates in GCAM and EU-TIMES but mostly in the last decade for the latter, replacing the previous substitution towards biomass energy. In the buildings sector, all models agree on a large penetration of

electricity to reduce emissions; only FORECAST diverges a bit because heat energy takes a large part of the energy mix through district heating and heat pumps. Finally, the electrification of transport is a common result of the models, but some complement it by a reduction of energy demand as in ALADIN, NEMESIS, GEMINI-E3 and ICES and/or by the introduction of other fuels: e-fuels in ALADIN and hydrogen in EU-TIMES, both to decarbonise other road freight and aviation.

In terms of socio-economic impacts, the NZE targets can be achieved without important GDP loss in the EU if enough mitigation options avoid relying on a demand tightening as in the ICES model. GEMINI-E3, with highly restrictive assumptions about capital market flexibility (Pollit and Mercure, 2018), shows an EU GDP loss in EU of 1.5% between 2020 and 2050, compared to the *WWH21* scenario. Contrary NEMESIS, with less restrictive assumptions on the capital market but assuming a unilateral climate action of the EU, presents a lower impact, with -0.4% of GDP. On employment, NEMESIS projects a slightly decline mainly in the services sector, penalised by the lower private consumption whereas the industry and even the heavy industry benefits from strong investment needs to realise the energy transition. GEMINI-E3 expects almost null employment impact and shows some important employment loss in the heavy industry.

We follow the study by further delving in some key points of the EU climate policy, with:

- an analysis of the update of EU climate policy, the “Fit for 55” proposal, with a scenario called *WWH21+* run by six different models.
- a detailed analysis of the Member States’ long-term strategies (LTS) for the agriculture, forestry and land use (AFOLU) sector, a blind spot of our multi-model analysis.
- a modelling assessment of different implementations of EU carbon border adjustment mechanisms, a new climate policy instrument that could be implemented in the EU in the coming decade.

On the *WWH21+* scenario, the results are close to the NZE scenarios for 2030, with no major difference. Nevertheless, the use of the past emissions intensity improvements to project post-2030 mitigation effort leads to between 600 and 700 MtCO₂ in 2050, which will not allow reaching NZE in 2050, if we assume that LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions will optimistically give a sink of about 200 Mt. Furthermore, on the six models used, five reach the -55% target for 2030, but only three models show a RES share compatible with the 40% EU objective (and out-of-reach of the 45% proposed in the RePowerEU plan) and no model matches the -39% energy efficiency target, even if two are relatively close.

Our assessment of the MS LTS for the AFOLU sector shows that despite that Member States have evaluated the role of AFOLU to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, most of their LTS present general intentions, measures and objectives, and 40% of them lack quantitative data on future LULUCF emission and removals. The vast majority of the countries consider forest management essential to reach their climate target, while in the mitigation category ‘agriculture’ and ‘demand side’, the most important policies and measures are agroforestry and promoting healthy diets, respectively. However, the mitigation potential of the policy and measure can vary substantially across countries depending on the place and time of their implementation: for example, agroforestry is very effective, or applicable, mainly in Mediterranean countries and peatland restoration in Northern countries. Furthermore, we found that more effective policies and measures could be planned and implemented to enhance the AFOLU contribution to reach mid-century climate neutrality.

Finally, the implementation of a CBAM in the EU in the GEMINI-E3 model, in accordance with the scope of the European Commission proposal on direct emissions of the energy-intensive industry --EEI (European Commission, 2021c), decreases the CO₂ leakage by approximately one-third and slightly reduces the production loss of European EII production. The enlargement of the scope of the CBAM to direct and indirect emissions reinforce

previous results. The carbon tariffs shift the economic burden on non-European countries, and especially on the developing world. To overcome this side-effect, different recycling options of the CBAM revenues for the least developed countries (LDC) have been assessed with the GEMINI-E3 model and it shows that the use of these revenues to support energy transition substantially reduces carbon leakage and can improve welfare in LDC (Perdana and Vielle, 2022).

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6 Annex I – PAC core scenarios

6.1 EU+ GDP projections update

The economic dimension and particularly the post-COVID-19 pandemic economic situation in EU+³² is quantified by the NEMESIS model. The economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 is based on the DG ECFIN economic forecast (European Commission, 2021i) allowing for reproduction in NEMESIS, GDP through its counterparts: households' final consumption, public consumption, gross fixed capital formation, exports and imports for each Member State. Furthermore, the impacts are differentiated by economic sector by using quarterly data available in Eurostat for every Member State up to the third quarter of 2020 (Eurostat, 2021). The calibration procedure for 2020 consists of introducing gap variables in behavioural equations in the model: (i) households' consumption by purpose to mimic the impacts of non-pharmaceutical interventions imposed on households, (ii) in employment and income to consider job retention schemes implemented by public authorities and (iii) in intra- and extra-EU+ demand to reproduce the reduction in trades of goods and services. After 2020, according to scenarios, these gap variables are either completely or partially phased out and with different temporality.

Table 26: GDP in the pre- and post-COVID-19 context

		EU+ GDP (bn€ ₂₀₁₀ /y.)				Average EU+ GDP growth rate (%/y.)			
		2020	2025	2030	2050	2021-2025	2026-2030	2021-2030	2031-2050
Pre-COVID-19	Where are we headed (WWH)	14 806.9	15 771.5	16 817.6	22 287.8	1.3%	1.3%	1.3%	1.4%
	Full economy recovery (FR)	13 702.2	15 725.3	16 676.6	22 277.8	2.8%	1.2%	2.0%	1.4%
Post-COVID-19	Limited economic recovery (LR)	13 702.2	15 321.7	16 165.7	21 550.4	2.3%	1.1%	1.7%	1.4%
		<i>-7.5%</i>	<i>-2.9%</i>	<i>-3.9%</i>	<i>-3.3%</i>				

Source: NEMESIS model, in italic percentage deviation with respect to the pre-COVID-19 WWH scenario

NEMESIS runs three different scenarios, a pre-COVID-19 scenario, with an EU average annual GDP growth of 1.3% between 2021 and 2030 and two post-COVID-19 scenarios, one with a full recovery in 2025 and a second one with limited economic recovery, considering an EU+ GDP loss of 3.9% compared with the pre-COVID-19 situation (Table 26). For the "Full economic recovery" scenario, the European economy strongly upturns in 2021 and 2022 allowing the EU+ economies to fill the GDP gap with a pre-COVID-19 economic outlook by the year 2025. The methodology used assumes that the behavioural changes observed in production and production patterns in 2020 are only temporary and vanish totally in 2025. Consequently, after 2025, the economic growth in the EU+ countries comes back close to the potential GDP growth rate assumed before the COVID-19 crisis, with a yearly growth rate of EU+ GDP of 1.2%. In the "Limited economic recovery" case, the EU+ economy upturns more slowly and weakly between 2021 to 2023, the EU+ GDP is 2.9% lower in 2025 in comparison with the pre-COVID-19 scenario and 3.9% lower in 2030.

³² EU+ covers EU27+UK

6.2 Detailed emissions caps for EU27 in the WWH21 scenario

Table 27: Detailed emissions caps for EU27 in the WWH21 scenario

	1990	2005	2019	2030
EU-ETS w intra-EEA aviation*		2.07	1.44	1.18
EU-ETS w intra-EEA aviation* (EU27+NO+IS+LI)		2.09	1.47	1.19
ESR		2.57	2.30	1.76
LULUCF	-0.21	-0.31	-0.25	-0.23
Non-CO ₂ emissions (wo LULUCF & w In't aviation)	0.98	0.79	0.69	0.58
Total wo LULUCF & w intra-EEA aviation*	4.89	4.58	3.66	2.94
Total w LULUCF & w. intra-EEA aviation*	4.68	4.27	3.41	2.71

Source: historical values (EEA, 2021a and 2021b); LULUCF emissions authors' calculation based on current LULUCF regulation (European Commission, 2018b) and non-CO₂ emissions authors' calculation based on "Mix-50" from European Commission (2020).

*: GHG emissions from intra-EEA aviation are assumed to represent 40% of total GHG emissions from international aviation in 1990, 2005: the average value from 2015 to 2019 based on EEA (2021a; 2021b).

NB: Original data have been corrected from the UK when relevant.

6.3 United-Kingdom specific emissions caps for the PAC core scenarios

Table 28: Synthesis of main GHG emissions reduction targets in UK in the PAC core scenarios

	WWH21			NZE		
	2030	2050	2025	2030	2035	2050
GHG emissions reduction(w.r.t 1990)	-58% (wo LULUCF & in't transports)		-55% (w LULUCF & wo in't transports)	-68% (w LULUCF & wo in't transports)	-78% (w LULUCF & w in't transports)	NZE
EU-ETS GHG emissions	2021-2025: 736 MtCO ₂ eq. 2026-2030: 630 MtCO ₂ eq.	carbon price equivalent				
ESR GHG emissions reduction	-37% (w.r.t. 2005)					

Source: WWH21 UK-ETS cap: ICAP (2021) and NZE: CCC (2020)

Table 29: Detailed emissions caps for UK in PAC core scenarios

MtCO ₂ eq./y	1990	2005	2019	WWH21		Net Zero Emissions				
				2030	2050	2025	2030	2035	2050	
UK-ETS w. Intra-EEA aviation		274.8	129.6	117.5						
ESR		446.5	356.5	215.6						
LULUCF*	18.0	8.3	5.9	6.6			10.4	6.6	1.0	-18.7
Non-CO ₂ emissions (wo. LULUCF & w. In't bunkers)*	193.4	119.1	83.2	65.7	n/a		66.2	48.6	41.0	27.1
Total wo. LULUCF & w aviation*	806.8	686.2	505.3	333.1						
Total w. LULUCF & wo. in't bunkers*	809.4	694.5	455.1			364.2	259.0			
Total w. LULUCF & w. in't bunkers*	833.9	738.6	502.3					183.5		0.0

Source: historical values (EEA, 2021a); LULUCF and non-CO₂ emissions authors' calculation based on CCC (2020) scenario "Balanced Net Zero Pathway".

*: From 2025, numbers have been adjusted to be compatible with the UK GHG Inventory. In the 6th Carbon Budget report, GHG

emissions are based on AR5 GWPs with feedback and differ from GHG UK inventory (AR4 without feedback).

6.4 Specific assumptions for the FORECAST model

The FORECAST model is a sector-specific model for the European industry and buildings sectors and therefore cannot comply with the general PAC scenario protocol, Thus, we detail below the specific assumptions used in the model firstly for the industry and secondly for the buildings.

6.4.1 FORECAST Industry: Scenario definition and specific assumptions

In the *WWH21* scenario, existing technologies are used and complete diffusion of today's best available technologies is assumed. The *WWH21* scenario aims to capture today's level of policy implementation at the EU level, but does not yet include instruments that were proposed or are being discussed within e.g. the 'Fit for 55' package. Fuel switch is mostly driven by prices and takes place towards natural gas and biomass. Fast development of the circular economy is assumed which leads to higher shares of recycling. In addition, initial uses of hydrogen are introduced in the iron and steel industry and as feedstock for ammonia production, which take into account the considerations of the EU hydrogen strategy (European Commission, 2020b) in combination with the PARIS REINFORCE scenario framework.

The Net Zero Mix focus electrification ("*NZE EU Policy Standard*") scenario describes a pathway that is in line with CO₂ neutrality by 2050 and aims to achieve the long-term goal of at least 95% GHG reduction by 2050 compared to 1990 for the industry sector. The "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" scenario capitalises on a mix of innovative technologies with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) above 4. This implies that technical challenges have been overcome and technology readiness has been demonstrated in pilot plants. Major challenges for the market introduction are upscaling and economics. The scenario draws on a relatively balanced mix of mitigation strategies including energy and material efficiency, circularity, as well as carbon capture and storage (CCS). The "*NZE EU Policy Standard*" with a focus on hydrogen, called the "*NZE EU PS – H₂*" scenario, is similar to the previous scenario, but with a stronger focus on hydrogen as a major decarbonisation option for feedstocks and process heating.

For the industrial sector, the main assumptions by scenario are summarised in, which is categorised by mitigation option.

Table 30: Summary of the specific assumptions for FORECAST (Industry) model for the PAC core scenarios

	WWH21	NZE EU Policy Standard	NZE EU PS H ₂
Economic growth	Continued long-term growth of industry GVA ~0.8%, recovery of Covid-crisis with higher growth before 2030		
Energy Efficiency	Fast deployment of Best-Available-Techniques (BAT) efficiency	Fast deployment of BAT efficiency + innovations >= TRL 4	
Fuel switch	Fuel switch driven by prices	Financial support for RES and electricity	Financial support for RES and Hydrogen
CCU/S	No CCU/S	Optional - for High-Value Chemicals (HVC) and Cement	
Downstream	More recycling: steel, glass, paper, aluminium	More recycling and strong increases in material efficiency	
CO₂ Price	Low EU ETS prices in line with Ref2020 50€/tCO ₂ -eq in 2030 200€/tCO ₂ -eq in 2050	High CO ₂ price for the EU ETS 110€/tCO ₂ -eq in 2030 490€/tCO ₂ -eq in 2050	

6.4.2 FORECAST Buildings: Scenario definition and specific assumptions

Two scenarios have been assessed with the FORECAST – Buildings model:

- *WWH21* scenario: the policies that are currently applied until 2030 stay as is for a longer term (i.e. until 2050)
- “*NZE EU Policy Standard*” (NZE EU Policy) scenario: Member States apply policies in line with the “Fit-for-55” package of the European Commission.

The main assumptions to describe the scenarios for the buildings sector are summarized in detail in Table 31. This includes the diffusion of building efficiency standards, compliance rates, renovation rates and depths, the applied ESR sector CO₂ price, regulations and technology preference. In the “*NZE EU Policy scenario*”, the preference for renewable heating technologies reflects the requirements of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) for a certain share of renewables in buildings, and it is modelled through a high willingness to pay for renewable heating systems. Fossil heating technologies are replaced earlier than the end of their lifetime, in the light of the zero-emissions building standard as well as the national replacement subsidies.

In this analysis, we assume limited capacity for biomass supply for buildings and therefore a higher preference for heat pumps and district heating in comparison to biomass. District heating is assumed to be used to its full expansion potential and will be produced via renewable resources such as large-scale heat pumps (Paardekooper et al., 2018). Decentral heat pumps are attractive where district heating networks are not projected to expand.

Table 31: Summary of the specific assumptions for FORECAST (Buildings) model for the PAC core scenarios

	WWH21	NZE EU Policy Standard
Building standards	Building standards improve at the current pace, with moderate compliance rates.	Building standards improve ambitiously in accordance with the revised EPBD. High compliance rates.
Renovation/Refurbishment	Refurbishment rates and depths stay at current level.	New building standards diffuse into renovations from 2030 onwards. Refurbishment rates reach at least twice of current levels by 2030.
Non-ETS CO₂ Price	Scheduled prices by 2030 are continued in the long-term. Member states who did not declare any prices in the short-term lower the EU28 price average to 40€/t in 2030 and to 60€/t in 2050.	All member states apply carbon tax in buildings. Prices reach 130€/t in 2030 and 200€/t in 2050.
Technology preference	Willingness to pay for RE technologies stay at current levels as current incentives.	Willingness to pay for RE technologies are high.
Regulation	Ban of coal heating systems.	Ban of coal and oil heating systems after 2025. Ban of new natural gas boiler implementations after 2030.
Lifetime of heating systems	Technologies are used until end of their lifetimes.	Fossil heating systems have shorter lifetime to be replaced faster.

7 Annex II – Fuel mix of primary energy consumption by Member State in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 47: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Denmark, Finland and Sweden in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 48: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 49: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Austria, Germany and the Netherlands in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 50: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Belgium, France and Luxembourg in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 51: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Czechia, Hungary and Lithuania in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 52: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Bulgaria, Poland and Romania in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 53: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Italy, Portugal and Spain in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 54: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Croatia, Greece and Slovenia in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Fuel mix in total primary energy (%)

Figure 55: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in Cyprus, Ireland and Malta in the “NZE Benchmark – Medium” scenario

Figure 56: Fuel mix of primary energy consumption in the United-Kingdom "NZE Benchmark – Medium" scenario

8 Annex III – Swiss and German National Stakeholders Workshops – Poll results

8.1 Swiss National Workshop – 18th May 2021

The poll was realised online with the Slido application. Below are the poll results

1. For the following sectors within Europe, how would you characterise the difficulties associated with decarbonisation: (number of respondents: 33)

- a. Agriculture?
 - i. Low: 0%
 - ii. Medium: 48%
 - iii. High: 52%
- b. Power Generation:
 - i. Low: 48%
 - ii. Medium: 36%
 - iii. High: 15%
- c. Industry
 - i. Low: 9%
 - ii. Medium: 55%
 - iii. High: 36%
- d. Transport
 - i. Low: 27%
 - ii. Medium: 36%
 - iii. High: 36%
- e. Buildings
 - i. Low: 21%
 - ii. Medium: 64%
 - iii. High: 15%

2. How important do you consider the following technologies to be for achieving ambitious GHG reduction targets (net-zero): (number of respondents: 33)

- a. Carbon, Capture and Storage (CCS)?
 - i. Low: 12%
 - ii. Medium: 18%
 - iii. Important: 33%

- iv. Essential: 36%
- b. Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS)?
 - i. Low: 18%
 - ii. Medium: 30%
 - iii. Important: 33%
 - iv. Essential: 18%
- c. Hydrogen (blue/green)?
 - i. Low: 9%
 - ii. Medium: 42%
 - iii. Important: 27%
 - iv. Essential: 21%
- d. Electric Mobility?
 - i. Low: 0%
 - ii. Medium: 9%
 - iii. Important: 21%
 - iv. Essential: 70%
- e. Renewables?
 - i. Low: 0%
 - ii. Medium: 0%
 - iii. Important: 9%
 - iv. Essential: 91%
- f. Direct Air Capture (DAC)?
 - i. Low: 33%
 - ii. Medium: 39%
 - iii. Important: 21%
 - iv. Essential: 6%
- g. Bio-Energy CCS (BECCS)?
 - i. Low: 9%
 - ii. Medium: 33%
 - iii. Important: 18%
 - iv. Essential: 39%
- h. Behavioural Changes?
 - i. Low: 3%

- ii. Medium: 21%
- iii. Important: 21%
- iv. Essential: 55%

3. Which of the following sectors should be included in the EU-ETS? (Choose as many as you wish) (number of respondents: 31)

- a. Industrial emitters which are currently excluded: 84%
- b. Agriculture: 35%
- c. Commercial Buildings: 58%
- d. Residential Buildings: 42%
- e. Road Transport: 61%
- f. Maritime Transport: 77%

4. Do you think that the EU should implement EU wide carbon taxation on the ESR (non-EU-ETS) sectors? (Levy a carbon tax on all GHG emissions based on CO₂eq). (Number of respondents: 33)

- a. Yes: 84%
- b. No: 18%

5. How do you think that revenue from carbon taxation should be used? (Choose up to 3 options) (number of respondents: 32)

- a. Reduce national public debt: 3%
- b. Reduce other taxes on households and/or companies: 41%
- c. Support household investment into green goods: 63%
- d. Support company investment into green goods: 31%
- e. Support workers' retraining in most penalised economic activities: 31%
- f. Support international GHG mitigation action (International Green Fund): 13%
- g. Support R&D in green technologies: 41%
- h. Support public information campaigns on climate change: 6%
- i. Support adaption actions: 22%
- j. Support a fund for future negative emissions: 19%

8.2 German National Workshop – 8th July 2022

The poll was realised online with the Menti application. Below are the poll results

1. Which sector will be the most challenging to decarbonise in Germany. (Number of respondents: 14)

- a. Agriculture: 6
- b. Power Generation: 0

- c. Industry: 5
 - d. Transport: 1
 - e. Buildings: 3
- 2. Please assess the importance of the following mitigation strategies/measures for decarbonizing the industry sectors (ranking: 4: Essential, 3: Important, 2: Moderated; 1: Low; 0: Negligible; number of respondents: 13)**
- a. Energy Efficiency: 2.8
 - b. Material Efficiency: 2.9
 - c. Circular Economy: 2.7
 - d. Fuel Switch: 3.6
 - e. Process Switch: 3.6
 - f. Carbon Capture usage (CCU) or storage (CCS): 2.2
 - g. Demand reduction: 2.4
- 3. In which sectors do you expect the use of negative emission technologies (multiple choice; number of respondents: 12):**
- a. Power: 5
 - b. Steel: 1
 - c. Cement: 9
 - d. Other industry: 4
 - e. None: 2
- 4. In which sectors do you expect the use of hydrogen technologies (multiple choice; number of respondents: 12):**
- a. Power: 3
 - b. Steel: 12
 - c. Cement: 3
 - d. Chemicals: 11
 - e. Other industry: 1
 - f. Transport: 7
 - g. Buildings: 1
 - h. None: 0
- 5. How will the German (Primary) Energy Consumption evolve taking into consideration the GHG emissions mitigation measures? (Ranking: 2: Will grow, 1: Will not change significantly, 0: Will decrease; number of respondents: 12)**
- a. Total economy: 1.9

b. Industry: 1.8

6. Please assess the importance of the following mitigation strategies/measures for the decarbonizing the industry sectors (ranking: 4: Essential, 3: Important, 2: Moderated; 1: Low; 0: Negligible; number of respondents: 12)

- a. Bio-energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS): 1.5
- b. Biomass: 2
- c. E-Fuels: 1.8
- d. Carbon-free electricity: 3
- e. Fossil fuels with Carbon Capture, Usage or Storage (CCUS): 0.8
- f. Hydrogen: 2.7
- g. Other carbon-free heat: 1.8

9 Annex IV – The “Fit for 55” proposal

Table 32: Large summary of EU legislation update from the "Fit for 55" proposal

Legislation	Reference documents	Synthesis
EU-ETS	European Commission (2021d)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maritime: “The extension of the EU ETS to maritime transport applies in respect of emissions from intra-EU voyages, half of the emissions from extra-EU voyages and emissions occurring at berth in an EU port” • Linear reduction factor and one-off cap reduction: “The linear reduction factor is changed to 4,2 %” and “This ensures that the overall quantity of allowances ('cap') will decline at an increased annual pace resulting in an overall emission reduction of sectors under the EU ETS of 61 % by 2030 compared to 2005.” • Use of auction revenues: “the provision on the use of auction revenues is amended so that the Member States must use all the revenues, to the extent they are not attributed to the Union budget, for climate-related purposes, including to support low-income households’ sustainable renovation.” And “Further, to address the distributional and social effects of the transition, the proposal provides for auctioning an additional 2,5 % of the cap to fund the energy transition of the Member States with GDP per capita below 65 % of the EU average in 2016-2018, through the Modernisation Fund.” • Carbon border adjustment measures: “A Carbon Border Adjustment Measure (CBAM) is an alternative measure to mitigate carbon leakage risks. Sectors and subsectors covered by that measure should therefore not receive a free allocation.” • Introduction of emissions trading for buildings and road transport: “New emissions trading for buildings and road transport should be established as a separate self-standing system from 2025” and “The emissions cap for the new emissions trading system will be set from 2026 based on data collected under the Effort Sharing Regulation and ambition

		<i>level and decrease to reach emission reductions of 43 % in 2030 compared to 2005 for the sectors of buildings and road transport”³³</i>
Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR)	European Commission (2021e)	See Table 34 in Annex IV, for national targets.
Energy Efficiency Directive	European Commission (2021f)	<p>Old targets for EU-28:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1,273 Mtoe of primary energy consumption • 956 Mtoe of final energy consumption <p>Old targets for EU-27:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1,124 Mtoe of primary energy consumption • 864 Mtoe of final energy consumption <p>New targets for EU-27:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1,023 Mtoe of primary energy consumption • 787 Mtoe of final energy consumption
Renewable Energy Directive	European Commission (2021j)	Target: “updated 2030 EU target of at least a 40% share of energy from renewable sources in the Union’s gross final consumption of energy in 2030”

³³ “The total quantity of allowances for the new emissions trading should follow a linear trajectory to reach the 2030 emissions reduction target, taking into account the cost-efficient contribution of buildings and road transport of 43 % emission reductions by 2030 compared to 2005. The total quantity of allowances should be established for the first time in 2026, to follow a trajectory starting in 2024 from the value of the 2024 emissions limits (1,109,304,000 CO₂t), calculated in accordance with Article 4(2) of Regulation (EU) 2018/842 of the European Parliament and of the Council²⁶ on the basis of the reference emissions for these sectors for the period from 2016 to 2018. Accordingly, the linear reduction factor should be set at 5,15 %. From 2028, the total quantity of allowances should be set on the basis of the average reported emissions for the years 2024, 2025 and 2026, and should decrease by the same absolute annual reduction as set from 2024, which corresponds to a 5,43 % linear reduction factor compared to the comparable 2025 value of the above defined trajectory. If those emissions are significantly higher than this trajectory value and if this divergence is not due to small-scale differences in emission measurement methodologies, the linear reduction factor should be adjusted to reach the required emissions reduction in 2030”

<p>LULUCF Regulation</p>	<p>European Commission (2021b)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitments for 2021-2025: <i>"the Member States are committed to ensuring that the greenhouse gas emissions do not exceed removals [...], the "no-debit rule"."</i> • Member States targets for 2026-2030: <i>"the Union target will be set out to reach net removals of 310 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent by 2030 [...] The Union target of 310 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent of net removals will be distributed among the Member States in order to determine binding national targets of minimum net removals to achieve in 2030 according to a table in Annex II."</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>"From 2031 onwards, the LULUCF sector will include the non-CO₂ emissions from the agriculture sector [...] The post-2030 individual targets for the Member States will be the subject to an impact assessment and a new legislative proposal."</i> • See Table 34 in Annex IV for national targets.
<p>Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanisms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission (2021h) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope: <i>"carbon border adjustment mechanism (the 'CBAM') for addressing greenhouse gas emissions embedded in the goods"</i> • Goods concerned (aggregated) and GHG covered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cement: CO₂ ○ Electricity: CO₂ ○ Inorganic Fertilizers: CO₂ and N₂O ○ Iron and Steel: CO₂ ○ Aluminium: CO₂ and PFCs • Exceptions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Non-EU countries participating in EU-ETS (currently: Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland) ○ <i>"The Union may conclude agreements with third countries with a view to take account of carbon pricing mechanisms in these countries"</i> • Calculation of embodied emissions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Simple goods:

$$SEE_g = \frac{AttrEm_g}{AL_g}$$

- Complex goods

$$SEE_g = \frac{AttrEm_g + \sum_{i=1}^n M_i * SEE_i}{AL_g}$$

Where:

SEE_g : Specific embodied emissions in good g.

$AttrEm_g$: Attributed emissions (or direct emissions) to the production of good g.

AL_g : the Activity Level of good g.

M_i : the Mass of input i, used in the production process.

SEE_i : Specific embodied emissions in input i.

<p>CO₂ emissions performance standards for new passenger cars and new light commercial vehicles</p>	<p>European Commission (2021k)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "From 1 January 2030, the following EU fleet-wide targets shall apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ for the average emissions of the new passenger car fleet, an EU fleet-wide target equal to a 55 % reduction of the target in 2021 is determined in accordance with point 6.1.2 of Part A of Annex I; ○ for the average emissions of the new light commercial vehicles fleet, an EU fleet-wide target equal to a 50 % reduction of the target in 2021 determined in accordance with point 6.1.2 of Part B of Annex I." • "From 1 January 2035, the following EU fleet-wide targets shall apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ for the average emissions of the new passenger car fleet, an EU fleet-wide target equal to a 100 % reduction of the target in 2021 is determined in accordance with Part A, point 6.1.3, of Annex I; ○ for the average emissions of the new light commercial vehicles fleet, an EU fleet-wide target equal to a 100 % reduction of the target in 2021 determined in accordance with Part B, point 6.1.3, of Annex I."
<p>Alternative fuel Infrastructure Regulation</p>	<p>European Commission (2021l)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To that end Member States shall ensure that, at the end of each year, starting from the year referred to in Article 24, the following power output targets are met cumulatively: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ for each battery-electric light-duty vehicle registered in their territory, a total power output of at least 1 kW is provided through publicly accessible recharging stations; and

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ for each plug-in hybrid light-duty vehicle registered in their territory, a total power output of at least 0.66 kW is provided through publicly accessible recharging stations. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For additional technical details see the proposal
<p>ReFuelEU Aviation</p>	<p>European Commission (2021m)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Aviation fuel suppliers shall ensure that all aviation fuel made available to aircraft operators at each Union airport contains a minimum share of sustainable aviation fuel, including a minimum share of synthetic aviation fuel in accordance with the values and dates of application set out in Annex I.”</i> • Annex I (volume shares) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ From 1 January 2025, a minimum share of 2% of SAF; ○ From 1 January 2030, a minimum share of 5% of SAF, of which a minimum share of 0.7% of synthetic aviation fuels; ○ From 1 January 2035, a minimum share of 20% of SAF, of which a minimum share of 5% of synthetic aviation fuels; ○ From 1 January 2040, a minimum share of 32% of SAF, of which a minimum share of 8% of synthetic aviation fuels; ○ From 1 January 2045, a minimum volume share of 38% of SAF, of which a minimum share of 11% of synthetic aviation fuels. ○ From 1 January 2050, a minimum volume share of 63% of SAF, of which a minimum share of 28% of synthetic aviation fuels”
<p>FuelEU Maritime</p>	<p>European Commission (2021n)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“The limit referred to in paragraph 1 shall be calculated by reducing the reference value of [X grams of CO₂ equivalent per MJ]* by the following percentage:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ -2% from 1 January 2025; ○ -6% from 1 January 2030; ○ -13% from 1 January 2035; ○ -26% from 1 January 2040; ○ -59% from 1 January 2045;

- **-75% from 1 January 2050.**

- *[Asterix: **The reference value**, which calculation will be carried out at a later stage of the legislative procedure, **corresponds to the fleet average greenhouse gas intensity of the energy used on-board by ships in 2020** determined on the basis of data monitored and reported in the framework of Regulation (EU) 2015/757 and using the methodology and default values laid down in Annex I to that Regulation.]*

Table 33: New national target for GHG reduction between 2030 and 2005 in the ESR sectors

<i>Member State GHG reductions in 2030 in comparison with 2005 (ESR sector)</i>		
	Previous Target	Next target
Belgium	-35%	-47%
Bulgaria	-0%	-10%
Czechia	-14%	-26%
Denmark	-39%	-50%
Germany	-38%	-50%
Estonia	-13%	-24%
Ireland	-30%	-42%
Greece	-16%	-22.7%
Spain	-26%	-37.7%
France	-37%	-47.5%
Croatia	-7%	-16.7%
Italy	-33%	-43.7%
Cyprus	-24%	-32%
Latvia	-6%	-17%
Lithuania	-9%	-21%
Luxembourg	-40%	-50%
Hungary	-7%	-18.7%
Malta	-19%	-19%
Netherlands	-36%	-48%
Austria	-36%	-48%
Poland	-7%	-17.7%
Portugal	-17%	-28.7%
Romania	-2%	-12.7%
Slovenia	-15%	-27%
Slovakia	-12%	-22.7%
Finland	-39%	-50%
Sweden	-40%	-50%

Source: European Commission (2021c)

Table 34: New GHG emissions from LULUCF targets in 2030 by Member State (in ktCO₂eq.)

	Value of the net GHG emissions reduction in ktCO ₂ eq. in 2030
Belgium	-1,352
Bulgaria	-9,718
Czechia	-1,228
Denmark	5,338
Germany	-30,840
Estonia	-2,545
Ireland	3,728
Greece	-4,373
Spain	-43,635
France	-34,046
Croatia	-5,527
Italy	-35,758
Cyprus	-352
Latvia	-644
Lithuania	-4,633
Luxembourg	-403
Hungary	-5,724
Malta	2
Netherlands	4,523
Austria	-5,650
Poland	-38,098
Portugal	-1,358
Romania	-25,665
Slovenia	-146
Slovakia	-6,821
Finland	-17,754
Sweden	-47,321
EU-27	-310,000

Source: European Commission (2021p)

